

MEDICAL UNIVERSITY
OF VIENNA

Statistical Approaches for Handling Complex Correlation Structures in Prediction Modelling

Doctoral thesis at the Medical University of Vienna
for obtaining the academic degree

Doctor of Philosophy

Submitted by

Dipl.-Ing. Dipl.-Ing. Mariella Gloria Gregorich, BSc.

Supervisor:

Ao. Univ.-Prof. Mag. Dr. Georg Heinze

Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Data Science, Medical University of Vienna

Thesis committee members:

Assoc. Prof. Mag. Dr. Daniela Dunkler

Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Data Science, Medical University of Vienna

Prof. Dr. Dr. Kristel Van Steen

Department of Human Genetics, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

GIGA-R Medical Genomics, University of Liège, Liège, Belgium

Vienna, 02/2024

Contents

I	Introduction	1
1.1	Background	2
1.2	Aims of the thesis	4
1.3	Structure of the thesis	6
II	Methods	7
2.1	Correlation and graphical modelling	8
2.2	Statistical modelling	20
III	Publications	31
3.1	Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution	33
3.2	Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods	47
3.3	Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction	65
3.4	Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach	99
IV	Discussion	129
4.1	Summary of contributions and implications	130
4.2	Future prospects and outlook	134
	Bibliography	137
	Appendix	143
	Curriculum Vitae	159

Abstract

Multivariable statistical modelling is widely used to relate health outcomes with a set of explanatory variables. When the set of explanatory variables exhibits complex dependency structures, remedial measures may be required to ensure reliable model estimation, or the interrelated structure can be viewed as an informative attribute of the data reflecting the molecular mechanisms of complex diseases at the system level. This doctoral thesis focuses on statistical approaches intended to handle the complex dependence structures within a set of explanatory variables, in particular within the realm of high-dimensional data in biomedical research. The doctoral thesis is organized around four main contributions. First, we have challenged the established approach of variable omission as a remedy for correlated predictors in statistical modelling and highlighted the importance of being guided by the research question to prevent misusing and inaccurately specifying models in low-dimensional settings. Applied data examples demonstrated the consequences of incorrectly handling the correlated predictors for the main research question. The use of network modelling effectively facilitates the analysis of dependency structures, leading to the second contribution, which encompassed a comprehensive scoping review of various statistical methodologies for individual-specific network inference in prediction modelling. The aforementioned endeavour laid the groundwork for devising the third contribution, a flexible parameterization approach for the values of graph-theoretical features obtained from individual-specific networks with varying degrees of sparseness. Through numerical studies and a case study on brain maturity prediction in children, the efficiency of this method was evaluated in comparison to alternative competitors. In the final contribution, we formally define and examined one-stage and two-stage regularized regression approaches to address correlation and zero inflation in a high-dimensional predictor setting, with a focus on the abilities of the nonnegative garrote approach in identifying a smaller set of prognostic variables while maintaining predictive accuracy. The four project phases led to a body of work that focuses on various dependency structure aspects in statistical modelling.

Zusammenfassung

Multivariable statistische Modellierung ist ein weit verbreitetes Instrument, um Gesundheitsergebnisse mit einer Gruppe von erklärenden Variablen in Beziehung zu setzen. Wenn die Gruppe der erklärenden Variablen komplexe Abhängigkeitsstrukturen aufweist, können entweder Maßnahmen erforderlich werden, um die zuverlässige Modellschätzung zu gewährleisten, oder die Abhängigkeitsstruktur kann als informatives Merkmal der Daten betrachtet werden, das die molekularen Mechanismen komplexer Krankheiten auf Systemebene widerspiegelt. Diese Dissertation konzentriert sich auf statistische Ansätze zur Bewältigung komplexer Abhängigkeitsstrukturen innerhalb einer Gruppe von erklärenden Variablen, insbesondere im Bereich hochdimensionaler Daten in der biomedizinischen Forschung. Die Dissertation ist in vier Hauptbeiträge organisiert. Erstens haben wir den etablierten Ansatz des Variablenausschlusses als Mittel zur Behandlung korrelierter Prädiktoren in der statistischen Modellierung in Frage gestellt und die Bedeutung betont, sich bei der Modellspezifikation in einem niedrigdimensionalen Setting von der Forschungsfrage leiten zu lassen, um Fehlanwendungen und fehlerhafte Modellierung zu vermeiden. Angewandte Datenbeispiele zeigten die Konsequenzen einer falschen Behandlung korrelierter Prädiktoren für die Hauptforschungsfrage auf. Der Einsatz von Netzwerkmodellierung erleichtert effektiv die Analyse von Abhängigkeitsstrukturen und führt zum zweiten Beitrag der Dissertation, der einen umfangreichen systematischen Review verschiedener statistischer Methoden für die Individuen-spezifische Netzwerkinferenz in der Vorhersagemodellierung umfasste. Dieses Unterfangen legte den Grundstein für die Ausarbeitung des dritten Beitrags, einer flexiblen Parametrisierungsmethode für die Werte graphentheoretischer Merkmale, die aus Individuen-spezifischen Netzwerken mit unterschiedlichem Dichtegraden gewonnen wurden. Durch numerische Studien und eine Fallstudie zur Vorhersage der Gehirnreife bei Kindern wurde die Effizienz dieser Methode im Vergleich zu alternativen Konkurrenten untersucht. Im abschließenden Beitrag der Dissertation haben wir explizit einstufige und zweistufige regularisierte Regressionsansätze herausgearbeitet und angewendet, um Korrelation und Null-Inflation in einem hochdimensionalen Prädiktorsetting zu adressieren, wobei der Fokus auf den Fähigkeiten des nicht-negativen Garrote-Ansatzes lag, eine kleinere Menge prognostischer Variablen zu identifizieren und gleichzeitig eine gute Vorhersagegenauigkeit zu erhalten. Die vier Projektphasen führten zu dieser Arbeit, die sich auf verschiedene Aspekte von Abhängigkeitsstrukturen in der statistischen Modellierung konzentriert.

Publications arising from this thesis

The doctoral thesis comprises the following four manuscripts:

- [1] Gregorich M, Strohmaier S, Dunkler D, and Heinze G. Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2021;18:4259.
- [2] Gregorich M, Melograna F, Sunqvist M, Michiels S, Van Steen K, and Heinze G. Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. 2022;22:1–17.
- [3] Gregorich M, Simpson SL, and Heinze G. Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction. *arXiv preprint: 2308.15365*. 2023.
- [4] Gregorich M, Kammer M, Mischak H, and Heinze G. Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach. *arXiv preprint:2402.02064*. 2024

Paper I - The paper *Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution* delves into the common practices employed when dealing with highly correlated predictors in applied regression analysis. It challenges the conventional approach of excluding one or more of the set of correlated predictors from the regression model, highlighting the shortcomings of this method. Instead, we advocate for tailoring the way to address correlated predictors on the conceptual modelling objective.

Paper II - The paper *Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods* provides a systematic scoping review of statistical methodologies for inferring individual-specific networks for prediction modelling and identifies their primary areas of application in practical research. The paper highlights that current practices for network construction often rely on correlation-based approaches, which rely on reliable approaches to achieve network sparsity..

Paper III - The paper *Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction* introduces a novel method for adaptively parameterizing graph-theoretical features derived from individual-specific networks across varying sparsity levels. The proposed approach aims to enhance predictive tasks by assessing the relative leverage of the values of graph-theoretical features, acquired through different network sparsity thresholds, on the outcome. To accomplish this, functional weight functions are incorporated and their determination is guided by statistical goodness-of-fit criteria.

Paper IV - The paper *Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach* examines strategies for dealing with an abundant set of zero-inflated and correlated predictors with the aim of prediction. The paper explicitly defines and evaluates both, one-stage and two-stage penalized regression approaches, with particular attention given to the nonnegative garrote approach to address zero inflation in the predictor variables.

The four papers above were published under an open-access license, therefore publisher permission to include them in this thesis is not required.

Declaration

The work for this thesis was carried out at the Institute of Clinical Biometrics of the Center for Medical Data Science (CeDaS) of the Medical University of Vienna, Austria. The Ph.D. candidate received funding for the project as part of the DOC fellowship from the Austrian Academy of Sciences.

Contributions

The contribution of the author of this thesis (Mariella Gloria Gregorich; MGG) and all co-authors (Georg Heinze, GH; Kristel Van Steen, KVS; Daniela Dunkler, DD; Susanne Strohmaier, SS; Stefan Michiels, SM; Federico Melograna, FM; Martina Sunqvist, MS; Michael Kammer, MK; Sean L. Simpson, SLS; Harald Mischak, HM) to the included articles are stated below.

Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution

MGG and GH contributed to the conceptualization of the work and the structure of the manuscript. MGG conducted the data analysis in R and wrote the initial draft of the manuscript. All authors (MGG, GH, SS, DD) reviewed, edited the manuscript, and agreed to the final version.

Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods

MGG and GH conceived the idea for the manuscript. MGG performed the literature search, along with screening the title, abstract, and full text of all papers identified in the search. FM, MS, and GH carried out the full-text screening for a subset of all articles. MGG was in charge of writing the first draft of the manuscript. All authors (MGG, FM, MS, SM, KVS, GH) of the manuscript reviewed, edited, and agreed on the final version of the manuscript.

Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction

MGG and GH conceived and designed the study. MGG performed the programming in R and C++. MGG acquired and analyzed the data. MGG wrote the initial draft of the manuscript. GH critically revised the manuscript. All authors (MGG, SLS, GH) of the manuscript reviewed, edited, and agreed on the final version of the manuscript.

Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach MGG, MK, and GH contributed to the conceptualization of the work. MGG performed the programming for the simulation study in R and conducted the data analysis of the application. MGG was responsible for writing the initial draft of the manuscript. All authors (MGG, MK, HM, GH) carefully read the manuscript and provided helpful discussions and improvements for the final version of the manuscript.

Additional publications during the PhD

Additional studies that were conducted and published in the course of the PhD:

- [5] Aschauer C, Jelencsics K, Hu K, Heinzl A, Gregorich M, Vetter J, Schaller S, Winkler SM, Weinberger J, Pimenov L, et al. Prospective tracking of donor-reactive T-cell clones in the circulation and rejecting human kidney allografts. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2021;12:750005.
- [6] Gregorich M, Heinzl A, Kammer M, Meiselbach H, Böger C, Eckardt KU, Mayer G, Heinze G, and Oberbauer R. A prediction model for the decline in renal function in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus: study protocol. *Diagnostic and Prognostic Research*. 2021;5:1–9.
- [7] Aschauer C, Jelencsics K, Hu K, Gregorich M, Reindl-Schwaighofer R, Wenda S, Wekerle T, Heinzl A, and Oberbauer R. Effects of reduced-dose anti-human T-lymphocyte globulin on overall and donor-specific T-cell repertoire reconstitution in sensitized kidney transplant recipients. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2022;13:843452.
- [8] Kammer M, Heinzl A, Hu K, Meiselbach H, Gregorich M, Busch M, Duffin KL, Gomez MF, Eckardt KU, and Oberbauer R. Different roles of protein biomarkers predicting eGFR trajectories in people with chronic kidney disease and diabetes mellitus: a nationwide retrospective cohort study. *Cardiovascular Diabetology*. 2023;22:1–10.
- [9] Gregorich M, Kammer M, Heinzl A, Böger C, Eckardt KU, Heerspink HL, Jung B, Mayer G, Meiselbach H, Schmid M, et al. Development and Validation of a Prediction Model for Future Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate in People With Type 2 Diabetes and Chronic Kidney Disease. *JAMA Network Open*. 2023;6:e231870–e231870.

Acknowledgments

“We are drowning in information and starving for knowledge.”

— Rutherford D. Roger

First and foremost, I want to thank my supervisor Georg Heinze, whose guidance and support have been invaluable throughout my academic journey. His mentorship and insightful feedback have contributed to the development and completion of this thesis. Furthermore, I extend my sincere appreciation to all my collaborators involved in the papers included in this doctoral thesis. The fruitful discussions and input have not only facilitated new insights but also enriched the quality of the work and improved the papers. My special thanks go to Rainer Oberbauer for enabling me to embark on my PhD journey. Through collaboration with the researchers from the Division of Nephrology and Dialysis, I have not only acquired skills in statistical modelling beyond my doctoral research focus but also found great fulfillment in working on applied projects and in a team.

I also would like to thank all my colleagues at the Institute for Clinical Biometrics for their valuable support, advice, and many helpful conversations. In particular, I want to thank Michael Kammer, whose open-door policy and helpful advice have been a constant source of support and with whom I have enjoyed working these years. In addition, I would also like to thank my colleagues from our "neighboring" Institute of Medical Statistics for the many great conversations, shared experiences, and of course the social gatherings over the last years.

A heartfelt appreciation extends to my family, longstanding friends, and the new friends that I came to know during my PhD, who have always been there to offer moral and emotional support, especially during challenging phases.

I

Introduction

1.1 Background

Statistical learning from medical data is constantly challenged by the variety of data structures it encounters. In recent decades, there has been a significant increase in efforts to invent and evaluate statistical learning techniques to support the development of models that provide predictions tailored to an individual's distinct set of attributes. A research area commonly referred to as personalized medicine. The surge in research has been fuelled by advances in biotechnology, resulting in the generation of high-dimensional data sets with extensive information about each individual in the study cohort.

Multivariable statistical models are often used to explore the relationship between a health outcome and a set of explanatory variables. However, many of the measured variables display strong interrelationships indicated by the inherent correlational structures arising from the underlying group structure between biological entities. This leads to the tendency of fluctuations in value to occur in conjunction with changes in other variables, posing challenges for traditional statistical modelling. These issues are particularly relevant in high-dimensional datasets, such as in the area of omics which refers to disciplines like proteomics, metabolomics, genomics, and others that aim to comprehensively study biological molecules or entities within a system. To effectively navigate the landscape of highly correlated variables in statistical modelling, several methodologies and analyzing strategies have been proposed to ensure the appropriate handling, including variable selection, regularization methods, and clustering techniques for dimensionality reduction. The use of such techniques can help mitigate the adverse impact of correlated variables and improve the overall (predictive) performance and interpretability of statistical models. Whilst the challenges posed by complex correlation structures are widely acknowledged, the proper handling remains an unresolved matter. Remedies can generally be categorized into two camps: remove or keep. While the former views correlated variables as redundant information, the latter capitalizes on the correlational structure as an insightful aspect of the data with the premise that it can enhance predictions of clinical endpoints. These two facets give rise to the papers that are included in this doctoral thesis and will be further elaborated on in the subsequent sections.

Remove. Statistical variable selection approaches based on regularized regression or other sophisticated model selection techniques are widely used to identify a subset of biomarkers, in particular in situations where the number of variables exceeds the sample size ($p > n$ scenario). Variable selection aims to distinguish between the true variables with predictive value and the noise variables that possess little to no predictive value. In simpler terms, the objective is to identify the variables that (collectively) best explain and predict changes in the outcome variable. Many regularization-based variable selection methods have been

developed over the past decades. However, the problem of variable selection is exacerbated when highly correlated variables are included in the covariate set [10]. Such methods provide a sparse solution, which increases interpretability, but it is unclear whether they handle the relational structure of the data properly. While some authors advocate for preconditioning the variables before statistical modelling by transforming the given data matrix and/or the outcome vector before conducting regularized regression [11, 12] or modify the regularization term of statistical models [13], it may be advantageous to rely on prior background knowledge for the initial selection of variables as recommended by Heinze et al. [10]. In situations where background knowledge is missing or unreliable, the use of regularization-based techniques that can perform variable selection is crucial in identifying relevant variables.

Keep. While it is common to search for a concise list of predictive variables, previous research in the field has shown that biological entities often interact and function as a system [14]. Graphs, also called networks, have the ability to describe these complex systems as mutually dependent components in an assembled unit and thus capture the relational information between variables as opposed to the traditional vector-based representation. This viewpoint has given rise to the emergence of the field of network medicine [15]. In particular, the analysis of group-level networks, including protein-protein interaction networks, metabolomic networks, and gene co-expression networks, which derive a network from the whole cohort or one for each subgroup of a cohort (e.g. healthy individuals and those with a condition), has proven to be an important approach for extracting meaningful insights from relational data [14, 15]. However, these networks neglect the heterogeneity among individuals which can be valuable for prediction. The inference of individual-specific networks in which we obtain a distinct network for each individual in the study cohort resolves this issue and makes use of the otherwise challenging data property of many highly correlated variables by inferring correlation-based networks. They have the same set of nodes in common but deviate in terms of the edge weights. For example, an individual in poor health is likely to deviate from the group-level network behavior. Individual-specific networks have already been proven informative for prediction, particularly in neurological studies, for example, for the diagnosis of Alzheimer’s disease [16], the prognosis of the performance in a memory task based on individual brain networks [17] or the estimation of brain maturity for the study of neurodevelopmental disorders [18, 19]. The main challenge is to accurately capture the relational structure and translate that information into practical insights. To achieve this, methodological gaps in research practice must be addressed and reproducibility ensured.

1.2 Aims of the thesis

This thesis explores innovative statistical methods for incorporating data structures from observational studies that are high-dimensional and intricately correlated to examine how knowledge obtained from complex dependencies can augment predictive performance and provide clinical insights. We challenge the current practice of arbitrarily omitting correlated variables and instead focus on individual-specific network inference for predictive modelling. We assessed conventional regularized regression techniques for variable selection, addressing additional obstacles in biomedical research such as zero inflation and high dimensionality. The thesis provides a comprehensive review of statistical concepts used in the papers, aiming to generate evidence on handling correlated variables and introduce novel modelling techniques that leverage data relations. The overarching objectives of the thesis are as follows:

Aim I: Is variable omission a good default solution for handling highly correlated variables?

The issue of collinearity in empirical research is a common yet frequently overlooked concern for researchers in applied fields. Assessing the potential problem of collinearity often entails employing several diagnostic tools such as the calculation of correlation coefficients, the variance inflation factor, or the condition number [20]. When these diagnostics yield low values, the model is assumed to be 'problem-free', while in contrast, high values of the diagnostic tools presumably indicate the need for modifications of the model-building strategy with a default solution often conducted being variable omission. However, excluding one or more of the set of highly correlated variables may not be a universally applicable remedy for all modelling objectives, whether they aim to describe, predict, or explain. Therefore, we aimed to demonstrate that variable omission is not a good default solution, as detailed in Paper I. For instance, in explanatory modelling, it may be necessary to consider confounding variables, despite their high correlation to adequately address the research question. Similarly, we aimed to demonstrate that the diagnostic tools can also fail to guide the applied researcher, even when near-collinearity negatively affects the model's predictive accuracy. Therefore, the first objective addressed in Paper I was to emphasize the importance of the modelling objective when collinearity is detected, to guide the model-building strategy.

Aim II: Can the correlational structure between variables be explicitly taken into account to improve prediction modelling?

Traditionally, variables have been individually included in analyses, assuming that a single variable would predominantly explain the observed variability in the outcome of interest. However, with advancing comprehension of biological systems, there's a growing be-

lie among researchers that the diverse variability in structural and topological attributes describing such complex systems could offer additional value to conventional statistical modelling. This shift in understanding suggests that an individual’s variability in network structure might hold significance for personalized prognosis or diagnosis, especially considering that single cellular features obtained from high-throughput sequencing or high-resolution imaging are seldom directly linked to disease development or progression, but rather the malfunction of the system usually serves as an indicator. Therefore, we aimed to investigate state-of-the-art methodologies in inferring individual-specific networks and their primary areas of application, prompting the conduct of a comprehensive scoping review described in Paper II.

Throughout the scoping review process, we identified several methodological gaps in the current research practice. Specifically, network sparsification suffers from a notable lack of consensus, in particular in correlation-based network inference. This finding motivated the idea to incorporate a flexible weighting function for the values of graph-theoretical features linked to threshold parameters across the complete spectrum of the threshold sequence such that the relative leverage of a graph-theoretical feature at each threshold is taken into account and an ill-informed a-priori selected threshold is avoided. Therefore, in Paper III, we aimed to evaluate the proposed flexible parametrization approach and compare it with current state-of-the-art approaches in a plasmode simulation study [21, 22] and an applied data example for the prediction of brain maturity in children.

Aim III: How can a concise selection of prognostic biomarkers be attained, given a large number of predictors that are both correlated and zero-inflated?

A classical approach to handle high-dimensional and correlated variables in prediction modelling is by performing variable selection. Therefore, the third aim focused on the investigation of one-stage and two-stage regularised regression approaches with a focus on predictive performance and predictor selection. As data acquisition in omics fields can be cumbersome, time-consuming, and expensive due to the abundance of variables measured, often the objective in prediction modelling is to obtain not only a model with good predictive performance but also to end up with a parsimonious set of variables such that the model can be easily generalized to new cohorts. We opted to assess regularized regression approaches in mass-spectrometry data which presented an additional challenge due to the excess of zero values in the candidate predictors (zero inflation). In particular, our focus was to highlight the capabilities of the nonnegative garrote method in terms of predictive accuracy and identifying a concise selection of predictors. We also compared it to established one-stage competitors, such as ridge and lasso, as well as two-stage regularized regression approaches like a ridge-lasso and a lasso-ridge combination. Overall, our objective was to formally define and examine how these approaches perform in addressing both correlation challenges and the excess of zero values among variables.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

The remainder of this doctoral thesis is structured as follows: Chapter I provides relevant background information on statistical concepts and methodologies for comprehending the four manuscripts forming this doctoral thesis. The research presented here falls within three main topic categories: correlation analysis, graphical modelling, and statistical modelling. The background information in these three categories has been meticulously curated to establish the theoretical foundation for the four manuscripts. However, it's important to note that these sections serve as a comprehensive summary of the statistical topics within the constraints of this thesis. Therefore, we will delve into these areas, with particular emphasis on aspects relevant to the papers at hand, while directing interested readers to more extensive literature for further information.

Chapter III forms the core of the thesis comprising the four manuscripts in chronological order. In Section 3.1, Paper I titled *“Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution”* provides an introductory work on the topic of correlation by challenging the current practice in handling correlated variables. In Section 3.2, Paper II titled *“Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods”* provides a comprehensive overview of the statistical methodology for individual-specific network inference. Proceeding this, Paper III titled *“Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction”* in Section 3.3 highlights our flexible parametrization approach that includes graph-theoretical features at different network density levels, thereby enhancing the accuracy of a prediction modelling. Lastly, Paper IV titled *“Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach”* covers the use of regularization-based techniques for selecting variables in cases where variables are correlated and zero-inflated in Section 3.4. In Chapter IV, we conclude with some final remarks, methodological recommendations of the proposed approaches, and an outlook on possible extensions of this research. Appendix A encompasses all supplementary online materials for the papers found in Chapter III, while Appendix B comprises the curriculum vitae of the doctoral candidate.

II

Methods

2.1 Correlation and graphical modelling

The measurement of marginal or conditional relationships between random variables is at the heart of multivariate statistics and is therefore of immense importance in all empirical fields. Despite the simplicity of the concept, it plays a central role as an initial approach to assess the extent and nature of relationships between variables, provide essential information on variable groupings, and guide the selection of an appropriate analytical approach for further steps. Here, we will use uppercase Roman characters (e.g. X , Y) to represent random variables and lowercase (e.g., x , y) to indicate the specific values taken on by these random variables.

2.1.1 The correlation coefficient: A conceptual introduction

In statistical terms, the degree of association between two scalar random variables X and Y can be measured by a numerical statistic referred to as the correlation coefficient $\rho(X, Y)$. The most commonly used correlation coefficient assumes a linear relationship between the scalar random variables and is called Pearson's correlation coefficient [23].

Consider two continuous random variables X and Y with finite variances, then a measure of linear dependence between X and Y is given by the Pearson product-moment correlation

$$\rho_P(X, Y) = \frac{\text{cov}(X, Y)}{\sigma_X \sigma_Y}, \quad (2.1.1)$$

where $\text{cov}(X, Y)$ is the population covariance between X and Y where $\text{cov}(X, Y) = \mathbb{E}(X, Y) - \mathbb{E}(X)\mathbb{E}(Y)$ with \mathbb{E} denoting the expected value. The parameters σ_X and σ_Y denote the population standard deviation of X and Y defined as $\sigma = \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[X^2] - (\mathbb{E}[X])^2}$. The sample Pearson correlation $r_P(x, y)$ between two observed continuous variables x and y is given by

$$r_P(x, y) = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{\sqrt{[n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2][n \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^2]}}. \quad (2.1.2)$$

The value of the coefficient ranges between -1 and $+1$ and indicates a positive relationship when in the range $(0, 1]$, while a coefficient in $[-1, 0)$ indicates a negative relationship. While the Pearson correlation coefficient is widely used for measuring linear relationships, it lacks robustness in the case of non-linearity and high-leverage outliers. A non-parametric alternative for non-linear relationships is Spearman's rank correlation coefficient $\rho_S(X, Y)$ [24]. Spearman's correlation coefficient follows the definition of Pearson's correlation coefficient for the ranking of values, R_X and R_Y , between two variables, rather than the raw values, hence it is given by $\rho_S(X, Y) = \rho_P(R_X, R_Y)$. If no ties are present, the empirical statistic for the Spearman's correlation coefficient between two observed variables x and y

consisting of n observations is equivalent to

$$r_S(x, y) = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad (2.1.3)$$

where d_i denotes the difference in ranks between values of x and y [24].

The correlation is not only a measure of the strength but also the direction of the dependence between X and Y . In the case of perfect linear dependence, it holds that $Y = aX + b$ or $P[Y = aX + b] = 1$ for $a, b \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$. In the case of independence, it holds that

$$X \perp\!\!\!\perp Y \implies \text{cov}(X, Y) = 0 \implies \rho(X, Y) = 0, \quad (2.1.4)$$

meaning that the independence (denoted by $\perp\!\!\!\perp$) of two random variables X and Y implies them to be uncorrelated. However, the reverse generally does not hold. For example, the two random variables $X \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and $Y = X^2$ are not independent, yet they exhibit zero correlation. This is because their covariance is zero, owing to the symmetry of the standard normal distribution and the fact that its third moment is zero [25].

Extending correlation to a random vector $\mathbb{X} = (X_1, \dots, X_p)$ is easily achieved by the arrangement of all pairwise correlation coefficients in a symmetrical matrix. Consider the random vector \mathbb{X} with X_j and X_k denoting two scalar random variables, $j, k = 1, \dots, p$, then the $p \times p$ -dimensional correlation matrix ρ with entries ρ_{jk} is defined by

$$\rho_{jk} := \rho(X_j, X_k) \quad j, k = 1, \dots, p. \quad (2.1.5)$$

Similarly, the entries of the covariance matrix Σ have the form

$$\Sigma_{jk} := \text{cov}(X_j, X_k) \quad j, k = 1, \dots, p. \quad (2.1.6)$$

When dealing with three or more variables, an interesting question is the relationship between X_j and X_k while accounting for the impact of the remaining random variables $\mathbb{X} \setminus \{X_j, X_k\}$. Partial correlation measures the degree of linear dependence among a group of random variables while adjusting for the linear effect of other confounding variables [26]. We will denote the partial correlation coefficient between the variables X_j and X_k by $\pi_{jk} := \pi(X_j, X_k | \mathbb{X} \setminus \{X_j, X_k\})$, where $\mathbb{X} \setminus \{X_j, X_k\} = \{X_m : m = 1, \dots, p, m \neq j, m \neq k\}$ and $\hat{\pi}$ for its empirical representation.

Consider a setting where our data are given by the $n \times p$ matrix $\mathbf{X} = [x_1, \dots, x_p]$ obtained by stacking the n independently, and identically distributed (i.i.d.) observations given by $p \times 1$ -dimensional vectors $x_j = (x_{1j}, \dots, x_{nj})^T$ for $j = 1, \dots, p$. There are multiple ways to compute the partial correlation coefficient but we will specifically concentrate

on the two most prevalent approaches.

1. **Correlation of prediction error.** In the first approach, multiple multivariable regression models are employed among all variables, using each variable x_j , $j = 1, \dots, p$ once as the outcome variable and all $(p - 1)$ remaining variables as independent regressors. Each regression model can be written as

$$x_j = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}x_1 + \dots + \beta_{(j-1)j}x_{j-1} + \beta_{(j+1)j}x_{j+1} + \dots + \beta_{pj}x_p + \epsilon_j, \quad (2.1.7)$$

where $\beta_j = (\beta_{0j}, \beta_{1j}, \dots, \beta_{(j-1)j}, \beta_{(j+1)j}, \dots, \beta_{pj})$ is the p -dimensional regression coefficients of the j th model with the intercept β_{0j} and ϵ_j is the error terms of the j th model. Alternatively, it can be written in matrix notation as

$$x_j = \mathbf{X}_{-j} + \epsilon_j \quad (2.1.8)$$

with \mathbf{X}_{-j} denoting the matrix without the j th column. The partial correlation coefficient is the empirical Pearson correlation coefficient r between the residuals (prediction errors) [27, 28]:

$$\hat{\pi}_{jk} = r_P(\epsilon_j, \epsilon_k) \quad j, k = 1, \dots, p \text{ and } j \neq k. \quad (2.1.9)$$

2. **Matrix inversion.** If Σ is the covariance matrix of the Gaussian random vector \mathbb{X} , then the partial correlation coefficient can be computed from the (standardized) inverse of the variance-covariance matrix $\Omega = \Sigma^{-1}$ by

$$\pi_{jk} = \frac{\Omega_{jk}}{\sqrt{\Omega_{jj}\Omega_{kk}}}, \quad (2.1.10)$$

where Ω is called the precision or concentration matrix [26, 27].

2.1.2 Graphs and network modelling

Graphs or networks are a natural choice in the representation of high-dimensional systems encoding the relational data structure between the variables as nodes and edges. Formally, a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a mathematical object consisting of a finite set of nodes or vertices V linked by edges denoted by the set $E \subseteq V \times V$, where E comprises all unordered pairs of distinct nodes $(v_j, v_k) \in E$ for $v_j, v_k \in V$ and $j \neq k$ [26]. Within the scope of this thesis, we will only consider simple graphs, excluding networks with loops (i.e. edges connecting the same node at both ends), directed networks (i.e. $(v_j, v_k) \neq (v_k, v_j)$), and multi-edges (i.e. multiple edges between the same pair of nodes). Further, we focus on networks with nodes representing measured variables and not other entities, while the edges encode

the marginal or conditional dependency structure between the variables. The dependency structure of a graph is encoded in its matrix representation also referred to as the $p \times p$ -dimensional adjacency matrix $\mathbf{A} = [w_{jk}]_{j,k=1,\dots,p}$, where $w_{jk} := w(v_j, v_k)$ denotes the edge weights [29]. A non-zero value of an edge weight indicates the presence of an edge (i.e. $w_{jk} \neq 0 \Leftrightarrow (v_j, v_k) \in E$), while a zero value marks the absence. In a correlation-based graph, the graph's structure is entirely determined by the correlation matrix such that $w_{jk} = \rho(X_j, X_k)$ for $j, k = 1, \dots, p$, which defines the adjacency matrix A [29]. Due to the exclusion of graphs with loops, it follows that $w_{jk} = 0$. While the terms "graph" and "network" are often used interchangeably, hereafter, we will use the term 'network' for the practical implementation of a graph, devoid of theoretical abstraction. In an applied context, the set of nodes corresponds to the set of observed variables in a given data set.

In the past decades, the growing demand for a comprehensive understanding of human disease mechanisms has led to the development of a general theory and several application frameworks centered around group-level networks, as outlined by Barabási et al. [15]. Group-level network inference involves the estimation of a statistical network model using aggregated data from the entire study cohort or one network for each specified subgroup in the study cohort (e.g. healthy individuals and those with a condition). This results in one or more networks that capture the overall structure and topology of the entire cohort or a subgroup. Recently, the representation of individual patient data as individual-specific networks has garnered fresh interest within the realm of personalized medicine [2]. Contrary to group-level networks, individual-specific network inference involves the estimation of a unique network for each person in the study cohort. This approach encapsulates the heterogeneity of individual-specific system behavior of biological entities (see Figure 2.1.1 for an illustration). In the upcoming sections, we will provide a brief introduction to network inference, with a particular focus on individual-specific network inference rather than group-level network inference due to the emphasis on the former in Papers II and III.

Figure 2.1.1: Visual representation illustrating network inference on the individual and the group level. In the former, unique personalized networks with identical sets of nodes across the study cohort but varying edge weights are inferred for each individual, while in the latter, a network is estimated based on the aggregated data of the study cohort.

Group-level network inference

With advances in high-throughput biotechnology generating an abundance of biomedical data, group-level network inference has become a powerful tool for inferring the dependency structure that connects biological molecular entities, such as metabolites, genes, or peptides, from aggregated observational data. A graphical model is a statistical model associated with a graph [30]. In its simplest form, a group-level network model can be estimated using the measurements of a set of variables to deduce the relationships between variable pairs through marginal correlation. Following the definition in Equation 2.1.5, the set of edges is defined as $E = \{(v_j, v_k) \in V^{(2)} : \rho_{jk} \neq 0\}$ where v_j, v_k denote elements of V such that the presence of an edge is given for non-zero correlations. Thus, the entries of the adjacency matrix are defined by $w_{jk} := \rho(X_j, X_k)$, $j, k = 1, \dots, p$ with ρ either being Pearson's or Spearman's correlation coefficient.

Two variables X_j and X_k may be strongly correlated but could be affected by a third node, making it difficult to interpret the link as a direct relationship. In Section 2.1.1, we discussed partial correlation which is completely encoded in the precision matrix, $\mathbf{\Omega} = \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}$ as described in Equation 2.1.10. The interesting aspect of this graphical model lies in the fact that when all variables follow a joint Gaussian distribution, the partial correlation between two variables being zero corresponds to the conditional independence given all other variables, i.e. $\pi_{jk} = 0 \equiv X_j \perp\!\!\!\perp X_k | \mathbb{X} \setminus \{X_j, X_k\}$ for $j, k = 1, \dots, p$ [26]. The approach is known as Gaussian graphical modelling (GGM). An edge (v_j, v_k) will be present in the graph G only if the variable X_j is dependent on X_k conditional on all other variables in $V \setminus \{j, k\}$. In practice, GGM is employed to infer gene regulatory network structures [31, 32], understand functional brain connectivity networks [16, 33], and explore symptom networks in psychopathology [34]. Estimating $\mathbf{\Omega}$ can be challenging when the sample size n is comparable to or smaller than the number of variables p , leading to a numerically unstable or non-invertible estimator. To address this issue, the maximum likelihood estimation of the precision matrix can be extended using a penalty term. For further information, please refer to the tutorial on GGM by Shutta et al. [35].

Individual-specific network inference

A drawback of group-level network inference is that it neglects the individual-specific heterogeneity that characterizes a clinical condition, as a diseased subject may diverge from the average healthy system behavior. The rapid development of high-throughput technologies has led to a growing interest in using molecular individual-specific networks to study human diseases, such that the development of novel approaches could even further enhance our understanding of complex disease mechanisms and personalized treatment regimens. Thus, the subsequent section offers an overview of the concept of individual-

specific network inference. For an in-depth introduction, we direct readers to Paper II of this doctoral thesis, titled *Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods* in which, we conducted an extensive systematic search to evaluate existing methodologies for individual-specific network inference and identify the primary domains of application [2].

We define an individual-specific network as a network that describes the system behavior among entities (e.g. peptides, genes, anatomical regions in the brain) observed and measured for an individual. Additionally, we will confine the theory to individual-specific networks that share the same set of nodes for all individuals in the study cohort, while only edge weights vary across individuals. The nodes within individual-specific networks may not align in some applications, as observed in the analysis of the human immune cell repertoires [5, 36]. While individual-specific network inference in neuroscience has been well established for decades, see [16, 17, 37–39], the development of individual-specific networks theory and application in other fields such as cancer research, see [40–42], or other medical fields, see [43, 44], is recent, as evidenced by Figure 2.1.2.

Figure 2.1.2: The number of publications on PubMed up until 2023 using the search query (A) "brain network" and (B) "individual-specific networks" OR "sample-specific networks" OR "patient-specific networks" OR "personalized networks" OR "single-sample networks" OR "subject-specific networks NOT "brain" in the title or abstract (accessed on February 5th, 2024)

The method of estimating correlation matrices is commonly used to infer individual-specific networks when there are repeated measurements per variable and individual available. This is particularly evident in the context of non-invasive neuroimaging analysis e.g. in functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) in which time series data for the blood oxygen level-dependent (BOLD) signals from different regions of interest (ROIs) in the human brain are recorded [45]. The data is analyzed using pairwise correlations to determine links between ROIs. Nevertheless, in situations where every individual has just one measurement per variable available, GGM has been recently extended to estimate individual-specific brain connectivity networks through adjustment of the edge weights by observed demographic and clinical covariates [46, 47].

For high-throughput sequencing and co-expression data (e.g. in the field of omics), which often lack repeated and temporal measurements, two methods for inferring individual-specific networks have been recently introduced:

1. Jackknife network inference or leave-one-out principle. The approach, introduced by Kuijjer et al. [48] in 2019, estimates an individual-specific network by quantifying the edge-weight perturbations observed when that individual is removed from the group-level network estimation. Hence, estimation follows the leave-one-out principle to quantify an individual’s relative contribution to the group-level network. In mathematical terms, consider the matrix $\mathbf{X} = [x_1, \dots, x_p]$ representing a dataset with p variables with each column $x_j = (x_{j1}, \dots, x_{jn})^T$ comprising n observations. The variables $x_j, x_k, j, k = 1, \dots, p$ are represented by the nodes $v_j, v_k, j, k = 1, \dots, p$. The weights can be computed by correlation such that $w_{jk} = r(x_j, x_k)$ for $j, k = 1, \dots, p$, where w_{jk} represents the edge weights of the group-level network derived from all n samples, while $w_{jk}^{(n-i)}$ denotes the edge weight of the group-level network when individual i is excluded. Each individual-specific edge weight $w_{jk}^{(i)}, i = 1, \dots, n$, is calculated through linear interpolation using the formula

$$w_{jk}^{(i)} = \kappa(w_{jk}^{(n)} - w_{jk}^{(n-i)}) + w_{jk}^{(n-i)}, \quad (2.1.11)$$

where the parameter κ is a scaling parameter that is usually set to $\kappa = n$. The algorithm is named Linear Interpolation to Obtain Network Estimates for Single-Samples (LIONESS) [48].

2. Differential network inference or differential perturbation analysis. The approach, introduced by Liu et al. [40] in 2016, estimates an individual-specific network through a statistical perturbation analysis that compares a single sample against a set of provided control samples. This process necessitates a group-level network derived from a reference cohort independent of the study cohort. The perturbation of edge weights caused by an individual is calculated by establishing a group-level network for the reference cohort and another for the same cohort augmented with the individual (the so-called perturbed network), then computing the difference between the two networks. Thus, in addition to the given study cohort of n individuals by the $n \times p$ matrix \mathbf{X} , a reference cohort with a $n_R \times p$ matrix \mathbf{X}_R comprising n_R i.i.d. observations must be available. Then, $w_{jk}^{(n_R)}$ denotes the edge weight of the group-level network of the reference cohort comprising n_R individuals, while $w_{jk}^{(n_R+i)}$ denotes the group-level network based on the reference cohort augmented by individual i . The individual-specific edge weight $w_{jk}^{(i)}$ is then calculated by the difference

$$w_{jk}^{(i)} = w_{jk}^{(n_R+i)} - w_{jk}^{(n_R)}. \quad (2.1.12)$$

Both methods, the Jackknife and the differential network inference approach, do not depend

on the specific approach used to estimate the group-level networks. The only requirement is that the resulting networks must contain scalar edge weights, which allow for interpolation and subtraction between the edge weights to derive the individual-specific networks [40, 48]. However, one drawback of both approaches is that they do not directly infer individual-specific networks but rather implicitly derive them by assessing an individual’s relative contribution to the group-level network structure.

2.1.3 Graph-theoretical features and network types

Network science has developed a range of statistical and mathematical measures to uncover fundamental aspects of network structure and topology. In this section, we will elaborate on the most important quantities and concepts in more depth, without aiming to comprehensively cover all metrics.

Graph-theoretical features can provide insights into local or global attributes of the network topology and structure. A local feature relates to an attribute of a node or a small subset of nodes, while a global graph-theoretical feature describes an attribute that concerns the full set of nodes or edges of the network. Notably, many local features can be converted into global features by averaging across all nodes or edges. The size of a network is inherently a global feature, defined by the cardinality of the node set, denoted as $|V|$. Since we will only consider networks in which each node v_j represents uniquely one observed variable x_j for $j = 1, \dots, p$, it follows that $|V| = p$. The density of a network quantifies the proportion of edges present in the network relative to the number of possible edges and can be computed by

$$den(G) = \frac{|E|}{|V|(|V| - 1)/2} = \frac{2|E|}{p(p - 1)}, \quad (2.1.13)$$

where the denominator is the number of all possible edges, $|V|(|V| - 1)/2$, and the numerator, $|E|$, is the number of present edges in a network. The density lies within the interval $[0, 1]$ [29].

Commonly used features to represent both local and global attributes include the degree distribution, the characteristic path length, and the clustering coefficient [2]. In an undirected and unweighted network, the degree of a node is simply the number of edges attached to the node $d_j := deg(v_j) = \sum_{k=1}^p A_{jk}$, while in a directed network the degree can be differentiated with regard to the direction of the edge (in-degree d_j^{in} and out-degree d_j^{out}) [29]. The degree distribution is the probability distribution of the degrees over the network. For a weighted network, the edge weights are added up and referred to as the node’s strength. The characteristic path length cpl of an unweighted network is the average of the shortest distance $dist(v_j, v_k)$, for $v_j, v_k \in V$ between all pairs of nodes $(v_j, v_k) \in E$

given by

$$cpl = \frac{1}{|V|} \sum_{i \neq j} dist(v_j, v_k), \quad (2.1.14)$$

where finding the shortest distance between a pair of nodes $dist(v_j, v_k)$ is a common problem with various algorithms (i.e. Dijkstra's algorithm [49]) designed to provide a solution [50]. Last but not least, the clustering coefficient measures the likelihood of two nodes connected to the same node also being connected. It is determined for a single node v_j by calculating the ratio of all potential triples to the number of all closed triples where a triple refers to a set of three nodes, termed closed if they all are interconnected. For a binary unweighted network, the global clustering coefficient has the form

$$cc = \frac{1}{|V|} \sum_{j=1}^p cc_j \text{ with } cc_j = \frac{diag(\mathbf{A})_j^3}{d_j(d_j - 1)}, \quad (2.1.15)$$

where d_j denotes the degree, cc_j the local clustering coefficient of node v_j and $diag(\mathbf{A})_j$ the j th diagonal element of the matrix \mathbf{A} [51]. The clustering coefficient quantifies the tendency of clustering within the network and lies between 0 and 1, with high values indicating densely connected nodes in the network. In the context of a weighted network, the generalization for some graph-theoretical features is straightforward, e.g. like degree to strength. However, extending the clustering coefficient to weighted networks proves challenging due to variations in incorporating the weight of triangles and neighboring nodes, a topic extensively examined by Saramäki et al. [52] and Wang et al. [51].

Further aspects of network analysis explore the extent to which subsets of nodes tend to form closely-knit or cohesive connection patterns based on the given edge conditions. The interpretation of these patterns largely relies on the specific context. For instance, in the realm of protein-protein interaction networks, a densely interconnected set of nodes may characterize proteins collaborating closely [29]. These interconnected nodes form 'communities,' which are groups of nodes with a higher likelihood of connections within the group than with nodes outside the group. An important research area of network analysis is dedicated to community detection, emphasizing that meaningful insights often emerge from communities within the network and not the study of the full network [33, 53].

Several noteworthy types of networks can be highlighted, distinguished by their set of specific attributes and statistical properties related to network organization, connectivity, and structure:

- A random network, introduced by Erdős and Rényi [54], describes a network in which all nodes are linked to each other with the same probability.
- A small-world network, introduced by Watts and Strogatz [55], describes a network with densely connected groups of nodes (high clustering coefficient), and a short

distance between any given pair of nodes in the network (low characteristic path length).

- A scale-free network, introduced by Barabási and Albert [56], describes a network with preferential attachment, meaning that the degree distribution of the network follows a power law, i.e. a node of degree d is of the probability $p(d) \sim d^{-\gamma}$ where γ is a parameter in the interval $(2, 3)$.

For a thorough examination and overview of different graphical models, we refer to Kocaczyk and Csárdi [29].

2.1.4 Sparsity in graphical modelling

Network inference aims to estimate a representative network based on observed data which involves both network construction and, at times, network sparsification. Network sparsification refers to the process of determining which edges to keep or remove based on certain thresholding criteria or statistical measures. The reasoning behind this process is manifold. In certain areas of application, the networks might be too dense for the effective application of graph-theoretical methods because the computational workload increases with the growing number of nodes and potential edges in the network. Further, in some scenarios, it is justifiable to presume that the actual system is sparse. For example, genetic networks are often considered sparse with only a few hub nodes having numerous interactions [14]. Therefore, some edges are likely to be a result of sampling variation and are considered noise. For instance, it is improbable for the empirical correlation coefficient to be exactly zero, making it challenging to infer the absence of an edge in the network. Lastly, network sparsification may be needed for a more comprehensible network visualization.

Edges with small weights are often deemed spurious and assumed to be uninformative to the true system structure. Many studies have conducted network analysis by setting a-priori threshold parameters to binarize or truncate the edge weights, leading to reduced density of the final network [2, 57]. While threshold values can theoretically range widely within biologically meaningful limits, the crucial aspect for leveraging network analysis in prediction modeling is ensuring that the chosen threshold optimally captures the informative structure relevant to the observed variability in the outcome variable. The most common thresholding approaches are density-based thresholding and weight-based thresholding. The former keeps a certain percentage of the strongest links, while the latter eliminates all edges below a specified cut-off to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. Omission of edges refers to the process of setting the edge weight to zero such that $w_{jk} = 0 \Leftrightarrow (v_j, v_k) \notin E$. Based on the predefined threshold, edge weights are either (i) truncated or (ii) binarized, i.e. choosing an arbitrary cut-off τ such that the weights in the adjacency matrix \mathbf{A} are defined either by

$$(i) \tilde{w}_{jk} = \begin{cases} w_{jk}, & w_{jk} \geq \tau \\ 0, & w_{jk} < \tau \end{cases} \quad \text{or} \quad (ii) \tilde{w}_{jk} = \begin{cases} 1, & w_{jk} \geq \tau \\ 0, & w_{jk} < \tau \end{cases}. \quad (2.1.16)$$

However, relying on an incorrect a-priori chosen threshold value τ can later largely reduce the predictive power of the graph-theoretical features assumed to be associated with an outcome of interest. Figure 2.1.3 illustrates the individual-specific variability in the clustering coefficient as weight-based thresholding is applied using thresholds within the positive range of $[0, 1]$ to sparsify the initial correlation-based adjacency matrix of each individual. This matrix is constrained to its positive edge weights, focusing on a subset of 30 randomly selected individuals from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) initiative study cohort for each person [58, 59]. Without loss of generality, we only consider positive edges $w_{jk} \in [0, 1]$ because the interpretation of positive and negative values can differ neurobiologically, and certain graph-theoretical features depend on positive weights, such as the strength of a network [60, 61].

Figure 2.1.3: Individual-specific variability of the graph-theoretical feature clustering coefficient (left) and the characteristic path length (right) across incrementally increasing thresholds for the correlation-based networks derived from a subset of 30 individuals from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) initiative.

Since the true system is unknown, the chances of obscuring the system representation by a suboptimal threshold are high and thus can lead to inconclusive results when incorporated into a statistical model. Weighted networks avoid the issue of thresholding by including edge weights. However, the consideration of weights necessitates the analysis of a fully connected adjacency matrix, which leads to an increased computational effort. More importantly, the analytical tools for these networks are still under development as the extension of common graph-theoretical features to its weighted version is oftentimes not straightforward [33, 52]. Therefore, the utilization of network thresholding or sparsification techniques is commonly deemed beneficial in improving the signal-to-noise ratio and reducing computational costs, despite the lack of consensus on the optimal inference approach [2].

To avoid relying on an ill-informed decision of the threshold value, a common approach

involves multiple thresholding of the adjacency matrix [2]. Consider a study cohort of n individuals with their initial individual-specific adjacency matrices $\mathbf{A}_i, i = 1, \dots, n$. To reduce noise or computational efforts, a sequence of threshold values $\tau_l, l = 1, \dots, L$, is preselected within the range of the edge weights $[a, b]$ such that $a \leq \tau_1 < \dots < \tau_L \leq b$. Applying these thresholds according to Equations 2.1.16 to the initial adjacency matrices yields a sequence of adjacency matrices $\mathbf{A}_i(\tau_l)$ for each individual i that demonstrate the diverse representation options of the system for an individual. For each of these matrices corresponding to an individual i , a graph-theoretical feature (e.g. clustering coefficient) could be extracted resulting in an L -dimensional feature vector $z_i(\tau_l)$ with $l = 1, \dots, L$. The final graph-theoretical feature corresponding to individual i is then computed either by selecting the optimal threshold parameter by repeatedly refitting the model with each $z_i(\tau_l), l = 1, \dots, L$, respectively, until a loss function is optimized (e.g. minimizing the root mean squared prediction error), or the arithmetic mean of the values of a graph-theoretical feature over a subset of the threshold sequence

$$z := \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L z(\tau_l) \quad (2.1.17)$$

under the assumption of a central tendency of the distribution is computed. However, usually not the full range of possible thresholds $[a, b]$ is considered but a small prespecified subset such that $a < \tau_1 < \dots < \tau_L < b$. In Paper III of this doctoral thesis, a novel approach is proposed, deviating from the conventional practice by using the complete range of possible edge weight values $z := \{z(\tau_l) | l = 1, \dots, L\}$ with $\tau_1 = a$ and $\tau_L = b$ by introducing a flexible weighting function after multiple thresholding of the full sequence of possible thresholds $[a, b]$. For example, for correlation-based network models in which only positive edge weights are considered, $[a, b] = [0, 1]$, as illustrated in Figure 2.1.3.

2.2 Statistical modelling

The combination of a mathematical model and statistical assumptions provides a powerful framework for understanding and analyzing relationships between entities in various research domains. In this chapter, we outline the basic concepts and methodology of statistical modelling relevant to the topics covered in the papers included in this doctoral thesis.

2.2.1 To explain or to predict?

A statistical model establishes a relationship between a dependent response variable y and a set of independent variables or predictors $\{x_1, \dots, x_p\}$, where the $x_j := (x_{1j}, \dots, x_{nj})^T$, $j = 1, \dots, p$ are column vectors while accounting for the presence of uncertainty denoted by the n -dimensional error term ϵ such that

$$E(y|x_1, \dots, x_p) = f(x_1, \dots, x_p, \epsilon). \quad (2.2.1)$$

The function f is assumed to be unknown and the random error term ϵ is assumed to be independent of the variables. The use of a statistical model serves three main objectives according to the seminal work by Shmueli [62]:

1. Descriptive modelling aims to estimate the association between a dependent variable and one or several independent variables in observed data.
2. Predictive modelling aims for the development of statistical models for the prediction of future outcomes (prognostic prediction) or the diagnosis of a condition (diagnostic prediction).
3. Explanatory modelling aims to draw causal conclusions about the effect of an intervention on an outcome or to study mediation or moderation of causal effects.

The objectives are not mutually exclusive, so a descriptive model can also act as a transparent and explainable prediction model. Since the focus of Papers II-IV was prediction modelling, we will concentrate on this aim in the following. In medical applications, prediction modelling comprises not only the prediction of a health outcome of interest but also the identification of prognostic and diagnostic variables that are indicators of increased risk of disease development, health deterioration, or death (prognostic factor research) [63]. Identifying prognostic features and patterns in observational data has been a major concern for the biomedical field for a long time and has received new interest with advances in modern data acquisition such as high-throughput sequencing or high-resolution imaging.

2.2.2 General linear model

Consider a scalar response variable y_i and a set of predictor variables x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip} with $i = 1, \dots, n$, the general linear model consists of a linear combination of the weighted predictors of the form

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \dots + \beta_p x_{ip} + \epsilon_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (2.2.2)$$

where β_1, \dots, β_p denote the regression coefficients with the intercept β_0 and we assume that the error term follows a centered normal distribution, $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$. Denote $\mathbf{X} = [x_0, x_1, \dots, x_p] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times (p+1)}$ with x_0 being a vector full of 1s, $y = (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and $\epsilon = (\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_n)^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ [64]. Then, the model can be written as

$$y = \mathbf{X}\beta + \epsilon. \quad (2.2.3)$$

The parameter vector $\beta = (\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)$ is estimated by ordinary least squares (OLS) which minimizes the residual sum of squares (RSS)

$$RSS_{OLS} = \|y - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p x_{ij}\beta_j)^2 \quad (2.2.4)$$

with $\|\cdot\|_2$ denoting the Euclidean norm. Taking the first derivative with respect to β and setting the function zero, then yields the OLS estimate

$$\hat{\beta}_{OLS} = (\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X})^{-1} \mathbf{X}^T y, \quad (2.2.5)$$

which is uniquely defined if $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ is non-singular and \mathbf{X} is a full-column rank matrix [65].

2.2.3 The problem with multicollinearity

Collinearity refers to the linear dependence of two variables i.e. one of the variables can be written as a linear combination of the other, whereas when dealing with a set of variables ($p > 2$), it is termed multicollinearity. Mathematically, a set of p random variables X_1, \dots, X_p is linearly dependent if there exists parameters c_1, \dots, c_p not all equal to 0, such that [20]:

$$c_1 X_1 + \dots + c_p X_p = 0. \quad (2.2.6)$$

The term collinearity was first introduced by Nobel laureate Ragnar Frisch in 1934, who noted that its occurrence back then was more frequent than one would expect [66] which probably still holds today. According to him, a substantial portion of the regression and correlation analyses conducted on economic data prior is considered to be unfounded.

Due to the colloquial usage of the term for highly correlated predictors, a distinction

is made in the literature between the presence of substantial correlation among a group of independent variables referred to as the problem of near-multicollinearity, while the linear dependence among variables as stated in Equation 2.2.6 is termed exact multicollinearity. The issues arising from near and exact multicollinearity, as well as potential remedies that align with the modelling objective, are outlined in Paper I of this doctoral thesis. Here, we will provide a brief overview of the challenges [20]:

- Non-unique least squares solution due to exact-collinearity. When there is a perfect linear relationship between predictors, the predictor matrix \mathbf{X} is not of full rank, the product $\mathbf{X}^T\mathbf{X}$ in Equation 2.2.5 is singular and thus the regression coefficients $\hat{\beta}$ not uniquely defined.
- Instability of regression coefficients and inflation of standard errors. Near-collinearity increases the standard errors of the regression coefficients, leading to imprecise estimation of the coefficients.
- Identification of important predictors. Due to the strong dependence of the variables, it is difficult to assess whether the effect sizes are truly attributable to one variable alone or whether the effects merge.
- Instability of the model. Due to the reasoning as in the point above, small changes in the data can then lead to large model changes.
- Interpretability of effects. The interpretation of the model becomes more challenging as the classical meaning of variable effects, where all variables remain constant except for a one-unit change in one variable, is no longer viable because of the dependencies.

Collinearity is a data-related problem that may arise when creating new variables from existing ones, when dealing with entities present within the same system such as biological molecules, due to flawed study design resulting in the representation of the same concept by several variables, or insufficient or inadequate sampling. Sometimes, adding new data points or conducting an in-depth evaluation of the study design can remedy the issue. If neither of these solutions is adequate or feasible, steps aligned with the modelling objective can be considered [1].

2.2.4 Regularized regression

When there are groups of correlated predictors, selecting a subset of variables from a pool of candidate predictors is challenging, particularly in situations $p > n$ where the number of predictors (p) is greater than the number of observations (n). Regularized regression models can facilitate effect estimation and/or variable selection by offering a refined twist to standard OLS models by minimizing the classical loss function in Equation 2.2.4 with an added penalty term [65]. The specification of the penalty term is important since it

shapes the behavior of the model. Various types of regularized regression can be expressed as an optimization problem which assumes the form

$$\hat{\beta}(\lambda) = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p x_{ij}\beta_j)^2 + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^p |\beta_i|^q, \quad (2.2.7)$$

where $q \geq 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$ controls the amount of penalization. The penalty term excludes the intercept β_0 . Usually, the columns of \mathbf{X} are standardized before solving 2.2.7 to ensure the solution is independent of variable unit differences. Standardization is not needed if the variables share the same unit. For convenience, we assume the outcome y to be centered which results in the intercept estimate being given by $\hat{\beta}_0 = \bar{y} := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i$. Then, the intercept can be omitted from the notation and the matrix \mathbf{X} has p columns instead of $p + 1$ [65, 67]. Equation 2.2.7 can be then expressed in its vector form

$$\hat{\beta}(\lambda) = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|y - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda \|\beta\|_q. \quad (2.2.8)$$

The penalty parameter $\lambda \geq 0$ needs to be specified which is commonly done by tuning it via cross-validation or information criteria such as Akaike's information criterion (AIC) [68] or the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) [69]. The larger λ , the more the coefficients tend to be shrunk toward zero. In the subsequent sections, we shall proceed with the matrix notation, presuming standardized inputs.

Ridge regression

Ridge regression [70] employs the L_2 -penalty to shrink the estimated regression coefficient towards zero by minimizing the criterion

$$\hat{\beta}_{ridge}(\lambda) = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|y - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda \|\beta\|_2^2 \quad (2.2.9)$$

with the ridge estimator assuming the form

$$\hat{\beta}_{ridge} = (\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X} + \lambda \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{X}^T y, \quad (2.2.10)$$

where \mathbf{I} is a $p \times p$ -dimensional identity matrix. In contrast to OLS, ridge regression can handle highly correlated predictors by incorporating a penalty term that adds the positive constant $\lambda \mathbf{I}$ to the diagonal of $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ before inversion. This adjustment ensures that the problem remains nonsingular, even when $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ is not of full rank [65].

Lasso regression

Variable selection in addition to shrinkage of the regression coefficients of the candidate predictors can be achieved with the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (lasso)

by imposing the L_1 -penalty [70]. Again, under the assumption of standardized inputs, the objective function of the lasso minimizes the criterion

$$\hat{\beta}_{lasso}(\lambda) = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|y - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda\|\beta\|_1. \quad (2.2.11)$$

In contrast to ridge regression, there is no closed form expression for $\hat{\beta}_{lasso}$ because of the use of the L_1 -penalty term to enforce model sparsity. The absolute value function has no first derivative at $\beta = 0$. Therefore, programming algorithms such as coordinate gradient descent are used to solve lasso [65, 71].

Further, a prerequisite for the consistency of true model selection by the lasso is given by the so-called irrepresentable condition, which states that the lasso selects the true model consistently if and (almost) only if the predictors that are not in the true model are irrepresentable by predictors that are in the true model Zhao and Yu [72]. The irrepresentable condition is a mathematical inequality condition that ensures that the effect of noise predictors is not too strongly correlated with the outcome, making it more likely for the lasso penalty to correctly shrink the true coefficients to zero. Therefore, the condition relies on the correlation structure between the candidate predictors and those representing background noise, as well as the correlation between the candidate predictors. When these correlations are high, the irrepresentable condition does not hold. However, the performance of the lasso can still be good even when the condition is not strictly met [72, 73].

The adaptive lasso

The adaptive lasso (AL) is a two-stage modification of lasso [73]. In the first stage, a weight term is obtained by taking the reciprocal of the absolute value of the estimated preliminary coefficients $\hat{\beta}$ from Equation 2.2.9 to the power of η

$$w_j = \frac{1}{|\hat{\beta}_j|^\eta}, \quad (2.2.12)$$

where $\eta \in \{0.5, 1, 2\}$ specifies the impact of the weights and has to be determined similarly to the tuning parameter λ . The coefficients of the adaptive lasso are then given by Equation 2.2.11 with the weight term defined in Equation 2.2.12

$$\hat{\beta}_{AL}(\lambda) = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|y - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda\|w\beta\|_1. \quad (2.2.13)$$

where the penalty is an elementwise multiplication i.e. $\lambda\|w\beta\| := \lambda\sum_{i=1}^p w_j|\beta_j|$. This helps to overcome some of the limitations of the standard lasso method by providing greater shrinkage to predictors with small coefficients, and less shrinkage to predictors

with large coefficients. The adaptive lasso is beneficial when working with several groups of correlated predictors and provides improved stability with fewer coefficients that are precisely zero in comparison to the standard lasso, as noted by Zou [73].

The nonnegative garrote

The nonnegative garrote (NNG), introduced in the 1990s by Breiman [74], is a two-stage regression approach that involves shrinking the coefficients of the variables towards zero while constraining the shrinkage factors to be nonnegative. The nonnegative garrote is a straightforward shrinkage method, which takes preliminary coefficient estimates from the first stage, such as OLS estimates $\hat{\beta}_{OLS} = (\hat{\beta}_1, \dots, \hat{\beta}_p)$, as proposed in the original paper by Breiman [74], and multiplies them by some nonnegative shrinkage factor $c = (c_1, \dots, c_p)$ obtained in the second stage. The nonnegative garrote estimates can be computed by

$$\hat{\beta}_{NNG}(\lambda) = c(\lambda)\hat{\beta}_{OLS} \quad (2.2.14)$$

with the nonnegative shrinkage factors $c = (c_1, \dots, c_p)^T$ being obtained through the optimization of

$$\hat{c}(\lambda) = \arg \min_c \|y - \mathbf{X}\hat{\mathbf{B}}c\|_2^2 + \lambda\|c\|_1, \text{ subject to } c_j \geq 0 \text{ and } \lambda > 0, \quad (2.2.15)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{B}}$ is a diagonal matrix of the OLS coefficients $\hat{\beta}_{OLS}$ obtained in the first stage. Originally designed for classical linear regression models with low-dimensional data, the nonnegative garrote fell quickly out of favor with the rise of high-dimensional datasets which can be attributed to the inadequacy of OLS estimates in $p > n$ settings. More than 10 years later, Yuan et al. [75] demonstrated in their study that alternative initial estimates like ridge regression estimates, $\hat{\beta}_{ridge} = (\hat{\beta}_1, \dots, \hat{\beta}_p)$, can be used instead in high-dimensional settings. Despite the extension, the nonnegative garrote is still hardly employed in applied practice [76]. However, due to its good properties, such as smaller subset selection and good predictive ability, efforts are made to 'exhume' the nonnegative garrote such as in Kipruto and Sauerbrei [76] and Paper IV of this doctoral thesis.

2.2.5 Flexible modelling of nonlinear associations

Assuming the nature of the association between predictors and the outcome to be linear, can sometimes be too simplistic to capture the underlying complexity of the relationship. Splines offer a flexible parametrization of non-linear relationships, enhancing the model fit by relaxing the linearity assumption [65]. However, spline models require graphical interpretation as the numeric coefficients of the spline functions cannot be easily interpreted.

Consider the statistical model with a continuous outcome y and one independent n -

dimensional variable x given by

$$y = f(x) + \epsilon. \quad (2.2.16)$$

In applied research, there is usually a lack of prior information concerning the biological association, which makes it challenging to determine the functional form of $f(x)$ and thus needs to be estimated based on observed data. Various types of transformations of x can be considered to model the function $f(x)$ such as (piecewise) polynomials, piecewise linear functions, restricted cubic splines [64], B-splines [77], penalized splines [78], and fractional polynomials [79]. However, in the following, we will concentrate on penalized splines, which were of central interest in Paper III, and B-splines, since they comprise the fundamental building block for the understanding of penalized splines. For a general overview of spline procedures, we refer to Perperoglou et al. [80].

A B-spline function consists of $m := K + q$ piecewise polynomials of degree q fitted to K adjacent segments connected by a knot sequence $t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_{K+1}$ and has the form

$$f(x) = \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha_j B_j(x|t_j, q) = \mathbf{B}\alpha \quad (2.2.17)$$

with the piecewise polynomials with local support being known as B-spline basis functions B_j and the coefficients α_j , for $j = 1, \dots, m$ [78]. In the rows of the B-spline matrix $\mathbf{B} = [B_1(x), \dots, B_m(x)]$, only a few values are non-zero. More important are the coefficients α_j , $j = 1, \dots, m$ that shape the fit of the curve. The first t_1 and last knots t_{K+1} are referred to as the boundary knots and define the domain on which the spline is assessed, otherwise, the knots are called inner knots and are usually placed equidistantly. Alternatively, a commonly used method of knot sequencing involves the usage of the quantiles of the empirical distribution of the underlying variable to determine the knot placement [81].

A B-spline basis function is defined by the differences between truncated power functions

$$h(x|t, q) = (x - t)^q I(x > t), \quad (2.2.18)$$

where $I(\cdot)$ denotes the indicator function. The basis functions are defined in a way that ensures each function is orthogonal to almost all others, primarily because the basis functions are concentrated around their respective knots. Consequently, the majority of their supports do not overlap. Using the definition in Equation 2.2.18, a linear ($q = 1$) and a quadratic ($q = 2$) B-spline basis have the form

$$\text{Linear B-spline: } B_1(x, t_j, 1) = h(x|t_j, 1) - 2h(x|t_{j+1}, 1) + h(x|t_{j+2}, 1)$$

$$\text{Quadratic B-spline: } B_1(x|t_j, 2) = h(x|t_j, 2) - 3h(x|t_{j+1}, 2) + 3h(x|t_{j+2}, 2) - h(x|t_{j+3}, 2)$$

For example, consider a scenario where we divide the domain $[0, 1]$ into four segments

($K = 4$) using three inner knots 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 along with boundary knots 0, 1. If the B-spline has a linear degree ($q = 1$), the order of the B-spline basis functions becomes 5 ($m = K + q$). For quadratic B-splines ($q = 2$), the order becomes 6, and for cubic B-splines ($q = 3$), the order is 7. This is illustrated by the number of B-spline basis functions in Figure 2.2.1.

Figure 2.2.1: B-spline basis functions for linear, quadratic, and cubic spline functions applied over a grid comprising four segments with inner knots at $\{0.25, 0.5, 0.75\}$ and the boundary knots $\{0, 1\}$ within the domain of $[0, 1]$.

However, there are a few drawbacks to B-splines [81]. In the case of sparse data points and many B-spline bases, there is little data support for the optimal estimation of the corresponding coefficients, which can lead to instability. In addition, the splines are sensitive to knot number and placement. Thus, penalized splines or P-splines as introduced by Eilers and Marx [78] are a popular class of splines, that ensures smoothness, bypasses the problem of knot selection and placement, and reduces the user choices to a single penalty parameter. A difference penalty term is incorporated to ensure the smoothness of the curve and numerical stability [81]. The penalized sum of squares has the form

$$\sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha_j B_j(x_i | t_j, q)]^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=q+1}^m (\Delta^q \alpha_j)^2, \quad (2.2.19)$$

where $\Delta^1 \alpha_j = \alpha_j - \alpha_{j-1}$ and $\Delta^q \alpha_j = \Delta^{q-1} \Delta^1 \alpha_j$ for $q \geq 1$ [78, 82].

In matrix notation, Equation 2.2.19 can be written as

$$\|y - \mathbf{B}\alpha\|^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{D}_q \alpha\|^2 \quad (2.2.20)$$

with the difference matrix \mathbf{D}_q of degree q . For example, for degree $q = 2$ the difference matrix is given as

$$\Delta^2 \alpha = \mathbf{D}_2 \alpha \quad \text{with } \mathbf{D}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -2 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.2.21)$$

such that $\Delta^2\alpha_j = (\alpha_j - \alpha_{j-1}) - (\alpha_{j-1} - \alpha_{j-2}) = \alpha_j - 2\alpha_{j-1} + \alpha_{j-2}$.

Recommendations suggest incorporating many segments with evenly spaced knots $t_1 < \dots < t_{K+1}$ and relying on the penalty parameter λ to manage the rest. The larger λ the smoother (and straight) the fit will be otherwise for low λ and many B-spline bases the fit can become wiggly as illustrated in Figure 2.2.2. The right value for λ is (similar to regularized regression) obtained by cross-validation or information criteria such as Akaike's information criterion (AIC) [68].

Figure 2.2.2: Illustration of the impact of the penalty parameter λ on the smoothness of the p-spline fit, using simulated data consisting of 203 data points. The p-splines are of degree 3, and the number of segments is set to 100. Notably, for a small λ value (e.g., $\lambda = 1$), overfitting is apparent, whereas a smoother fit is observed for $\lambda = 25$. Conversely, with progressively larger λ values (e.g., $\lambda = 100,000$), oversmoothing becomes evident.

2.2.6 Flexible modelling of functional predictors

At times, we may be interested in modelling the relationship between a response variable y and a functional real-valued independent variable $x(s)$ with $s \in I$ where $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ denotes a compact interval [83]. Unlike traditional variables, whose values are data points, functional variables capture the variability of processes or phenomena over a continuous domain of values (e.g. time) and are therefore functions [84]. For instance, functional predictors like the electrical activity of the heart captured through an ECG signal over time [85], the temporal patterns of brain activity [86], the longitudinal behavioral patterns (such as eating, sleeping, flying) of *Drosophila* flies [87] or the growth rate curves of boys and girls between the age of 1 to 18 from the well-known Berkeley Growth study [88] could be considered. The latter is illustrated in Figure 2.2.3 as an example of functional data, showcasing heightened growth during both early years and adolescence.

Standard linear regression can be extended to include functions as explanatory features and also a functional outcome variable $y(s)$ [84, 89]. Here, we will limit the response variable y to remain scalar and the observed functional data to be on a common dense grid

with no measurement error. We consider the model of the following form

$$y_i = \int_I \beta(s)x_i(s)ds + \epsilon_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (2.2.22)$$

with the coefficient function $\beta(s)$, $s \in I$ [90]. For the sake of simplicity, we will assume $I = [0, 1]$. Since the observations $x_i(s)$ are never truly functional, but rather observed on a (fine) grid with discrete points e.g. $\{x_i(s_l) : s_l \in [0, 1]\}$ with $l = 1, \dots, L$. The integral can then be approximated by a Riemann sum of the form

$$\int_0^1 x_i(s)\beta(s)ds \approx \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L x_i(s_l)\beta(s_l) = \sum_{l=1}^L x_i(s_l) \frac{\beta(s_l)}{L} \quad (2.2.23)$$

such that depending on the estimated coefficient function $\hat{\beta}(s)$ varying parts of the functional variable will be emphasized differently [91]. For instance, if $\beta(\cdot) = \beta$ all observations of $x(s)$ receive the same weight β . Then, the functional regression model is given by $y = \beta \int_0^1 x(s)ds$ and reduces to a standard univariable regression model with the mean of the functional variable as the regressor. The estimation of the functional coefficient $\beta(\cdot)$ can be estimated using penalized splines with the aforementioned difference penalty so that $\beta(s) = \sum_{k=1}^K b_k \phi_k(t) = \phi(s)b$ where $\phi(t) = \{\phi_1(s), \dots, \phi_K(s)\}$ is a penalized spline basis and $b = (b_1, \dots, b_K)$ a vector of the coefficient parameters. For more information on the preprocessing of functional data, additional challenges and extensions to functional outcomes, please refer to Kokoszka and Reimherr [84] and Ramsay and Silverman [89] for comprehensive insights.

Figure 2.2.3: Growth rate curves of 50 randomly selected participants comprised in the Berkeley study.

III

Publications

3.1 Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution

Authors: Mariella Gregorich¹, Susanne Strohmaier², Daniela Dunkler¹, Georg Heinze¹

Affiliations: ¹ Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Data Science, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria

² Department of Epidemiology, Center for Public Health, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria

Publication status: The paper is published in the peer-reviewed journal *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. The supplementary material of this manuscript is provided in Appendix A of this doctoral thesis.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18084259>

Prelude: While several diagnostic tools exist in the literature for detecting potentially problematic levels of correlation in the data, the typical course of action that is recommended and taught at universities is the exclusion of one or more of the set of highly correlated variables. In Paper I, we question the current practice in applied research in a low-dimensional setting. We argue that the modelling objective - whether it is descriptive, predictive, or explanatory - in this context should guide the adequate handling of the correlated predictors. To emphasize the importance of the modelling objective, we illustrate, that there is no one-fits-all solution for all three objectives through various practical data examples.

Article

Regression with Highly Correlated Predictors: Variable Omission Is Not the Solution

Mariella Gregorich ¹, Susanne Strohmaier ^{1,2}, Daniela Dunkler ¹ and Georg Heinze ^{1,*}

¹ Section for Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Statistics, Informatics and Intelligent Systems, Medical University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria; mariella.gregorich@meduniwien.ac.at (M.G.); susanne.strohmaier@meduniwien.ac.at (S.S.); daniela.dunkler@meduniwien.ac.at (D.D.)

² Center for Public Health, Department of Epidemiology, Medical University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria

* Correspondence: georg.heinze@meduniwien.ac.at

Abstract: Regression models have been in use for decades to explore and quantify the association between a dependent response and several independent variables in environmental sciences, epidemiology and public health. However, researchers often encounter situations in which some independent variables exhibit high bivariate correlation, or may even be collinear. Improper statistical handling of this situation will most certainly generate models of little or no practical use and misleading interpretations. By means of two example studies, we demonstrate how diagnostic tools for collinearity or near-collinearity may fail in guiding the analyst. Instead, the most appropriate way of handling collinearity should be driven by the research question at hand and, in particular, by the distinction between predictive or explanatory aims.

Keywords: correlated predictors; exposure-response association; collinearity; nonlinear effects; multivariable modelling

Citation: Gregorich, M.; Strohmaier, S.; Dunkler, D.; Heinze, G. Regression with Highly Correlated Predictors: Variable Omission Is Not the Solution. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2021**, *18*, 4259. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18084259>

Academic Editors: Jimmy T. Efirid and Paul B. Tchounwou

Received: 17 March 2021
Accepted: 15 April 2021
Published: 17 April 2021

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: © 2021 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Correlation between independent variables in multiple regression modelling can have a far-reaching impact on the accurate estimation of the model and, thus, its results and interpretation [1]. This often neglected phenomenon has been recognised as ‘collinearity’, but has rarely been addressed in data analyses with the adequate attention it deserves. Strictly speaking, collinearity or ‘ill-conditioning’ (as termed by Draper and Smith [2]) refers to linear dependence between two independent variables. The notion can be extended to ‘multicollinearity’, meaning that multiple independent variables are involved. The casual use of ‘collinearity’ to denote a situation of strongly but not perfectly correlated variables has led to a distinction between exact and near-collinearity, of which latter is indicated by strong but not perfect correlation between a pair of independent variables [2]. Exact collinearity leads to non-unique least-squares estimates of regression coefficients while near-collinearity can cause numerical problems when fitting the model. Under the latter condition, the least-squares estimates can have a substantially inflated variance [3], and with increasing degree of collinearity, the least-squares solution becomes more and more unstable, and regression coefficients more and more sensitive to small changes in the data. In such a case, the interpretation of a regression coefficient in a multivariable model, which is based on varying one variable while keeping the others constant, becomes more difficult since variations in one variable are associated with dramatic shifts in another variable. Small data samples are especially sensitive to collinearity as inflation of standard errors of regression coefficients induced by collinearity adds up to a generally more unstable estimation.

Exact collinearity may occur if variables are naturally related to each other. For example, in blood analysis, white blood cells consist of five subtypes: neutrophils, eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes. If the concentrations of all five subtypes and of

total white blood cells are measured and included as independent variables in a regression model to predict C-reactive protein (CRP), a software package will ‘automatically’ detect exact collinearity by linear programming and then arbitrarily choose one variable, often simply the last one, to be omitted from the model (see Table 1 and Supplementary Materials). For near-collinearity, however, recommendations include the use of a summary variable composed of several correlated independent variables in a regression model, or the omission of one or several variables assuming the dropped variable does not hold further valuable information. Hence, while collinearity has been studied in many articles in the past (e.g., [4–8]), treatment of the problem in practice mostly targets the prevention of symptoms (e.g., inflated variance, unstable parameter estimates). We propose a more purposeful approach to dealing with collinearity in statistical modelling by distinguishing description from prediction or explanation [9,10].

Table 1. Illustrative extract of the data of the study of Ratzinger et al. [11]. White blood cells consist of the five subtypes neutrophils, eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes and, hence, their sum equals the white blood cell count. See Supplementary Materials for the full table and the analysis.

Observation	Neutrophils (G/L)	Eosinophils (G/L)	Basophils (G/L)	Lymphocytes (G/L)	Monocytes (G/L)	White Blood Cell Count (G/L)	C-Reactive Protein (mg/dL)
1	11.5	0.0	0.1	0.6	1.1	13.3	15.99
2	13.9	0.0	0.0	3.0	3.3	20.2	13.27
3	13.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	1.1	14.5	14.99
4	11.0	0.1	0.0	0.6	0.8	12.5	9.93
5	10.1	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.8	11.5	16.70

Therefore, the objective of this article is to revisit collinearity diagnostics and associated recommendations to deal with collinearity by focusing on two simple case studies each with two independent variables, but with different types of research aims: diagnostic prediction and explanation. In particular, we will evaluate the use of the variance inflation factor (VIF), the condition number and a more refined method to detect high, possibly nonlinear correlation between independent variables using a generalised additive model. The first illustrative example uses data from a study by Tang et al. [12] who have aimed at identifying quantitative features derived from computer tomography (CT) chest images of 176 confirmed COVID-19 cases in order to perform binary classification of disease severity within this cohort. The second example is focused on the current anthropogenic contribution to the progression of climate change.

The remainder of this work is organised as follows. In Section 2, we will review the problem of collinearity in the context of model-building including well-known diagnostics and remedies and will use the blood analysis example for illustration. The two case studies will be presented in Section 3 to demonstrate how collinearity diagnostics would guide further analyses. Some concluding remarks are given in Section 4.

2. Methods

Previous discussions of ill-conditioned data and their consequences have focused on three key aspects: impact of collinearity on statistical estimation and inference, diagnostics to detect it, and proposals to resolve it [2,4,5,7,13,14]. The following section will adhere to this general structure with the intent to give insight into the basic considerations when dealing with highly correlated variables in regression analysis.

2.1. The Problem of Collinearity

We will briefly describe exact and near-collinearity. Consider the classical multiple linear regression model with p independent variables and sample size n given in matrix notation by

$$y = X\beta + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the dependent variable, $\epsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I)$ refers to the error term with the $n \times n$ identity matrix I , and $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times (p+1)}$ denotes the combination of the $n \times p$ design matrix of the independent variables $(x_1, \dots, x_p)^T$ and a unit vector $x_0 = (1, \dots, 1)^T$ in the first column. The vector $\beta = (\beta_0, \dots, \beta_p)^T$ represents the $p + 1$ regression parameters of the model.

The standard estimation approach to minimise the residual sum of squares is the well-known ordinary least-squares (OLS) estimation process aiming to minimise the residual sum of squares (RSS)

$$RSS(\beta) = (y - X\beta)^T (y - X\beta). \quad (2)$$

The closed-form expression of the estimate for the true unknown regression coefficients can then be obtained by the first derivation of Equation (2).

$$\hat{\beta} = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T y \quad (3)$$

Suppose one variable of the design matrix X is exactly equal to a linear combination of the remaining variables, e.g., white blood cell count exactly equals the sum of concentrations of granulocytes (neutrophils, eosinophils, basophils), lymphocytes, and monocytes (Table 1). Then, $X^T X$ is singular, i.e., has rank less than the number of its columns and cannot be inverted. Hence, $\hat{\beta}$ cannot be computed unless one of the variables in X is omitted from the analysis.

The variance–covariance matrix of the OLS estimator can be written as:

$$Var(\hat{\beta}) = (X^T X)^{-1} \mathbb{E}[e^T e] (X^T X)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

and reduces to

$$Var(\hat{\beta}) = \sigma^2 (X^T X)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

under the assumptions of homoscedasticity and no autocorrelation among the OLS residuals ($\mathbb{E}[e^T e] = \sigma^2 I$). In the case of linear dependence among the columns in the design matrix X , it is obvious that both Equations (4) and (5) cannot be numerically evaluated as $X^T X$ cannot be inverted. Now suppose we just consider white blood cells and neutrophils for the analysis. These two variables still have a correlation coefficient of 0.982 and $X^T X$ is close to singularity. The term is invertible, but the variance of the estimated regression coefficients of white blood cells and neutrophils will be outstandingly high. Hence, near-collinearity is sufficient to cause inflated standard errors and wide confidence intervals which, in turn, reflect that slight changes in the data can cause considerable variations in the parameter estimates [15]. However, near-collinearity is mainly defined as a matter of the degree of interrelation among the columns in the design matrix. Therefore, the question arises at which threshold of bivariate correlation should remedies be considered.

2.2. Diagnostics for Collinearity

Identifying the degree of interrelations between the independent variables is an important part of data screening prior to analysis [16]. Traditional diagnostics comprise checking the pairwise sample correlation matrix and investigating the variance inflation factor (VIF). As a pragmatic condition for ruling out near-collinearity, all pairwise correlations between independent variables intended to be included in the model should be clearly smaller than 1. According to Dohoo et al. [17], values above 0.9 almost certainly point towards the presence of collinearity. However, the proposed requirements present sufficient conditions, not necessary ones, for the presence of collinearity. In the blood analysis example, all pairwise correlations are smaller than 1, but still exact collinearity exists. Similarly, pairwise correlation coefficients can only partly detect near-collinearity.

A stricter criterion is obtained by evaluating the multiple correlation between covariates, i.e., the squared coefficient of determination R_i^2 of each model where one independent

variable, x_i , is regressed on all other independent variables $M_i = \{x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_p\}$. These numbers can be transformed into variance inflation factors [18] which express the magnitude by which variances of regression coefficients inflate when independent variables are correlated:

$$VIF(\beta_i) = \frac{1}{1 - R_i^2}. \quad (6)$$

If the independent variables in M_i are uncorrelated to x_i , we will obtain $R_i^2 = 0$ and, hence, $VIF(\beta_i) = 1$. In the case of exact collinearity (as in the blood analysis example), $R_i^2 = 1$ and $VIF(\beta_i) = \infty$. A rule-of-thumb claims that VIF values should all be lower than 10 (corresponding to $R_i^2 < 0.9$), while values between 5 and 10 are already considered problematic [14,19]. However, O'Brien [15] argues that model specification should not end with proving that the rule is met, and other issues with model building may also impact the stability of the estimates. In the reduced model with only neutrophils and white blood cells, VIF for both variables results as $1/(1 - 0.982^2) = 28.02$ indicating problems with near-multicollinearity according to this rule.

An alternative diagnostic proposed by Belsley et al. [1] is the condition number defined as the square root of the ratio of the largest (λ_{max}) to the smallest (λ_{min}) eigenvalue of the scaled design matrix. A condition number of around 10 gives evidence to weak dependencies, a value in between 30 and 100 indicates moderate to strong interdependencies, and a value above 100 points towards the presence of collinearity [20]. Condition indices and the so-called 'regression coefficient variance-decomposition proportions' are extensions of this metric that provide more insight into the variables responsible for collinearity in multi-variable situations with more than two variables. The interested reader is referred to [1] for further details. The condition number in the blood cell example was 23.28, confirming the conclusion from investigating the VIF.

Additional potential indicators of collinearity less often mentioned in the literature are obtained by checks of deviations from expected model behaviour against prior subject-matter knowledge (e.g., unexpected signs of coefficients) or by observing a large change of effect size caused by little alterations in the data matrix [2,14].

In addition, similarity checks of shared information considering non-monotone relationships among the independent variables can identify unnoticed patterns of association. One such approach is redundancy analysis. In this approach, also, variable-specific R_i^2 are estimated to investigate how well one variable can be predicted from the others, but instead of linear regression, generalised additive regression models [21] are used where continuous variables are modelled flexibly using restricted cubic splines instead of just assuming a linear relation between variables. The most predictable variable is then omitted in a stepwise manner. The approach is described in more detail in Harrell ([13], p. 80) and has been implemented in the R-function *redun* of the package *Hmisc* [22].

2.3. Remedial Measures for Collinearity

Recommended solutions in the presence of highly correlated independent variables involve (a) the omission of one of the affected variables from the analysis, (b) combining the strongly correlated variables into a single composite score or (c) switching to more adequate modelling approaches able to handle correlated variables such as principal component analysis (PCA), ridge regression or partial least-squares (PLS) regression [2,4,7,14]. A widely recommended and applied solution to near-collinearity is the omission of a "redundant" independent variable (data reduction). Tabachnick et al. [23] state that after deletion of one of the two redundant variables, the problem of near and exact collinearity can be considered solved when dealing with strong bivariate correlation such as 0.9 and higher. However, the authors suggest the omission of one variable or the creation of a composite score already for bivariate correlation around 0.7. The simplicity of variable pruning is alluring to researchers seeking a quick and easy remedy for the issue at hand because quite advanced approaches, such as PCA or ridge regression, may go beyond the typical level of statistical knowledge of health researchers. Alternatively, an adequate

transformation of the correlated variables into a single index is not always feasible, and the latter approaches result in a loss of interpretability of the individual contribution of the variables to the dependent variable [4,7].

In the blood analysis example, a simple solution that uses subject matter knowledge is to reparametrise the model such that instead of neutrophils and total white blood cell counts, neutrophils and the difference of white blood cell count and neutrophils are used as independent variables. These two variables exhibit a correlation of 0.668 and a VIF of only 1.806. In this way, the information contained in the two variables is fully retained, and the interpretation of the regression coefficients of the new components is even more appealing as before: for example, the regression coefficient of neutrophils now corresponds to the expected difference in CRP corresponding to a difference of 1 G/L of neutrophils, given equal concentration of other components of white blood cell count. The analysis of this data set can be found in the Supplementary Materials.

3. Examples

3.1. Worked Example: COVID-19 Study

In the study by Tang et al. [12], a set of potentially disease-associated features was extracted from 134 chest computer tomography (CT) images of 176 confirmed COVID-19 cases using machine learning techniques. These cases were classified as severe ($N = 55$) or non-severe ($N = 121$) based on the clinical course of the disease. Two CT-derived features were considered of higher importance: the volume of ground-glass opacity (GGO) regions and the consolidation region defined by a specific Hounsfield unit (HU) spectrum of the CT densities (GGO region: HU $[-750, -300]$; consolidation region: HU $[-300, 50]$). Suppose we are interested in predicting severity of the disease with these two continuous variables using a logistic regression model. The joint distribution of the two relevant independent variables is depicted in Figure 1. Both variables exhibit right-skewed distributions (and hence, Figure 1 shows their square roots).

Figure 1. COVID-19 study: scatterplot of the square roots of GGO and consolidation by severity of COVID-19 disease progression.

The Pearson correlation coefficient between GGO and consolidation region is 0.76, suggesting a strong linear relationship between the two variables. Hence, the VIF for both variables is 1.75, indicating no issue with near or exact collinearity. Likewise, redundancy analysis using generalised additive models results in R^2 of 0.618 and 0.600 if GGO or consolidation are predicted by the respective other variable. Similarly, the condition number is 4. Hence, none of the three criteria would suggest omitting any of the two variables in the model.

Table 2 contrasts the multivariable model with the two univariable models. The regression coefficient of the variable consolidation changes by -102% and is no longer significantly associated with the dependent variable disease severity when adjusted for GGO in the multivariable model. Such a deletion of effect size could be another indicator of multicollinearity as mentioned in Section 2.2. The model with GGO region alone achieves a lower value of the Akaike information criterion (AIC) than the model with both variables, and this comparison suggests omitting the consolidation region, contrary to the suggestion of the collinearity detection criteria. Similarly, the C-index of the model with only GGO region is not lower than that of the model with both variables. This example illustrated that for models aiming at providing accurate predictions, information criteria such as AIC may be useful quantities to guide model building, but collinearity checks are not sufficient to make decisions on variable selection.

Table 2. Odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals (CI), Akaike information criteria (AIC), and the C-statistics for the two fitted univariable logistic regression models and the multivariable model including both independent variables.

Model for Disease Severity	Independent Variable(s)	Odds Ratio		Model Performance	
		Estimate	95% CI	AIC	C-Index
Univariable model 1	GGO	1.82	(1.55, 2.22)	88.6	0.96
Univariable model 2	Consolidation	1.94	(1.59, 2.47)	142.8	0.89
Multivariable model	GGO	1.83	(1.48, 2.38)	90.6	0.96
	Consolidation	0.99	(0.74, 1.33)		

3.2. Worked Example: Carbon Emissions and Temperature Anomalies

Ill-conditioning in model building is often further complicated by nonlinear effects or autocorrelation, both of which we will illustrate in our second illustrative example. Research suggests that global temperature has been subject to long-term fluctuations in the past already before the evolution of mankind but has recently been heavily influenced by increasing carbon dioxide emissions (CO_2). Here, we define a hypothetical study in which we want to disentangle the two effects by means of analysis of time series of annual global temperature anomalies and annual global CO_2 emissions. In particular, we would determine to which extent temperature anomalies can be explained by CO_2 emissions, and in the analysis, we will use temperature anomalies as the dependent variable and globally emitted CO_2 as the main independent variable. To separate the effect of emissions from long-term fluctuations, we will adjust for calendar year. Calendar year itself probably indirectly causes two anthropogenic drivers of CO_2 emissions: advances in technology and growth in world population size. If we assume that there are no other common causes of temperature anomalies and carbon emissions than calendar year (exchangeability assumption) and if, theoretically, any amount of CO_2 emission could have been observed in any calendar year (positivity and non-interference assumptions [24]), then the effect of emissions on temperature could even be interpreted as causal effect. However, these assumptions are probably not realistic. Hence, it is important to emphasise that this illustrative data example is not intended as a reliable source to disentangle the effects of anthropogenic and natural contributions to climate change but rather serves to demonstrate problems related to (near-) collinearity. It goes well beyond the scope of this paper to reveal the true relationship between released CO_2 over the course of the last century and

the currently observed climatic changes. We refer the interested reader to Manabe and Wetherald [25] and the special report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) on the impacts of global warming of 1.5 celsius degrees above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission [26].

Our illustrative analysis is based on publicly available data on climate change distributed with the dslabs R package (data set ‘temp carbon’). The data set contains the annual relative temperature anomalies in centigrade from 1880–2018 over land, ocean, and globally with respect to the 20th century mean temperature [27] as well as the annual cumulative emissions estimate of CO₂ released to the atmosphere from fossil fuels and cement production from 1751–2014 provided by Boden et al. [28]. In our analysis, global temperature anomalies measured per year will be the dependent variable, and annual CO₂ emissions given in millions of metric tons and calendar year of measurement constitute the independent variables. In total, the data set contains 268 observations, but only 135 with both carbon emissions and global temperature anomalies (calendar years 1880–2014, Figure 2), which will be the basis of our analysis.

Figure 2. (a) Annual global temperature anomalies with respect to the 20th century mean and (b) annual global carbon emissions, 1880–2014.

In Figure 2, the slopes of both time series reveal a sharply increasing trend from the 1950s onwards. In contrast to the fairly smooth time series of carbon emissions, temperature anomalies exhibit severe annual fluctuations. The correlation coefficient between carbon emissions and year is 0.93 and indicates a strong linear relationship. The corresponding VIF is 7.071. As stated before, according to Dohoo et al. [17] and Tabachnick et al. [23], the high correlation between the two independent variables very likely indicates the presence of collinearity and suggests omission of one variable of the pair. Redundancy analysis using generalised additive models suggests the removal of the variable carbon emissions due to a higher adjusted R² value of 0.988. The estimated R² of the generalised additive model regressing year on modelled carbon emission was 0.954. Further, the condition number for this example is 303.3, indicating near-dependency.

Since the research aim was to explain temperature anomalies by changes in annual CO₂ emissions while adjusting for time itself, none of the two univariable models considering either calendar year or CO₂ emissions alone is appropriate, despite the recommendation of the collinearity detectors to remove one variable.

Equation (5) follows from Equation (4) only under the assumptions of homoscedasticity and no autocorrelation of the error terms. If these prerequisites do not hold, inference

based on Equation (5) will be biased. As the data stems from time series, there was evidence for first-order autocorrelation (Durbin–Watson test: $t = 0.71, p < 0.001$). Hence, we used a quadratic spectral kernel-based heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) estimator as implemented in the R package sandwich [29,30] to compute the empirical covariance matrix for the parameters of each model. The robust HAC estimator ensures consistent estimates of the covariance of the model parameters year and CO₂ emission despite the slight deviations from the underlying model assumptions.

Natural cubic splines with varying degrees of freedom were used to model the non-linear relationship between each of independent variables and the dependent variable, and tested against a model assuming linear association using the AIC. The AIC criterion suggested to include year without transformation and to use natural cubic splines with 5 degrees of freedom for annual CO₂ emissions.

Figure 3 displays the partial effects of the two independent variables on temperature anomalies [31]. The year 1975 was when the global temperature was closest to the 20th century mean. Therefore, to describe the effect of year, we fixed global CO₂ emission of 4596 mt (the emission of 1975) [32]. Likewise, we fixed the year at 1975 to illustrate the adjusted effect of CO₂ emission on temperature anomalies. The model suggests that temperature increases by 0.009 (95% CI: (0.003, 0.015); p -value = 0.006) centigrade each year irrespective of the emitted CO₂. Furthermore, temperature anomalies are related to CO₂ emissions in a nonlinear way. While temperature is negatively associated when emissions increased from 0 to around 4000 mt, emissions above 4000 mt appear to be positively associated with temperature, reaching a plateau at about 6500 mt. However, sparse data support for such high CO₂ emissions led to a wide confidence band which precludes any clear conclusions in that area. Similarly, the confidence bands are also wide at the lower extremes both for year and CO₂ emissions, but can be explained by the low variability in temperature anomalies of earlier years compared to years after the 1920s (see Figure 3). Our analysis assumes that there are no further common causes of CO₂ emissions and temperature anomalies (e.g., other types of emissions caused by the constantly growing world population). Under this assumption, the described effect of year is conceptionally interpreted as a controlled direct effect. However, the causal relation between these variables is certainly more complex. Therefore, we once again emphasise the illustrative purpose of this analysis: if a statistical model is fitted to disentangle different causes of a dependent variable, then even near-collinearity between the independent variables does not justify variable omission.

Figure 3. Partial effect plots of the independent variables year (left) and annual global CO₂ emission (right). Shaded area illustrates the 95% confidence interval of the partial effect curve.

4. Discussion

In this article, we have demonstrated, using two examples, how the diagnostic tools for collinearity and near-collinearity may fail in guiding the analyst in selecting the most appropriate way of handling collinearity. In particular, the analysis of the examples revealed that depending on the situation, misguidance may lead to keeping a clearly redundant variable in a prediction model, or to omitting a variable that would be needed for proper adjustment in an explanatory model. Hence, it is the aim of the analysis that should guide decisions on keeping or omitting a variable in a model.

When statistical modelling is used to pursue a predictive aim, two highly correlated independent variables will lead to high variance in the predictions, even if both variables are relevant for prediction. In small samples, it may then be beneficial to omit one of the pair in order to decrease that variance, even if this incurs some new bias in the predictions. This variance–bias trade-off is often expressed as mean squared error (MSE), which is defined as the expected squared deviation of an estimate from its estimand. It can also be expressed as $MSE = bias^2 + variance$ [33]. Several factors are relevant for the trade-off, the most important being the correlation between the two variables in question, the strength of the association of the variables with the dependent variable, the sample size, and the relative impact of noise (residual error). In the COVID-19 study, consolidation region was hardly associated with the dependent variable once adjusted for GGO region. Hence, despite its marginal association revealed by univariable analysis, the model fit of the prediction model was not affected by its omission, and the AIC even indicated a better fit. Nevertheless, one should not draw overly general conclusions from this result.

In explanatory models, one is usually interested in estimating one of the regression coefficients with high precision or, more generally, to estimate what would happen to the dependent variable if one changes the independent variable of main interest (the ‘exposure’) while other variables (the ‘confounders’) are held constant. Variable selection for such models should be based on the classical assumptions of causal inference, such as conditional exchangeability and positivity [24,34]. For our example, we have drastically simplified possible causes of climate change (apart from CO₂ emissions) into an assumed association of calendar time with temperature anomalies. Such an association is plausible given that there is evidence for temperature variation long before human beings appeared in the history of the earth or, as put by Sun and Bryan [35], ‘if anything has been constant with regard to the state of the climate system, it is that it has always been changing’. Hence, we adjusted for calendar time to be able to disentangle anthropogenic from other effects on temperature anomalies given our assumptions. In this scenario, by removing calendar time from the model, it would not be possible to answer the study question.

Shmueli [10] and Hernan et al. [9] also mention a third purpose of modelling, descriptive modelling. Here, a researcher is interested in providing a parsimonious description of the main associations in the data sets, and the selection of variables could be more data-driven than in explanatory modelling, where it is exclusively based on causal assumptions. Recommendations for variable omission in case of near-collinearity may stem from that descriptive point of view, but we agree with O’Brien [36] that variable omission in the case of collinearity should not be seen as the default solution. We summarised options to handle collinearity with respect to the research aim in Table 3.

Table 3. Some options to deal with collinearity by research aim. With ‘symptoms’, we mean typical consequences of collinearity such as inflated standard errors and unstable parameter estimates.

Method	Explanation	Remark
<i>Descriptive research aim</i>		
Variable omission	Omit one of the variables involved in the collinearity	Removes the symptoms, but leads to different interpretation of the model
Summary score	Combine several nearly collinear variables into a summary score and include only the summary score in the regression model	Removes the symptoms, retains most of the predictive value of the model, but leads to different interpretation of the model
<i>Predictive research aim</i>		
Use information criteria	Information criteria such as Akaike’s can be used to guide model building	Information criteria guide the analyst in a search for the most predictive model
<i>Explanatory research aim</i>		
Use causal reasoning	Specification of variables (exposure of interest, confounders) is necessitated by causal reasoning	Neither exposure nor confounders should be omitted as this violates assumptions needed to identify the causal estimand of interest

Increased standard errors due to the inclusion of correlated independent variables in the regression model sometimes have to be accepted in order to adequately answer a research question. Excluding relevant variables will also lead to biased and inconsistent parameter estimates if the analysis requires all variables to be included in the model. The quick fix of variable omission provides an easy solution, but can lead to not answering the actual research question at hand or be intentionally misleading by dropping variable(s) such that the results of the presented final model support the researcher’s preferred hypothesis. Therefore, variable omission should not be the default solution for strong correlation between independent variables. O’Brien suggested to assess the “model influence” criterion [36] by checking a few alternative models for deviations from the original model with regards to sign and magnitude of the effect sizes of main interest and shifts in major conclusions. This could be extended to predictions from the model. Substantial changes would suggest keeping the dropped variable. If the set of variables to be included follows from causal assumptions, such competing models may still differ in the way continuous variables are parametrised (more or less flexible), or which interactions between variables are considered. Even in the presence of near-collinearity, multiple regression can still be carried out, and ambiguity regarding the interpretation of the regression coefficients can be noted. However, this necessitates transparent reporting of the existing correlation structure and its impact on the regression results should be stated as the analysis proceeds. Overall, variable omission as a consequence of initial data analysis [16] should be avoided when such omission would affect the ability to answer the research question of interest.

In some examples, as in the blood analysis study, it is possible to remove near-collinearity by reparametrising the independent variables. This reparametrisation can often be guided by domain expertise and, such as in our example, even lead to more attractive interpretability of the regression coefficients. If reparametrisation is not an option, ideal but often unattainable remedies of collinearity would consist of revising the study design or repeating or extending the study such that dependency of variables is largely avoided or that higher accuracy of the parameter estimates is obtained by collecting a larger sample. However, these two suggestions are often not a viable option, and the course of action should then be driven by the research question and not the complexity of the remedy.

Supplementary Materials: The following are available online at <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/ijerph18084259/s1>. Table S1: Full subset of the data from the study of Ratzinger et al. (2014) used for the blood cell example in the paper. White blood cells consist of the five subtypes neutrophils eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes and monocytes and hence, their sum equals the white blood cell count; Table S1: Full subset of the data from the study of Ratzinger et al. (2014) used for the blood cell example in the paper. White blood cells consist of the five subtypes neutrophils eosinophils,

basophils, lymphocytes and monocytes and hence, their sum equals the white blood cell count., Table S2: Results of the linear regression model for temperature anomalies adjusted for year linearly and CO₂ emission with natural cubic splines with 5 degrees of freedom. The 95% CI was computed using the HAC estimator. Figure S1: Autocorrelation (left) and partial autocorrelation (right) function of the residuals of the non-linear regression model for temperature anomalies adjusted by year and CO₂ emission, Figure S2: Partial effect plots obtained by classical regression and the regression model using ARMA errors to adjust for the serially correlated error terms.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, M.G. and G.H.; methodology, M.G. and G.H.; software, M.G.; validation, M.G., S.S., G.H.; formal analysis, M.G.; investigation, M.G. and G.H.; resources, M.G. and G.H.; data curation, M.G. and G.H.; writing—original draft preparation, M.G. and G.H.; writing—review and editing, S.S., D.D. and G.H.; visualisation, M.G.; supervision, G.H.; project administration, D.D. and G.H.; funding acquisition, D.D. and G.H. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received funding by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), grant number I4739-B.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Ethical review and approval were waived for this study, due to using publicly available anonymized data sets (blood analysis study, Covid-19 study). Ethical review not applicable for the carbon emissions study.

Informed Consent Statement: Patient consent was waived due to using publicly available anonymized data sets (blood analysis study, Covid-19 study) or is not applicable (carbon emissions study).

Data Availability Statement: The data and code presented in this study are openly available as teaching examples in the repository ‘CorrPred’ on Github (<https://github.com/mgregorich/CorrPred>, accessed on 15 April 2021).

Acknowledgments: Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Belsley, D.A.; Kuh, E.; Welsch, R.E. *Regression Diagnostics: Identifying Influential Data and Sources of Collinearity*; John Wiley & Sons: New York, NY, USA, 2005.
- Draper, N.R.; Smith, H. *Applied Regression Analysis*; John Wiley & Sons: New York, NY, USA, 1998.
- Fox, J. *Applied Regression Analysis and Generalized Linear Models*; Sage Publications: Los Angeles, CA, USA, 2015.
- Vatcheva, K.P.; Lee, M.; McCormick, J.B.; Rahbar, M.H. Multicollinearity in regression analyses conducted in epidemiologic studies. *Epidemiol. Sunnyvale Calif.* **2016**, *6*, 227. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Graham, M.H. Confronting multicollinearity in ecological multiple regression. *Ecology* **2003**, *84*, 2809–2815. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Tu, Y.K.; Clerehugh, V.; Gilthorpe, M.S. Collinearity in linear regression is a serious problem in oral health research. *Eur. J. Oral Sci.* **2004**, *112*, 389–397. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Dormann, C.F.; Elith, J.; Bacher, S.; Buchmann, C.; Carl, G.; Carré, G.; Marquéz, J.R.G.; Gruber, B.; Lafourcade, B.; Leitao, P.J.; et al. Collinearity: A review of methods to deal with it and a simulation study evaluating their performance. *Ecography* **2013**, *36*, 27–46. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Leeuwenberg, A.M.; van Smeden, M.; Langendijk, J.A.; van der Schaaf, A.; Mauer, M.E.; Moons, K.G.; Reitsma, J.B.; Schuit, E. Comparing methods addressing multi-collinearity when developing prediction models. *arXiv* **2021**, arXiv:210101603. Available online: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.01603> (accessed on 15 April 2021).
- Hernán, M.A.; Hsu, J.; Healy, B. A second chance to get causal inference right: A classification of data science tasks. *Chance* **2019**, *32*, 42–49. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Shmueli, G. To explain or to predict? *Stat. Sci.* **2010**, *25*, 289–310. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Ratzinger, F.; Dedeyan, M.; Rammerstorfer, M.; Perkmann, T.; Burgmann, H.; Makristathis, A.; Dorffner, G.; Lötsch, F.; Blacky, A.; Ramharter, M. A risk prediction model for screening bacteremic patients: A cross sectional study. *PLoS ONE* **2014**, *9*, e106765. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Tang, Z.; Zhao, W.; Xie, X.; Zhong, Z.; Shi, F.; Liu, J.; Shen, D. Severity assessment of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) using quantitative features from chest CT images. *arXiv* **2020**, arXiv:200311988. Available online: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.11988> (accessed on 15 April 2021).
- Harrell, F.E., Jr. *Regression Modeling Strategies: With Applications to Linear Models, Logistic and Ordinal Regression, and Survival Analysis*; Springer: New York, NY, USA, 2015.
- Chatterjee, S.; Hadi, A.S. *Regression Analysis by Example*; John Wiley & Sons: New York, NY, USA, 2015.
- O’Brien, R.M. A caution regarding rules of thumb for variance inflation factors. *Qual. Quant.* **2007**, *41*, 673–690. [[CrossRef](#)]

16. Huebner, M.; le Cessie, S.; Schmidt, C.O.; Vach, W. A contemporary conceptual framework for initial data analysis. *Obs. Stud.* **2018**, *4*, 171–192.
17. Dohoo, I.R.; Ducrot, C.; Fourichon, C.; Donald, A.; Hurnik, D. An overview of techniques for dealing with large numbers of independent variables in epidemiologic studies. *Prev. Vet. Med.* **1997**, *29*, 221–239. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Marquardt, D.W. Generalized inverses, ridge regression, biased linear estimation, and nonlinear estimation. *Technometrics* **1970**, *12*, 591–612. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Hair, J.F.; Black, W.C.; Babin, B.J.; Anderson, R.E.; Tatham, R.L. *Multivariate Data Analysis*; Prentice Hall: Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA, 1998.
20. Rawlings, J.O.; Pantula, S.G.; Dickey, D.A. *Applied Regression Analysis: A Research Tool*; Springer Science & Business Media: Berlin, Germany, 2001.
21. Hastie, T.; Tibshirani, R. Generalized additive models: Some applications. *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* **1987**, *82*, 371–386. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Harrell, F.E., Jr.; Harrell, M.F.E., Jr. *Package 'Hmisc'*; CRAN2018; The R Foundation: Vienna, Australia, 2019; pp. 235–236.
23. Tabachnick, B.G.; Fidell, L.S.; Ullman, J.B. *Using Multivariate Statistics*; Pearson: Boston, MA, USA, 2007.
24. Hernán, M.A.; Robins, J.M. *Causal Inference: What if*; Chapman & Hall/CRC: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2020.
25. Manabe, S.; Wetherald, R.T. Thermal equilibrium of the atmosphere with a given distribution of relative humidity. *J. Atmos. Sci.* **1967**, *24*, 241–259. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Masson-Delmotte, V.; Zhai, P.; Pörtner, H.O.; Roberts, D.; Skea, J.; Shukla, P.R.; Pirani, A.; Moufouma-Okia, W.; Péan, C.; Pidcock, R.; et al. Summary for Policymakers. In *Global Warming of 1.5 °C*; An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global; World Meteorological Organization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2018.
27. NOAA. *National Centers for Environmental Information, Climate at a Glance: Divisional Time Series*; NOAA: Washington, DC, USA, 2018.
28. Boden, T.; Andres, R.; Marland, G. *Global, Regional, and National Fossil-Fuel CO₂ Emissions (1751-2014)(v. 2017)*. *Environmental System Science Data Infrastructure for a Virtual Ecosystem*; Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL): Oak Ridge, TN, USA, 2017.
29. Andrews, D.W. Heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent covariance matrix estimation. *Econom. J. Econom. Soc.* **1991**, *59*, 817–858. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Zeileis, A. Econometric computing with HC and HAC covariance matrix estimators. *J. Stat. Softw.* **2004**, *11*, 1–17. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Perperoglou, A.; Sauerbrei, W.; Abrahamowicz, M.; Schmid, M. A review of spline function procedures in R. *BMC Med Res. Methodol.* **2019**, *19*, 46. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. VanderWeele, T.J. Marginal structural models for the estimation of direct and indirect effects. *Epidemiology* **2009**, *20*, 18–26. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
33. Friedman, J.; Hastie, T.; Tibshirani, R. *The Elements of Statistical Learning*; Springer Series in Statistics; Springer: New York, NY, USA, 2001; Volume 1.
34. Witte, J.; Didelez, V. Covariate selection strategies for causal inference: Classification and comparison. *Biomed. J.* **2019**, *61*, 1270–1289. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Sun, D.-Z.; Bryan, F. *Climate Dynamics: Why Does Climate Vary?* John Wiley & Sons: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2013.
36. O'Brien, R.M. Dropping highly collinear variables from a model: Why it typically is not a good idea. *Soc. Sci. Q.* **2017**, *98*, 360–375. [[CrossRef](#)]

3.2 Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods

Authors: Mariella Gregorich^{1,2}, Federico Melograna³, Martina Sunqvist⁴, Stefan Michiels⁴, Kristel Van Steen^{3,5}, Georg Heinze¹

Affiliations: ¹ Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Data Science, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria; ² Division of Nephrology and Dialysis, Department of Internal Medicine III, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria ³ BIO3 Laboratory for Systems Medicine, Department of Human Genetics, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium ⁴ Service de Biostatistique et d'Epidémiologie, Gustave Roussy, Oncostat U1018, Inserm, University Paris-Saclay, labeled Ligue Contre le Cancer, Villejuif, France ⁵ BIO3 Laboratory for Systems Genetics, GIGA-R Medical Genomics, University of Liège, Liège, Belgium

Publication status: The paper is published in the peer-reviewed journal *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. The supplementary material of this manuscript is provided in Appendix A of this doctoral thesis.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-022-01544-6>

Interlude: The idea emerged to represent the inherent dependency structure of correlated data as networks on the individual level and incorporate it explicitly into the statistical modeling process. Therefore, we conducted a scoping review to identify statistical methodology including individual-specific networks or their graph-theoretical features for prediction modelling (prognosis or diagnosis) in applied health research or medicine. Paper II provides the scoping review which gives a comprehensive overview of the field, outlines the current practice in individual-specific network inference, and identifies the most common areas of application. We found that individual-specific networks are able to capture the complexities of high-dimensional data and thus, offer a new perspective to the analysis of relational data structures that may prove informative for the prediction of health outcomes.

RESEARCH

Open Access

Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling – A scoping review of methods

Mariella Gregorich^{1,2}, Federico Melograna³, Martina Sunqvist⁴, Stefan Michiels⁴, Kristel Van Steen^{3,5} and Georg Heinze^{1*}

Abstract

Background: Recent advances in biotechnology enable the acquisition of high-dimensional data on individuals, posing challenges for prediction models which traditionally use covariates such as clinical patient characteristics. Alternative forms of covariate representations for the features derived from these modern data modalities should be considered that can utilize their intrinsic interconnection. The connectivity information between these features can be represented as an individual-specific network defined by a set of nodes and edges, the strength of which can vary from individual to individual. Global or local graph-theoretical features describing the network may constitute potential prognostic biomarkers instead of or in addition to traditional covariates and may replace the often unsuccessful search for individual biomarkers in a high-dimensional predictor space.

Methods: We conducted a scoping review to identify, collate and critically appraise the state-of-art in the use of individual-specific networks for prediction modelling in medicine and applied health research, published during 2000–2020 in the electronic databases PubMed, Scopus and Embase.

Results: Our scoping review revealed the main application areas namely neurology and pathopsychology, followed by cancer research, cardiology and pathology ($N = 148$). Network construction was mainly based on Pearson correlation coefficients of repeated measurements, but also alternative approaches (e.g. partial correlation, visibility graphs) were found. For covariates measured only once per individual, network construction was mostly based on quantifying an individual's contribution to the overall group-level structure. Despite the multitude of identified methodological approaches for individual-specific network inference, the number of studies that were intended to enable the prediction of clinical outcomes for future individuals was quite limited, and most of the models served as proof of concept that network characteristics can in principle be useful for prediction.

Conclusion: The current body of research clearly demonstrates the value of individual-specific network analysis for prediction modelling, but it has not yet been considered as a general tool outside the current areas of application. More methodological research is still needed on well-founded strategies for network inference, especially on adequate network sparsification and outcome-guided graph-theoretical feature extraction and selection, and on how networks can be exploited efficiently for prediction modelling.

Keywords: Individual-specific network, Prediction, Personalized medicine, Graph theory, Methodological review, Network analysis, Genomics, Neurology, Pathopsychology, Biomarker

Introduction

Prediction modelling is essential to an individualized approach to risk assessment, diagnosis, prognosis, and medical decision-making. While the conventional

*Correspondence: georg.heinze@meduniwien.ac.at

¹ Section for Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Statistics, Informatics and Intelligent Systems, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria
Full list of author information is available at the end of the article

©The Author(s) 2022. **Open Access** This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. The Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication waiver (<http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>) applies to the data made available in this article, unless otherwise stated in a credit line to the data.

approach of model development is mainly based on a small set of patient characteristics, recent developments in biotechnology (e.g. high-resolution imaging modalities and high-throughput sequencing methods) have accelerated the generation of individual-specific data at an unprecedented level generally characterized by a high-dimensional variable space for each individual and complex correlation structures between the variables. Common methods of prediction modelling are not well suited to deal with such complex data structures in particular in small to moderately sized studies [1–3]. Hence the question arises how the abundance of biological information available per individual can be used most efficiently to provide accurate predictions of health outcomes.

Increasingly, it becomes possible to represent individual patient data as individual-specific networks that, apart from individual-specific node measurements, allow to capture connectivity information between variables (nodes) via their edges. Individual-specific networks are exemplified in Fig. 1 for a hypothetical small study cohort. The absence/presence of an edge, or its weight (strength of the connectivity) can be the same for all individuals in the sample (e.g. based on a reference or on sample estimates of a statistical measure of connectivity), or can vary from individual to individual. For example, the individuals depicted in Fig. 1 share the same network structure but are heterogeneous with respect to the edge weights. The network representation is further motivated by subject matter, since complex diseases of the human body are rarely caused by the malfunction of individual molecules but rather by the disruption or

dysfunction of the underlying system behaviour or a specific set of biological units [4]. Graph-theoretical features can then capture the heterogeneous variability of system patterns across individuals by describing individual-specific structural and topological network patterns or identify biological modules, a set of nodes acting as key drivers of disease manifestation. For the sake of clarity, variables that originate from individual-specific networks will be referred to as graph-theoretical features throughout this work in order to distinguish them from classical clinical variables. Graph-theoretical features condense a high-dimensional predictor space into few quantitative and interpretable descriptors that can be used in prediction models instead of or in addition to classical clinical predictors in order to improve such models. Such an approach may lead to new insights into disease development or progression and may even replace the often unsuccessful search for individual prognostic biomarkers in the high-dimensional space.

In the past decades, the call for a complex system-based understanding of human disease mechanisms has led to a general theory and various application frameworks of group-level networks, i.e. network inference based on the aggregated study cohort. For example, see Barabási et al. [4] for an extensive review on ‘network medicine’ and Li et al. [5] for an overview of graph representation learning in biology and medicine. However, a “one size fits all” approach for network inference may wash out the individual-specific systems behaviour. Linking individual-specific patterns of connections rather than group-level system behaviour across biological components to disease manifestation can not only capture the

heterogeneity of biological system behaviour across individuals but also pave the way for the detection of novel biomarkers for more individualized prediction.

To our knowledge, the potential of using graph-theoretical features of individual-specific networks as predictors in clinical prediction models has not yet been systematically explored and hence the state-of-the-art in this relatively new field of predictive research remains unknown. Therefore, we conducted a scoping review [6, 7] to systematically examine the scientific literature to identify, collate and critically appraise methodological approaches incorporating individual-specific networks to improve and advance prediction modelling of clinical outcomes in applied health research. We did not consider studies exclusively employing group-level networks and those which do not aim at individual outcome prediction.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we discuss the methodology of the scoping review. The general study characteristics and findings of the search strategy are presented in Section 3. Further, we present and collate the identified approaches to individual-specific network inference, graph-theoretical feature extraction and their usage for prediction in Section 4 and conclude with current challenges and future aspects of the identified methodology in Section 5.

Methods

Search strategy

We conducted a scoping literature search in the three electronic databases PubMed, Embase and Scopus to extract peer-reviewed articles published between January 1st, 2000 and August 31st, 2020. The search strategy consisted of three sets of terms to cover the research intersection of network analysis and prediction modelling adequately but also to reduce false positive hits by the broad meaning of the term 'network'. The three sets of terms were: 1) terms associated with network analysis, 2) terms associated with predictive research and 3) exclusion terms (see the [Supplementary Material](#) for a detailed overview).

Studies met the inclusion criteria if graph-theoretical features derived from an individual-specific network were considered as candidate predictors in prediction modelling in the medical field. Studies were excluded if they did not focus on prediction modelling of health outcomes and did not consider networks constructed for single individuals. Therefore, we excluded studies that concentrated solely on the descriptive analysis of individual-specific networks without examining their potential association with a clinical outcome or studies considering group-level networks computed from aggregated data. Studies that essentially aimed at predicting network

behaviour, link prediction or changes in network topology or structure were also discarded.

Selection of studies

All studies identified by the search strategy were initially screened based on the title and then, after inclusion, based on the abstract to determine eligibility. Letters, commentaries and conference abstracts were excluded. Selected articles were then subjected to a full-text analysis. The first author was responsible for the initial search, application of the exclusion criteria, screening of all the identified articles and the quality evaluation of the included papers. A random subset of studies (consisting of 250, 50 and 25 studies in the title, abstract and full-text screening phases, respectively) was independently assessed by three additional reviewers (GH, FM, MS) to ensure general validity and reliability of the screening process and data extraction of the first reviewer. Any inconsistencies in selection among the reviewers were discussed and resolved to reach a general consensus. We refer the reader to the [Supplementary Material](#) for a more detailed summary of the search strategy and the extraction process. Reporting adhered to the PRISMA-ScR guidelines [7] to ensure methodological transparency.

Results

Search results and study characteristics

A total of 4988 studies was initially retrieved from the electronic database search together with the manual selection from other sources. After the screening of the titles, 488 articles remained and after reviewing the abstracts, only 227 articles met the eligibility criteria for full-text analysis of which 79 were excluded due to the following reasons: (1) construction of non-individual-specific networks ($N=36$), (2) the term "network" was used in a different context ($N=17$), (3) no association with an outcome of interest was considered ($N=17$) or (4) graph-theoretical features were used as dependent variables ($N=9$). This left 148 studies (3.0%) out of the initial 4988 studies meeting the eligibility criteria of the review (see Fig. 2).

Through a synthesis of the sources of evidence, four medical domains of application were identified. The majority of the eligible studies ($N=129$, 87.2%) covered neurological research, followed by the fields of psychopathology ($N=9$, 6.1%), genomics ($N=7$, 4.7%), cardiology ($N=2$, 1.4%) and pathology ($N=1$, 0.7%). The oldest study meeting our inclusion criteria was published in 2009, with the number of studies published annually increasing steadily thereafter (see Supplementary Fig. S1). Most of the studies ($N=100$, 67.6%) were published after 2015. Out of the 148 included studies, 135 (91.2%) were identified as quantitative studies and 13 (8.8%) as

qualitative studies (e.g. reviews). Besides the process of data acquisition and preparation in applied health research, three main topics emerged in the included articles covering the intersection of network analysis and prediction and were addressed separately in the following subsections: Section 3.2 focuses on data-driven network inference consisting of the individual-specific network construction and network sparsification, Section 3.3

on the extraction of graph-theoretical features and Section 3.4 on predictive analytics using graph-theoretical features. Main modules in a general workflow of considering individual-specific networks in prediction modelling and some aspects of their implementation are illustrated in Fig. 3. However, a detailed presentation of each of the identified analytics for network analysis and prediction modelling as well as their theoretical

properties is beyond the scope of this article. Instead, the reader will find useful references throughout this work.

Network construction and sparsification

Notation and concepts

In general, an undirected network (or graph) consists of a pair $G=(V,E)$ where V denotes a finite, non-empty set of p nodes and E is a subset of $V \times V$ containing pairs of connected nodes $e_{ij} := (v_i, v_j)$ referred to as edges. In directed graphs (digraph), each edge has a direction such that $e_{ij} \neq e_{ji}$. In weighted networks, each edge e_{ij} is associated with a weight $w_{ij} := w(v_i, v_j) \in R$. A subnetwork $G'=(V',E')$ is a network such that $V' \subseteq V$ and $E' \subseteq E$. The data structure defining a network is the adjacency matrix $A=[a_{ij}]$ in which $a_{ij}=1$ indicates the presence of an edge between v_i and v_j , while $a_{ij}=0$ indicates its absence. For weighted networks $a_{ij}=w_{ij}$, and again $a_{ij}=0$ indicates the absence of the respective edge. For individual-specific networks, we assume that for each individual s ($s=1, \dots, N$) a unique network $G_s=(V_s, E_s)$ exists, where N is the number of individuals within the study cohort.

Global graph-theoretical features characterize properties of the entire network, while local features only take the information of a smaller substructure of the network (e.g. node, module) into account. For example, edge density is a global graph-theoretical feature defined as the ratio of the number of actual connections to the number of all possible connections in the network

$$d = \frac{2 | E |}{| V | (| V | - 1)} \tag{1}$$

See Table 1 for an overview of some global and local graph-theoretical features identified in the reviewed studies.

Construction of individual-specific networks

Repeated measurements per variable per individual Depending on the field of research, the nodes mainly represented regions of interest (ROIs) in the brain, genes or psychotic symptoms (e.g. stress, insomnia). In two individual proof-of-concept studies, the nodes corresponded to 5-min heart rate variability (HRV) segments [8] or ROI in muscle biopsy images [9]. A variety of methods were identified for defining connectivity between pairs of nodes based on data-driven structural learning, i.e., estimating the graphical structure from the data (see Fig. 4 for a schematic illustration).

The majority of identified studies conducted correlation-based approaches (see Fig. 4A) using repeatedly measured continuous data (e.g. sequential data, time series) to define edges between the prespecified nodes [10–27]. In neurological applications, adjacency matrices most frequently consisted of correlation coefficients ($N=69, P=48.9\%$) (e.g., Pearson product moment correlation coefficient) of time series of brain activity (e.g. blood oxygenation level dependent (BOLD) signal) or longitudinal cortical thickness between pairs of ROIs [16]. Fisher’s r-to-z transformation was applied to Pearson correlation coefficients to achieve approximate normality [14, 21, 26, 28, 29]. However, correlation-based inference of the network structure can be subject to interfering effects (e.g. outliers, noise) and can only capture pairwise information. Thus, variations of the Pearson correlation such as spatial smoothing have been proposed in which the time series corresponding to a region is obtained by a linear mixture of neighbouring time series or segmentation of the BOLD time series into subdivisions (e.g. snapshot graphs, sliding-window approach) [10, 30–32]. The sliding window or snapshot

Table 1 Explanation of the graph-theoretical features used in ≥ 10 prediction modelling studies. Local features can be averaged over all nodes to obtain the global-scale counterpart

Graph-theoretical feature	Abbrev.	N	Scale	Explanation
Clustering coefficient	CC	82	Both	Ratio of the connected triangles to the maximum possible number of triangles
Characteristic path length	CPL	60	Both	Average of all shortest paths over all pairs of nodes
Global efficiency	GE	55	Global	Average of the reciprocals of the shortest path lengths
Local efficiency	LE	45	Local	Global efficiency applied to the neighbourhood of a node
Small-world index	SWI	42	Global	Ratio of the CC normalized by that expected in a random graph and the CPL normalized by that expected in a random graph
Degree	Dg	38	Local	Number of links of a node
Betweenness centrality	BC	36	Local	Ratio of all shortest paths with and without the node
Edge weight	EW	34	Local	Strength of the connection between two nodes
Modularity	M	21	Global	Degree to which nodes tend to form relatively independent modules
Density	Ds	18	Global	Percentage of observed connections from the maximum number of possible connections
Assortativity	A	10	Global	Pearson correlation coefficient of degree between pairs of connected nodes

graph approach only consider small time windows of the full time series yielding a set of graphs $G_s = \{G_{s1}, \dots, G_{st}\}$ for individual s and t time windows. Then, a presumably more robust final version of the individual-specific network can be obtained by assessing the frequency of appearance of each edge in each G_{sj} for $j=1, \dots, t$ because only a few of these snapshot graphs G_{sj} are influenced by disruptions of the time series by noise artefacts [10]. Some studies also employed several modifications of the standard Pearson correlation coefficient to define connectivity [33–37].

An extension to the bivariate determination of connectivity were partial correlation-based networks [38, 39]. Partial correlation coefficients describe the correlation between two variables that cannot be explained by associations of the variable pair with other variables. In the case of non-normality of the data, a transformation can be applied prior. Another approach to control for covariates while accounting for temporal information is vector autoregressive (VAR) modelling that regresses the dependent variable measured at time point t on the lagged dependent variable and the predictors evaluated at time point $t-1$. VAR was only employed in psychological studies [40, 41]. This way directed individual-specific networks were obtained such that an edge weight w_{ij} associated with a directed link from node v_i to node v_j corresponds to the respective VAR coefficient in the model. The VAR model and resulting directed networks implied that in general $w_{ij} \neq w_{ji}$. Only 2 out of the 135 quantitative studies considered directed networks estimated using VAR models [40, 41].

A recently introduced network-based representation referred to as a visibility graph allows to derive individual-specific networks from time series data if available per patient in the cohort [42]. A time series with n sequentially ordered data points, $\{x_t\}_{t=1, \dots, n}$ is transformed into a network in which each time point t represents a node connected to time point s if the visibility criterion

$$x_u < x_s + (x_t - x_s) \frac{s - u}{s - t}$$

holds true for an additional data point x_u placed between them. Applications of visibility graphs were mostly found in context of EEG data [43–45] but also in a cardiologic study dealing with human heart rate variability time series to differentiate between wake/sleep stages [46] and patients of spinal cord injury [47]. A more thorough overview of concepts and algorithms to map time series data into networks can be found in Silva et al. [48].

Alternatively, various distributional similarity approaches were used to evaluate the similarity between two distributions corresponding to a pair of nodes (Jensen-Shannon divergence [49], Kullback-Leibler divergence [50], dynamic time warping [8], generalized measure of association [51]). Zhang et al. [49] employed a kernel-based on the Jensen-Shannon divergence to measure the similarity of multivariate time series, whereas Dong et al. [8] assessed similarity between pairs of time series based on dynamic time warping.

Single measurement per variable per individual The approaches presented so far are only applicable if repeated data points of all variables per individual are available. In the identified studies in which all independent variables were measured only once for an individual, individual-specific network inference was mainly based on quantifying each individual’s contribution to the overall group-level structure either by leave-one-out network construction (LOONC) [52, 53] or by a differential perturbation approach [54–59]. Strictly speaking, these two approaches do not involve individual-level parameter inference per se but aim to derive individual-specific networks from group-level networks regardless of the group-level network inference procedure. More precisely, LOONC removes a single individual from group-level network construction and measures the degree of change in all edge weights caused by the removal against the full group-level network. Kuijjer et al. [52] proposed to reversely engineer individual-specific networks by linear interpolation between each edge weight $w_{ij}^{(C_{int})}$ of the group-level network (using all $N_{C_{int}}$ observations in the study cohort of interest C_{int}) and the corresponding edge weight $w_{ij}^{(C_{int}\setminus q)}$ in the network using all observations except an individual of interest q to obtain the edge weight estimate $w_{ij}^{(q)}$ for a single individual by

$$w_{ij}^{(q)} = N \left(w_{ij}^{(C_{int})} - w_{ij}^{(C_{int}\setminus q)} \right) + w_{ij}^{(C_{int}\setminus q)} \tag{2}$$

where N can be a generic or individual-specific weight but is usually set to $N_{C_{int}}$. In contrast, differential perturbation analysis quantifies the extent to which an edge weight is perturbed by the addition of an individual compared to a reference network constructed independently from the cohort of interest. Edge weights of the individual-specific network G_q for individual q are determined by computing the absolute difference in edge weights between the network computed from the reference population augmented by that individual (augmented network) and the reference network as

$$w_{ij}^{(q)} = w_{ij}^{(C_{ref}\cup q)} - w_{ij}^{(C_{ref})} \tag{3}$$

where $w_{ij}^{(C_{ref})}$ denotes the edge weights in the reference network and $w_{ij}^{(C_{ref}\cup q)}$ in the augmented network.

Neither of the two presented approaches to individual-specific network construction for single measurements of each variable per individual relies on a particular inference method for the group-level networks. Equation (2) and (3) require the edge weights of the estimated group-level networks but do not specify how these networks have to be inferred. Perturbation analysis in contrast to

LOONC, however, depends on an additional reference network to obtain individual-specific edge weights.

In the study by Zhu et al. [54], a group-level reference network for the differential perturbation analysis was inferred using Pearson correlation coefficients of gene co-expression data of $N_{C_{ref}}$ cancer-free individuals of a reference cohort C_{ref} . An augmented network for an individual with cancer q was constructed by including the expression data of that individual in the reference cohort ($C_{ref}\cup q$). The approach was also found with networks constructed using partial correlation [57]. In Kuijjer et al. [52], LOONC was implemented using group-level networks derived from Pearson correlation and mutual information, a non-linear measure of association, while Lopes-Ramos et al. [53] used biologically motivated regulatory networks. Note that since both equations quantify the inferred difference in edge weighting, the obtained individual-specific weights can also assume values outside the boundaries of the underlying statistic of the group-level networks. For example, edge weights in the individual-specific networks derived from LOONC or differential perturbation using Pearson correlation can yield values < -1 and > 1 (see Eq. (2–3)). Both approaches were only found in cancer research [57, 59].

Only one of the identified studies using single measurements per variable did not conduct LOONC or perturbation analysis. Xie et al. [39] proposed conditional Gaussian graphical modelling with mean and covariance matrix depending on an individual’s covariates while assuming homogeneous network structure across individuals in order to infer individual-specific networks. Hence, differences in edge weights between individuals are covariate-dependent.

Domain-specific techniques In neurological application, certain high-resolution imaging methods for data acquisition generate domain-specific data structures that require a specifically designed methodology of network inference. For instance, tractography detects fibre pathways linking different anatomical brain regions [60–68]. Electroencephalographic (EEG)-based connectivity was predominantly assessed by metrics such as phase lag index, coherence-based similarity, or synchronization likelihood index [69–72]. The interested reader is referred to the references for more details on these applications.

Techniques for network sparsification

Network sparsification removes edges from a network with the intent to optimise the inference of the ‘true’ system by the omission of “spurious” edges, improve interpretability and enable computational feasibility in

construction and further processing of the network. In addition, the structural and topological properties of the network might be improved by removing seemingly spurious connections i.e. edges that are erroneously generated during network inference. Given an undirected network $G=(V,E)$, sparsification yields a subnetwork $G'=(V,E')$ of G with fewer edges such that $|E'| > |E|$.

More than half of the quantitative studies employed network sparsification ($N=74, 54.8\%$), followed by studies analysing non-sparsified networks ($N=58, 43.0\%$) and 3 studies that considered both approaches (2.2%). As illustrated in Fig. 4B, the most popular strategy was proportional thresholding ($N=37$) in which a common sparsity threshold (e.g. in terms of density) is defined for all individual-specific networks, and edges are removed sequentially in each network in ascending order of their edge weights until the prespecified sparsity threshold is reached [10, 21, 23–25, 29, 58, 73]. The second most common approach constituted weight-based thresholding ($N=31$) in which one common weight threshold is defined for all individual-specific networks such that all edge weights within an individual-specific network falling below (or above) the threshold are removed (Fig. 5) [8, 11, 67, 68, 74, 75]. The majority of the weight-based approaches employed binarization of all individual-specific networks ($N=21$) according to the selected weight threshold τ such that $w'_{ij} = 1$ if $w_{ij} > \tau$ and 0 otherwise [23, 27, 29, 75, 76]. Edges with negative weights were often removed due to their questionable interpretability or the inability to compute some graph-theoretical features from them (e.g. clustering coefficient or characteristic path length), omitting potentially meaningful inverse relation between nodes. In $N=6$ studies, a sparse representation of a partial correlation-based network was achieved individually by including an L_q -norm ($q \in \{1, 2\}$) regularization penalty to the network inference process in order to reinforce strong connections across individuals and drive weak connections towards zero [36, 37, 39, 77, 78]. Due to the individually imposed regularization, inter-subject variability might then be inherently induced

according to Wee et al. [36]. Hence, they imposed an additional group constraint to encourage a common network topology across the study cohort. Other studies selected a fixed penalty term for all individual networks which is why this approach can also be seen as a special case of weight-based thresholding [34, 37]. Group-level edge elimination for each individual-specific network was carried out by univariate testing of the edge weights ($N=17$), either by permutation testing to control the probability of including spurious connections at 0.05 or by only including edges with weights significantly different from zero [13, 15–19, 79–81]. Then all those edges that were characterized as spurious at the group level were removed from all individual-specific networks.

The implemented strategy of network sparsification across studies varied substantially in terms of: the sparsification method, the number or combination of investigated methods, the selected sparsification threshold(s) and the reasoning behind the chosen strategy. It was not uncommon for studies to combine several sparsification strategies [12, 21, 22, 24] or to examine several strategies separately [33, 34, 37]. Further, all of the identified approaches to network sparsification were dependent on the careful selection of a thresholding parameter by the researcher. To circumvent the arbitrariness associated with the selection of a single threshold, the majority of studies employed multiple thresholding, meaning that a range of cut-off values with small incremental steps was examined such that a series of networks $\mathcal{G}_s := \{G_{s,\tau_k}\}_{k=1,\dots,T}$ for each individual s ($s=1, \dots, N$) was obtained with T thresholds τ_k where $k=1, \dots, T$ [65, 73, 76, 82]. For an illustrated example of multiple thresholding, see Fig. 6. Only one study performed weight-based thresholding with a single, arbitrary threshold [83].

In general, there was considerable heterogeneity in the selection of the optimal threshold value for sparsification in the studies evaluated:(1) a threshold yielding a small-world index (see Table 1 for definition) above 1 of the networks was chosen [65, 84], (2) an arbitrary fixed

threshold was chosen [39], (3) the differently sparsified networks corresponding to a single individual \mathcal{G}_s were fused into an average individual-specific network [25], (4) the numerical integral or average of the graph-theoretical feature over the range of network \mathcal{G}_s was computed [25, 56, 64, 65, 76], (5) a threshold generating the best results in terms of classification accuracy or association with the outcome was selected [8, 29, 34, 51], and (6) further processing was done including varying network sparsity levels [24, 75, 85].

According to the identified studies conducting network sparsification, the choice of the threshold is crucial to balance between noise removal (spurious edges) and preservation of ‘true’ edges. For instance, proportional thresholding may leave edges with very low edge weights assumed spurious, whereas weight-based thresholding yields different densities across the individual-specific networks which then may affect other graph-theoretical features and in turn, hinder comparability across networks. While the evaluated studies often adequately addressed the selection of the threshold parameter weight-based and proportional thresholding, ‘hidden’ threshold parameters in regularized network inference (i.e. penalty strength) or univariate testing (i.e. significance level) were rarely further investigated.

Graph-theoretical feature extraction

Appropriate features describing the network after its construction reduce the dimensionality of the network, capture aspects of the graph structure and may constitute valuable biomarkers for clinical outcomes in applied health research. The connectivity information within a network can be characterized on different scales: globally or locally. While global features capture properties of the whole network, local features describe their characteristics in defined subareas such as nodes, edges or modules (i.e. clusters of nodes).

The majority of quantitative studies extracted both, local and global graph-theoretical features ($N=56$, 41.5%), followed by studies only focusing on local features ($N=44$, 32.6%) and studies interested only in global graph-theoretical features ($N=35$, 26.0%). The average number of computed global graph-theoretical features describing different aspects of the network across all studies was 3.19 with a standard deviation (SD) of 4.69 and a range of 0 to 44, while the average number of local features was comparatively small with a mean of 1.62 and a SD of 1.72 and a range of 0 to 10. The most frequently examined graph-theoretical features were the clustering coefficient (CC) ($N=84$, 62.2%) [86] quantifying the tendency of clustering within the network and the characteristic path length

(CPL) ($N=61$, 45.2%) defined as the *average* of all shortest paths over all pairs of nodes in a network. A total of 57 different graph-theoretical features were identified. The most commonly used metrics (examined in more than 10 studies) are briefly explained in Table 1. More detailed descriptions are available elsewhere [87]. In some studies, graph-theoretical features were normalized by dividing them by the same metric computed from a randomly generated network of identical size, density and/or degree distribution to account for differences in network size and density, introducing additional computational complexity. Largely, studies ($N=31$, 23.8%) examined the normalized clustering coefficient and characteristic path length obtained by dividing the CC and CPL by the CC and CPL of multiple randomly generated networks [18, 20, 79, 81, 84, 88]. For instance, Imms et al. [89] highlighted the use of normalized CC and CPL as diagnostic biomarkers to differentiate between controls and patients with traumatic brain injury.

Feature selection and prediction modelling

Around a third of the 135 quantitative studies ($N=46$, 34.1%) conducted implicit techniques for prediction i.e. elementary statistical analytics (e.g. hypothesis testing, correlation analysis) to identify potential biomarkers associated with the outcome [8, 59, 84, 90] while the remaining studies ($N=89$, 65.9%) conducted prediction modelling using explicit techniques i.e. methods with the possibility of predicting for an unseen individual. Among the latter, about two thirds aimed at the supervised identification of disease subgroups using graph-theoretical features as independent variables ($N=57$, 64.0%) and one third prognosticated a clinical outcome ($N=32$, 36.0%). Despite the similarity of the methodological frameworks, the evaluated studies turned out to be very heterogeneous regarding feature selection, sample size, outcome types, the outcome modelling technique and the validation analytics employed.

Feature selection Feature selection approaches identified in the studies used to define an optimal subset of features can be classified into filter methods (e.g. univariable testing, Pearson correlation) and wrapper methods (iterative optimization of a classification algorithm) but hybrid approaches were also proposed [83]. The majority of studies used filter methods to remove features before training a classifier or a regression model [20, 21, 91]. Wrapper methods (e.g. support vector machine (SVM) with recursive feature elimination (RFE), repeated selection across leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) runs) either iteratively reduced the features based on a ranking score (e.g. feature importance) of the feature in the prediction algorithm to optimize classification

accuracy [25, 63] or selected features with the most discriminative ability out of the full set of features based on repeated least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO) feature selection across LOOCV runs [77].

Prediction modelling The median sample size in neurology was 68 (interquartile range (IQR) 41 to 127), in genomics 445 (IQR: 333–761), and in pathopsychology 62 (IQR: 41–97) as illustrated in Fig. 7A. In pathology, only one study with a sample size of 70 was identified and two studies in cardiology with a sample size of 55 and 389 individuals, respectively. The most commonly investigated types of dependent variables across all 135 quantitative studies were binary ($N=86$, 63.7%), followed by continuous ($N=37$, 27.4%), categorical ($N=14$, 10.4%) and lastly, time-to-event ($N=4$, 3.0%) with some studies assessing multiple outcome types ($N=6$, 4.4%). The considered statistical modelling techniques employed for the task of prediction varied accordingly. Hence, for the sake of clarity, we will distinguish between data modelling and algorithmic modelling approaches according to Breiman [92] (Table 2). The former group contains modelling techniques that connect covariates to the outcome variable by a stochastic model (e.g. linear or logistic regression), while approaches belonging to the latter group use an algorithm to predict the outcome from the covariates (e.g. SVM, random forest). For a complete list of the grouping of the identified methods, we refer to the [supplementary material](#). In general, SVMs were the most popular approach ($N=40$, 45.0%) [27], followed by linear regression ($N=25$, 28.0%) [19, 22, 28, 64, 67, 81, 93, 94], random forests ($N=12$, 13.5%) [15, 41, 58, 72, 95, 96] and logistic regression ($N=9$, 10.1%) [41, 61, 65, 97, 98].

The majority of quantitative studies built discriminative classifiers for discrete outcome labels mainly using only local graph-theoretical features (see Table 2 and Fig. 7B). The most common approach extracted local graph-theoretical features with filter-based feature selection and then trained a linear SVM for outcome classification [16, 30, 37, 62, 77, 83]. A popular choice for feature selection before SVM training and classification was univariable feature screening of statistical significance [10, 13, 14, 34, 36, 74, 78]. However, this method is known to suffer from conceptual shortcomings [99]. In the case of multiple thresholding [74], the use of multiple data modalities [14] or the extraction of multiple local features [32, 100] for classification, a supervised multiple-kernel learning approach was adopted to fuse layers of features to predict disease subgroups. A subset of studies even trained multiple classifiers for the binary classification of the presence of disease (e.g. SVM, k-nearest neighbour, decision tree, random forests, Naïve Bayes, Adaptive Boosting)

Table 2 Types of prediction modelling approach identified in the 89 studies conducting advanced statistical procedures based on graph-theoretical features

	Algorithmic modelling	Data modelling
Total	56	46
Sample size	137.75 (171.46)	168.54 (232.62)
<i>Graph-theoretical scale</i>		
Global	9	23
Local	45	20
Both	2	4
<i>Outcome</i>		
Continuous	5	21
Binary	46	20
Categorical	5	3
Time-to-event	0	2

*Continuous variables stated as mean (standard deviation, SD). Categorical variables represent the number of approaches identified in the studies

[11, 26, 35, 69, 96, 101]. For instance, [26] stated to have built 67 classifiers to differentiate between children with autism spectrum disorder and age-matched controls and 23 advanced regression models for phenotypic prediction.

In terms of model validation, nearly all diagnostic studies reported model discrimination and performance of the classifier in terms of cross-validated accuracy, sensitivity, specificity and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) [12, 23, 25, 27, 70, 77]. Some studies reported estimated predictive accuracy

solely utilizing correlation between the predicted and the true values [93, 96]. In a few studies, performance was claimed to exceed previous approaches, but such a claim was often unsubstantiated and solely based on the comparison between their overall accuracy or AUC and that of the existing studies without consideration of other study factors (study design, set of variables, sample size, heterogeneity between study cohorts) [26, 102, 103]. Imbalanced distribution of class labels was stated as an issue for training accurate classifiers but was accounted for in some studies by assessing the balanced accuracy (i.e. the arithmetic mean of sensitivity and specificity) [58, 70, 74, 100]. Further, calibration analysis as a reliability assessment of the predicted probability of the event actually occurring with the observed relative frequency by the means of a calibration curve was rarely reported in any of the evaluated studies.

Regression-based modelling was mainly performed by linear regression ($N=28$, 60.7%), followed by logistic regression ($N=8$, 17.4%), Cox proportional hazards regression ($N=2$, 4.3%) and mixed-effects modelling ($N=2$, 4.3%). In case global graph-theoretical features were extracted from each individual-specific network or a continuous outcome type was of interest, regression-based analytics were the preferred course of action (see Table 2). The majority of the studies used only graph-theoretical features as independent variables and rarely adjusted for clinical characteristics (e.g. in [15, 18, 21, 22, 67, 73, 80, 97]). Even fewer studies adjusted for network size and density within the regression model to account for their inter-subject differences affecting the extracted graph-theoretical features [79, 81]. Model adjustment by clinical information was more common in studies

investigating the association of global graph-theoretical features with an outcome of interest rather than studies interested in local features. Batalle et al. [61] stated that the graph-theoretical features included in addition to the clinical-epidemiological covariates even proved to yield a higher contribution in terms of statistical significance after separate (blockwise) stepwise backward elimination of variables. However, clinical variables were not only used to adjust the model. For example, Xie et al. [39] proposed a two-stage approach consisting of first, deriving individual-specific network models from conditional Gaussian graphical models dependent on an individual's clinical features and second, the clinical outcome model to estimate the graph-theoretical parameters' effects on an outcome of interest adjusted by the same clinical features.

The sample size of studies conducting regression-based methods was slightly higher and showed a significantly greater variance in comparison with the sample size studies employing classification-based methods (Table 2). Furthermore, possible overfitting of predictive data modelling was rarely directly addressed as in the study by Batalle et al. [61] who reduced preselected graph-theoretical features into a single summary index or in Anderson et al. [98] who restricted the variables which entered the model to 4 to have at least 5 events per variables [104].

Only three of the 130 quantitative studies conducted Cox proportional hazards model to model a time-to-event outcome [66, 77, 79]. Tuladhar et al. [66] identified global efficiency instead of conventional MRI biomarkers as a predictor of all-cause dementia with lower global efficiency associated with a higher risk of dementia onset while adjusting for a set of clinical features. Similarly, Liu et al. [77] stated that none of the traditional clinical features was consistently selected in the majority of the LOOCV runs for overall survival time of high-grade glioma patients and out of the three most important selected features, two were graph-theoretical features.

Discussion

In this scoping review, we identified the state-of-the-art statistical methodology currently employed when using individual-specific networks for prediction in medicine and applied health research. We found a wide range of applications and methodological concepts in our review. We collated the key concepts identified across the 148 included studies considering three main aspects of modelling with individual-specific networks: (1) individual-specific network inference, (2) extraction of graph-theoretical features, and (3) prediction

modelling. Within each of these aspects, there is considerable methodological heterogeneity in the implementation, use, areas of application, and reporting. However, all approaches outlined in this work are in principle generalizable to any field of research and may be suitable to answer various prognostic or diagnostic research questions in medicine.

Individual-specific networks were frequently constructed by evaluating correlations between repeated measurements of pairs of variables (e.g. time-series data of two brain regions). Here we identified two main approaches based on bivariate and partial correlation analysis, some variants thereof, and some further approaches that were often tied to the process of data acquisition itself. Furthermore, the recently proposed visibility graphs offer a flexible approach to individual-specific network inference in relation to time series data. However, sometimes several time series are available per individual so that the individual-specific network is ambiguous, which leads to a further layer of complexity. In the absence of repeated measurements per variable, two novel and promising approaches were LOONC and differential perturbation. Despite their flexibility and ease of application to continuous independent variables, a big challenge in the latter two approaches remains the considerable computational burden, in particular in high-dimensional data settings, due to the repeated computation of the augmented network for each individual [57].

In the pursuit to separate 'real' from 'spurious' connections, in addition to the need for a reduced computational burden, network sparsification has become an important aspect of network analysis. However, sparsification not only depends on the selected technique but, more importantly, also on the chosen threshold, and hence, often multiple thresholds were employed to reduce the impact of a possibly flawed choice, yielding a sequence of networks per individual with varying edge weights. Various approaches were then applied to deal with the sequence of networks; numerical integration or averaging were the most popular approaches together with a threshold selection yielding the best AUROC. Although the majority of studies refrained from using a single, arbitrary threshold value, multiple edge weighting schemes and sparsification strategies were seldom guided by model fit. In addition, sensitivity analyses evaluating the impact of threshold choice on predictive performance were expected but hardly found.

For the extraction of graph-theoretical features, we found a set of global and local features (e.g. see Table 2) that were used in many studies across research fields. For the most part, the clustering coefficient, the

characteristic path length and the edge weights were examined in the search for potential biomarkers of the outcome of interest. Furthermore, the extraction of graph-theoretical features did not follow a deliberate process but often consisted of a greedy collection of network characteristics i.e. the computation and outcome-associated investigation of as many graph-theoretical variables as possible.

Despite the multiplicity of identified methodological approaches for individual-specific network inference across fields of application, the number of studies that proposed models actually intended to provide clinical outcome prediction for future individuals was quite limited, and most models were estimated to provide a proof-of-concept that graph-theoretical features may in principle be useful for outcome prediction. The lack of deployable clinical prediction models could be either a consequence of the fundamental challenges in network inference methods shared by all areas of application, in particular concerning the lack of a gold standard for network construction and sparsification, or of the general unawareness in how individual-specific networks can be exploited for prediction.

Through the systematic collation of the identified analytical approaches, we found some areas interesting for future research and which may help to reduce some of the arbitrariness of some analytical choices.

First, more research is needed to reduce the computational burden related to the construction and analysis of relatively large and dense networks and the inherent computational complexity of graph metric computation. Large omics studies generate substantial amounts of data which can lead to major computational difficulties in network inference and further analysis, if each node in the network represents a single variable. In particular, LOONC and differential perturbation approaches would suffer in such a data setting due to the computational burden caused by the repeated network computation for each individual in the study cohort. One possible strategy for reducing network complexity and facilitating network analysis and feature extraction could be node aggregation over groups of connected, non-independent nodes (modules). In this sense, variables could be combined as modules either through unsupervised clustering algorithms or through biological background knowledge, so that each node represents a group of independent variables and no longer a single variable.

Second, network sparsification and multivariable model estimation could be linked more closely by guiding the search for a suitable threshold or the integration over several thresholds by the model fit. Multiple thresholding yields a set of sequential graph-theoretical estimates of the networks that are computed over a fine grid on

a continuous domain using incremental steps between threshold values (e.g. grid searching). Ideas from functional data analysis could be transferred to the area of modelling with individual-specific networks. Briefly, instead of choosing a threshold that provides univariably optimal prediction performance, or integration over multiple pre-specified thresholds with equal weights of each threshold, one could interpret the individual-specific sequence of graph-theoretical features corresponding to the set of sparsified networks $\mathcal{G}_s := \{G_{s,\tau_k}\}_{k=1,\dots,T}$ as a functional data predictor. Then, one may define a flexible weighting function of $\tau_k, f(\tau_k)$, through outcome-guided calibration to optimize clinical prediction. Consequently, such an analysis would also yield an estimate of the relative importance of different thresholds for network sparsification. Alternatively, carefully conducted sensitivity analyses would allow evaluating to what extent the reported results depended on the choice of the selected threshold value in particular for studies continuing the search for the optimal threshold parameter by univariate analysis.

Further, the comparison of networks of varying sizes and edge densities can impose issues for prediction modelling since some graph-theoretical features are confounded by them [80]. The inclusion of these two features regardless of ‘significance’ may reduce the magnitude of bias, and improve prediction performance and explainability of such models [105]. Omission of these confounding variables could mask the actual effects of interest in model explanation. Generally, graph-theoretic features are inherently associated with each other, and more research is needed to better understand these associations.

In contrast, a reoccurring problem of multivariable model building was found in the evaluated studies: “univariable prefiltering” of variables in which only variables with a statistically significant association with the outcome are included in the model [106, 107]. However, a p -value above the statistical significance threshold of 5% is not sufficient evidence for the lack of an effect of the independent variable [108]. The popularity of prefiltering across the evaluated studies can presumably be traced back to the greedy collection of graph-theoretical features or to a disproportional number of local graph features that were obtained relative to sample size. Since the actual goal of univariable preselection was often a considerable reduction of the number of independent variables proportional to the sample size to seemingly avoid overfit, defining a minimum basic set of features (MBSF) to investigate may be beneficial when network analysis is employed for prediction. The identification of such an MBSF, however, is not an easy task and may require investigations across a range of applications embedded in the respective research fields.

Lastly, future studies should investigate the added benefit of graph-theoretical features in addition to clinical variables so as not to examine their clinical utility separately from traditional variables and hence, improve existing clinical prediction models. We have seen that graph-theoretical variables were mostly examined independently, which was partly due to the relatively low samples across the evaluated studies but also due to the dominant preference of algorithmic classification approaches with local graph-theoretical features, where clinical information was largely ignored. In some studies, in which graph-theoretical features were examined together with clinical variables, these even turned out to be stronger predictors than the traditional set of clinical variables. It remains elusive if this could be explained by publication bias or demonstrates the clinical relevance of graph-theoretical features.

Research on the aforementioned points is essential to establish a state-of-the-art and to provide more evidence-based guidance in using individual-specific networks for the prediction of clinical outcomes to applied researchers. Despite the identified aspects for future research, our scoping review is subject to some limitations. First, we may have missed some relevant applications due to the lack of standardized terminology to describe the intersection of network analysis (in particular approaches to construct individual-specific networks) and prediction modelling but also because of the ambiguity of the term 'network'. Secondly, by limiting our study to applications in medicine and health research, we may not have captured studies that employed individual-specific networks in which the individuals do not represent patients but other individual entities. Thirdly, since the screening of 4988 studies and extracting data for the 148 articles included in this review was laborious, some time passed between identification of studies and completion of data extraction. Nevertheless, we decided not to update our search to include more recent articles (i.e. published from August 2020 onwards) because we do not believe that there were substantial changes in practice in the intervening time. Last but not least, this review focused on the use of individual-specific network analysis for prediction which is why existing refinements of the presented methods for network construction and extraction of graph-theoretic ones might not have passed the inclusion criteria of our search strategy.

At this juncture, it is important to emphasize that we have not assessed the quality of included studies and did not perform a risk of bias assessment. This was done in agreement with the general guidelines on conducting a scoping review. Consequently, our review is unable to make definitive recommendations for practice but rather

describes the current methodological practice and possible areas of future research [7, 109].

Conclusion

Network analysis offers a flexible tool for personalized medicine, hence prediction with individual-specific networks is an emerging field full of potential for future research. The application in clinical research is still in its infancy but our findings can strengthen the methodological conduct to incorporate individual-specific network analysis in predictive tasks. The framework still requires further refinement, and research must cover statistical, computational and application-specific aspects. In addition to methodological advances, comparative studies of proposed methodologies are needed to understand how methods compare and which method works best in a specific setting. This may eventually lead to establishing a state-of-the-art in this novel and fascinating scientific arena located at the cross-section of statistics, computer science and medicine.

Abbreviations

AUC: Area under the curve; A: Assortativity; BC: Betweenness centrality; BOLD: Blood oxygenation level-dependent; CC: Clustering coefficient; CPL: Characteristic path length; DAG: Directed acyclic graph; Dg: Degree; Ds: Density; EEG: Electroencephalography; EW: Edge weight; GE: Global efficiency; HRV: Heart rate variability; IQR: Interquartile range; LASSO: Least absolute shrinkage and selection operator; LE: Local efficiency; LOONC: Leave-one-out network construction; LOOCV: Leave-one-out cross-validation; M: Modularity; MBSF: Minimum basic set of features; RFE: Recursive feature elimination; SD: Standard deviation; SVM: Support vector machine; SWI: Small world index; ROI: Region of interest; VAR: Vector autoregressive.

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-022-01544-6>.

Additional file 1. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist

Additional file 2: Supplementary Material S1. Detailed Methods.

Table S1. Keyword sets used in the search strategy across the databases for article extraction. **Figure S1.** Year of publication of the identified studies. **Table S2.** Scale of the graph-theoretical features used as candidate predictors stratified by the area of application.

Additional file 3. Supplementary Material S2. Questionnaire for full-text screening

Acknowledgements

KVS and FM acknowledge the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 860895 (TransSys-h2020transys.eu). KVS also acknowledges the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 813533 (MLFPM-mlfpm.eu).

Authors' contributions

MG was responsible for the conception, design of the study, search, screening, inclusion of relevant articles, data extraction of eligible studies and wrote the initial draft of the manuscript. GH was responsible for the conception, design and carried out the screening and data extraction of a fraction of articles. FM and MS conducted screening and data extraction of a fraction of articles. GH, KVS and SM revised the draft critically for important intellectual content. All authors agreed to the final submission.

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 860895 (FM, KVS).

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Declarations**Ethics approval and consent to participate**

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author details

¹Section for Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Statistics, Informatics and Intelligent Systems, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria. ²Division of Nephrology and Dialysis, Department of Internal Medicine III, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria. ³BIO3 Laboratory for Systems Medicine, Department of Human Genetics, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium. ⁴Service de Biostatistique et d'Epidémiologie, Gustave Roussy, Oncostat U1018, Inserm, University Paris-Saclay, labeled Ligue Contre le Cancer, Villejuif, France. ⁵BIO3 Laboratory for Systems Genetics, GIGA-R Medical Genomics, University of Liège, Liège, Belgium.

Received: 27 July 2021 Accepted: 11 February 2022

Published online: 06 March 2022

References

- Hastie T, Tibshirani R, Friedman J. The elements of statistical learning. New York: Springer Series in Statistics; 2001.
- Van Calster B, van Smeden M, De Cock B, Steyerberg EW. Regression shrinkage methods for clinical prediction models do not guarantee improved performance: simulation study. *Stat Methods Med Res*. 2020;29(11):3166–78.
- Šinkovec H, Heinze G, Blagus R, Geroldinger A. To tune or not to tune, a case study of ridge logistic regression in small or sparse datasets. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2021;21(1):199.
- Barabási A-L, Gulbahce N, Loscalzo J. Network medicine: a network-based approach to human disease. *Nat Rev Genet*. 2011;12(1):56–68.
- Li MM, Huang K, Zitnik M. Graph Representation Learning in Biomedicine. *arXiv*. 2021;210404883.v2. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.04883>. Accessed 10 Nov 2021.
- Peters MD, Marnie C, Tricco AC, Pollock D, Munn Z, Alexander L, et al. Updated methodological guidance for the conduct of scoping reviews. *JBI Evid Synth*. 2020;18(10):2119–26.
- Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Ann Intern Med*. 2018;169(7):467–73.
- Dong Z, Li X, Chen W. Frequency network analysis of heart rate variability for obstructive apnea patient detection. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*. 2017;22(6):1895–905.
- Sáez A, Rivas E, Montero-Sánchez A, Paradas C, Acha B, Pascual A, et al. Quantifiable diagnosis of muscular dystrophies and neurogenic atrophies through network analysis. *BMC Med*. 2013;11(1):1–11.
- Bian J, Xie M, Topaloglu U, Cislér JM. A Probabilistic Model of Functional Brain Connectivity Network for Discovering Novel Biomarkers. *AMIA Summ Transl Sci Proc*. 2013;2013:21.
- Saghayni M, Greenberg J, O'Grady C, Varno F, Hashmi MA, Bracken B, et al. Brain network topology predicts participant adherence to mental training programs. *Netw Neurosci*. 2020;4(3):528–55.
- Xu X, Li W, Mei J, Tao M, Wang X, Zhao Q, et al. Feature selection and combination of information in the functional brain connectome for discrimination of mild cognitive impairment and analyses of altered brain patterns. *Front Aging Neurosci*. 2020;12:28.
- Khazaee A, Ebrahimzadeh A, Babajani-Feremi A. Identifying patients with Alzheimer's disease using resting-state fMRI and graph theory. *Clin Neurophysiol*. 2015;126(11):2132–41.
- Wee C-Y, Yap P-T, Zhang D, Denny K, Browndyke JN, Potter GG, et al. Identification of MCI individuals using structural and functional connectivity networks. *NeuroImage*. 2012;59(3):2045–56.
- Paldino MJ, Zhang W, Chu ZD, Golriz F. Metrics of brain network architecture capture the impact of disease in children with epilepsy. *NeuroImage: Clin*. 2017;13:201–8.
- Li Y, Wang Y, Wu G, Shi F, Zhou L, Lin W, et al. Discriminant analysis of longitudinal cortical thickness changes in Alzheimer's disease using dynamic and network features. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2012;33(2):427 e15–e30.
- Paldino MJ, Golriz F, Zhang W, Chu ZD. Normalization enhances brain network features that predict individual intelligence in children with epilepsy. *PLoS One*. 2019;14(3):e0212901.
- Rimkus CM, Schoonheim MM, Steenwijk MD, Vrenken H, Eijlers AJ, Killestein J, et al. Gray matter networks and cognitive impairment in multiple sclerosis. *Mult Scler J*. 2019;25(3):382–91.
- Finn ES, Shen X, Scheinost D, Rosenberg MD, Huang J, Chun MM, et al. Functional connectome fingerprinting: identifying individuals using patterns of brain connectivity. *Nat Neurosci*. 2015;18(11):1664–71.
- van Duinkerken E, Ijzerman RG, Klein M, Moll AC, Snoek FJ, Scheltens P, et al. Disrupted subject-specific gray matter network properties and cognitive dysfunction in type 1 diabetes patients with and without proliferative retinopathy. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2016;37(3):1194–208.
- De Baene W, Rutten GJM, Sitskoorn MM. Cognitive functioning in glioma patients is related to functional connectivity measures of the non-tumoural hemisphere. *Eur J Neurosci*. 2019;50(12):3921–33.
- Wang Z, Zhang D, Liang B, Chang S, Pan J, Huang R, et al. Prediction of biological motion perception performance from intrinsic brain network regional efficiency. *Front Hum Neurosci*. 2016;10:552.
- Sen B, Bernstein GA, Mueller BA, Cullen KR, Parhi KK. Sub-graph entropy based network approaches for classifying adolescent obsessive-compulsive disorder from resting-state functional MRI. *NeuroImage: Clin*. 2020;26:102208.
- Cheng H, Newman S, Goñi J, Kent JS, Howell J, Bolbecker A, et al. Nodal centrality of functional network in the differentiation of schizophrenia. *Schizophr Res*. 2015;168(1–2):345–52.
- Wen H, Liu Y, Rekik I, Wang S, Chen Z, Zhang J, et al. Combining disrupted and discriminative topological properties of functional connectivity networks as neuroimaging biomarkers for accurate diagnosis of early tourette syndrome children. *Mol Neurobiol*. 2018;55(4):3251–69.
- Zhou Y, Yu F, Duong T. Multiparametric MRI characterization and prediction in autism spectrum disorder using graph theory and machine learning. *PLoS One*. 2014;9(6):e90405.
- Hojjati SH, Ebrahimzadeh A, Babajani-Feremi A. Identification of the early stage of Alzheimer's disease using structural MRI and resting-state fMRI. *Front Neurol*. 2019;10:904.
- Yamashita M, Kawato M, Imamizu H. Predicting learning plateau of working memory from whole-brain intrinsic network connectivity patterns. *Sci Rep*. 2015;5(1):1–8.
- Zhang T, Zhao Z, Zhang C, Zhang J, Jin Z, Li L. Classification of early and late mild cognitive impairment using functional brain network of resting-state fMRI. *Front Psych*. 2019;10:572.
- Zhou L, Wang Y, Li Y, Yap P-T, Shen D. Initiative AsDN. Hierarchical anatomical brain networks for MCI prediction: revisiting volumetric measures. *PLoS One*. 2011;6(7):e21935.
- Richiardi J, Achard S, Bunke H, Van De Ville D. Machine learning with brain graphs: predictive modeling approaches for functional imaging in systems neuroscience. *IEEE Signal Process Mag*. 2013;30(3):58–70.
- Zhang Y, Zhang H, Chen X, Lee S-W, Shen D. Hybrid high-order functional connectivity networks using resting-state functional MRI for mild cognitive impairment diagnosis. *Sci Rep*. 2017;7(1):1–15.
- Damaraju E, Allen EA, Belger A, Ford JM, McEwen S, Mathalon D, et al. Dynamic functional connectivity analysis reveals transient states of dysconnectivity in schizophrenia. *NeuroImage: Clin*. 2014;5:298–308.

34. Qiao L, Zhang H, Kim M, Teng S, Zhang L, Shen D. Estimating functional brain networks by incorporating a modularity prior. *NeuroImage*. 2016;141:399–407.
35. Cecchi GA, Rish I, Thyreau B, Thirion B, Plaze M, Paillere-Martinot M-L, et al. Discriminative Network Models of SchizophreniaNIPS; 2009.
36. Wee C-Y, Yap P-T, Zhang D, Wang L, Shen D. Group-constrained sparse fMRI connectivity modeling for mild cognitive impairment identification. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2014;219(2):641–56.
37. Bohland JW, Saperstein S, Pereira F, Rapin J, Grady L. Network, anatomical, and non-imaging measures for the prediction of ADHD diagnosis in individual subjects. *Front Syst Neurosci*. 2012;6:78.
38. Lord L-D, Allen P, Expert P, Howes O, Broome M, Lambiotte R, et al. Functional brain networks before the onset of psychosis: a prospective fMRI study with graph theoretical analysis. *NeuroImage: Clin*. 2012;1(1):91–8.
39. Xie S, Li X, McColgan P, Scahill RI, Zeng D, Wang Y. Identifying disease-associated biomarker network features through conditional graphical model. *Biometrics*. 2020;76(3):995–1006.
40. Booij SH, Wichers M, De Jonge P, Sytema S, Van Os J, Wunderink L, et al. Study protocol for a prospective cohort study examining the predictive potential of dynamic symptom networks for the onset and progression of psychosis: the Mapping Individual Routes of Risk and Resilience (MIRROR) study. *BMJ Open*. 2018;8(1):e019059.
41. Lutz W, Schwartz B, Hofmann SG, Fisher AJ, Husen K, Rubel JA. Using network analysis for the prediction of treatment dropout in patients with mood and anxiety disorders: A methodological proof-of-concept study. *Sci Rep*. 2018;8(1):1–9.
42. Lacasa L, Luque B, Ballesteros F, Luque J, Nuno JC. From time series to complex networks: The visibility graph. *Proc Natl Acad Sci*. 2008;105(13):4972–5.
43. Ahmadlou M, Adeli H, Adeli A. New diagnostic EEG markers of the Alzheimer's disease using visibility graph. *J Neural Transm*. 2010;117(9):1099–109.
44. Bajestani GS, Behrooz M, Khani AG, Nouri-Baygi M, Mollaei A. Diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder based on complex network features. *Comput Methods Prog Biomed*. 2019;177:277–83.
45. Grobelny BT, London D, Hill TC, North E, Dugan P, Doyle WK. Betweenness centrality of intracranial electroencephalography networks and surgical epilepsy outcome. *Clin Neurophysiol*. 2018;129(9):1804–12.
46. Hou F, Li F, Wang J, Yan F. Visibility graph analysis of very short-term heart rate variability during sleep. *Phys A Stat Mech Appl*. 2016;458:140–5.
47. Chen S, Gallagher MJ, Hogg F, Papadopoulos MC, Saadoun S. Visibility graph analysis of intraspinal pressure signal predicts functional outcome in spinal cord injured patients. *J Neurotrauma*. 2018;35(24):2947–56.
48. Silva VF, Silva ME, Ribeiro P, Silva F. Time series analysis via network science: Concepts and algorithms. *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Data Min Knowl Discov*. 2021;11(3):e1404.
49. Zhang Z, Ding J, Xu J, Tang J, Guo F. Multi-scale Time-series Kernel-based Learning Method for Brain Disease Diagnosis. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*. 2021;25(1):209–17.
50. Homan P, Argyelan M, DeRosse P, Szeszko PR, Gallego JA, Hanna L, et al. Structural similarity networks predict clinical outcome in early-phase psychosis. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2019;44(5):915–22.
51. Philips GR, Daly JJ, Príncipe JC. Topographical measures of functional connectivity as biomarkers for post-stroke motor recovery. *J Neuroeng Rehabil*. 2017;14(1):1–16.
52. Kuijjer ML, Tung MG, Yuan G, Quackenbush J, Glass K. Estimating sample-specific regulatory networks. *Iscience*. 2019;14:226–40.
53. Lopes-Ramos CM, Kuijjer ML, Ogino S, Fuchs CS, DeMeo DL, Glass K, et al. Gene regulatory network analysis identifies sex-linked differences in colon cancer drug metabolism. *Cancer Res*. 2018;78(19):5538–47.
54. Zhu K, Pian C, Xiang Q, Liu X, Chen Y. Personalized analysis of breast cancer using sample-specific networks. *PeerJ*. 2020;8:e9161.
55. Liu X, Wang Y, Ji H, Aihara K, Chen L. Personalized characterization of diseases using sample-specific networks. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2016;44(22):e164–e.
56. Audrain S, Barnett AJ, McAndrews MP. Language network measures at rest indicate individual differences in naming decline after anterior temporal lobe resection. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2018;39(11):4404–19.
57. Huang Y, Chang X, Zhang Y, Chen L, Liu X. Disease characterization using a partial correlation-based sample-specific network. *Brief Bioinform*. 2021;22(3):bbaa062.
58. Das T, Borgwardt S, Hauke DJ, Harrisberger F, Lang UE, Riecher-Rössler A, et al. Disorganized gyrification network properties during the transition to psychosis. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 2018;75(6):613–22.
59. Park B, Lee W, Park I, Han K. Finding prognostic gene pairs for cancer from patient-specific gene networks. *BMC Med Genet*. 2019;12(8):1–14.
60. Boot EM, van Leijsen EM, Bergkamp MI, Kessels RP, Norris DG, de Leeuw F-E, et al. Structural network efficiency predicts cognitive decline in cerebral small vessel disease. *NeuroImage: Clin*. 2020;27:102325.
61. Bataille D, Eixarch E, Figueras F, Muñoz-Moreno E, Bargallo N, Illa M, et al. Altered small-world topology of structural brain networks in infants with intrauterine growth restriction and its association with later neurodevelopmental outcome. *NeuroImage*. 2012;60(2):1352–66.
62. Sun Y, Bi Q, Wang X, Hu X, Li H, Li X, et al. Prediction of conversion from amnesic mild cognitive impairment to Alzheimer's disease based on the brain structural connectome. *Front Neurol*. 2019;9:1178.
63. Wee C-Y, Yap P-T, Li W, Denny K, Browndyke JN, Potter GG, et al. Enriched white matter connectivity networks for accurate identification of MCI patients. *NeuroImage*. 2011;54(3):1812–22.
64. Welton T, Constantinescu CS, Auer DP, Dineen RA. Graph theoretic analysis of brain Connectomics in multiple sclerosis: Reliability and relationship with cognition. *Brain Connectivity*. 2020;10(2):95–104.
65. Du J, Wang Y, Zhi N, Geng J, Cao W, Yu L, et al. Structural brain network measures are superior to vascular burden scores in predicting early cognitive impairment in post stroke patients with small vessel disease. *NeuroImage: Clin*. 2019;22:101712.
66. Tuladhar AM, van Uden IW, Rutten-Jacobs LC, Lawrence A, van der Holst H, van Norden A, et al. Structural network efficiency predicts conversion to dementia. *Neurology*. 2016;86(12):1112–9.
67. Yeo RA, Ryman SG, Van Den Heuvel MP, De Reus MA, Jung RE, Pommy J, et al. Graph metrics of structural brain networks in individuals with schizophrenia and healthy controls: group differences, relationships with intelligence, and genetics. *J Int Neuropsychol Soc*. 2016;22(2):240.
68. Gou L, Zhang W, Li C, Shi X, Zhou Z, Zhong W, et al. Structural brain network alteration and its correlation with structural impairments in patients with depression in de novo and drug-naive Parkinson's disease. *Front Neurol*. 2018;9:608.
69. Liu W, Zhang C, Wang X, Xu J, Chang Y, Ristaniemi T, et al. Functional connectivity of major depression disorder using ongoing EEG during music perception. *Clin Neurophysiol*. 2020;131(10):2413–22.
70. Babajani-Feremi A, Noorizadeh N, Mudigoudar B, Wheless JW. Predicting seizure outcome of vagus nerve stimulation using MEG-based network topology. *NeuroImage: Clin*. 2018;19:990–9.
71. Gomez-Pilar J, de Luis-García R, Lubeiro A, de la Red H, Poza J, Núñez P, et al. Relations between structural and EEG-based graph metrics in healthy controls and schizophrenia patients. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2018;39(8):3152–65.
72. Van Diessen E, Otte WM, Braun KP, Stam CJ, Jansen FE. Improved diagnosis in children with partial epilepsy using a multivariable prediction model based on EEG network characteristics. *PLoS One*. 2013;8(4):e59764.
73. Wen W, Zhu W, He Y, Kochan NA, Reppermund S, Slavin MJ, et al. Discrete neuroanatomical networks are associated with specific cognitive abilities in old age. *J Neurosci*. 2011;31(4):1204–12.
74. Jie B, Zhang D, Wee CY, Shen D. Topological graph kernel on multiple thresholded functional connectivity networks for mild cognitive impairment classification. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2014;35(7):2876–97.
75. dos Santos SA, Biazoli Junior CE, Comfort WE, Rohde LA, Sato JR. Abnormal functional resting-state networks in ADHD: graph theory and pattern recognition analysis of fMRI data. *Biomed Res Int*. 2014;2014:380531.
76. Hou Z, Wang Z, Jiang W, Yin Y, Yue Y, Zhang Y, et al. Divergent topological architecture of the default mode network as a pretreatment predictor of early antidepressant response in major depressive disorder. *Sci Rep*. 2016;6(1):1–9.
77. Liu L, Zhang H, Wu J, Yu Z, Chen X, Rekić I, et al. Overall survival time prediction for high-grade glioma patients based on large-scale brain functional networks. *Brain Imaging Behaviour*. 2019;13(5):1333–51.

78. Yu R, Zhang H, An L, Chen X, Wei Z, Shen D. Connectivity strength-weighted sparse group representation-based brain network construction for MCI classification. *Hum Brain Mapp.* 2017;38(5):2370–83.
79. Tijms BM, Ten Kate M, Gouw AA, Borta A, Verfaillie S, Teunissen CE, et al. Gray matter networks and clinical progression in subjects with pre-dementia Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging.* 2018;61:75–81.
80. Tijms BM, Yeung HM, Sikkes SA, Möller C, Smits LL, Stam CJ, et al. Single-subject gray matter graph properties and their relationship with cognitive impairment in early-and late-onset Alzheimer's disease. *Brain Connectivity.* 2014;4(5):337–46.
81. Hawkins R, Shatil A, Lee L, Sengupta A, Zhang L, Morrow S, et al. Reduced global efficiency and random network features in patients with relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis with cognitive impairment. *Am J Neuroradiol.* 2020;41(3):449–55.
82. Jie B, Liu M, Zhang D, Shen D. Sub-network kernels for measuring similarity of brain connectivity networks in disease diagnosis. *IEEE Trans Image Process.* 2018;27(5):2340–53.
83. Dai D, He H, Vogelstein JT, Hou Z. Accurate prediction of AD patients using cortical thickness networks. *Mach Vis Appl.* 2013;24(7):1445–57.
84. Langer N, Pedroni A, Gianotti LR, Hänggi J, Knöch D, Jäncke L. Functional brain network efficiency predicts intelligence. *Hum Brain Mapp.* 2012;33(6):1393–406.
85. Hashmi JA, Kong J, Spaeth R, Khan S, Kaptchuk TJ, Gollub RL. Functional network architecture predicts psychologically mediated analgesia related to treatment in chronic knee pain patients. *J Neurosci.* 2014;34(11):3924–36.
86. Watts DJ, Strogatz SH. Collective dynamics of 'small-world' networks. *nature.* 1998;393(6684):440–2.
87. Rubinov M, Sporns O. Complex network measures of brain connectivity: uses and interpretations. *NeuroImage.* 2010;52(3):1059–69.
88. Tijms BM, Möller C, Vrenken H, Wink AM, de Haan W, van der Flier WM, et al. Single-subject grey matter graphs in Alzheimer's disease. *PLoS One.* 2013;8(3):e58921.
89. Imms P, Clemente A, Cook M, D'Souza W, Wilson PH, Jones DK, et al. The structural connectome in traumatic brain injury: A meta-analysis of graph metrics. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2019;99:128–37.
90. Lee J, Lee M, Kim D-S, Kim Y-H. Functional reorganization and prediction of motor recovery after a stroke: a graph theoretical analysis of functional networks. *Restor Neurol Neurosci.* 2015;33(6):785–93.
91. Raamana PR, Weiner MW, Wang L, Beg MF. Initiative AsDN. Thickness network features for prognostic applications in dementia. *Neurobiol Aging.* 2015;36:S91–S102.
92. Breiman L. Statistical modeling: The two cultures (with comments and a rejoinder by the author). *Stat Sci.* 2001;16(3):199–231.
93. Christov-Moore L, Reggente N, Douglas PK, Feusner JD, Iacoboni M. Predicting empathy from resting state brain connectivity: A multivariate approach. *Front Integr Neurosci.* 2020;14:3.
94. Doucet GE, Rider R, Taylor N, Skidmore C, Sharan A, Sperling M, et al. Presurgery resting-state local graph-theory measures predict neurocognitive outcomes after brain surgery in temporal lobe epilepsy. *Epilepsia.* 2015;56(4):517–26.
95. Corps J, Reikik I. Morphological brain age prediction using multi-view brain networks derived from cortical morphology in healthy and disordered participants. *Sci Rep.* 2019;9(1):1–10.
96. Gheiratmand M, Rish I, Cecchi GA, Brown MR, Greiner R, Polosecki PI, et al. Learning stable and predictive network-based patterns of schizophrenia and its clinical symptoms. *NPJ Schizophr.* 2017;3(1):1–12.
97. Dicks E, Tijms BM, Ten Kate M, Gouw AA, Benedictus MR, Teunissen CE, et al. Gray matter network measures are associated with cognitive decline in mild cognitive impairment. *Neurobiol Aging.* 2018;61:198–206.
98. Anderson ED, Giudice JS, Wu T, Panzer MB, Meaney DF. Predicting concussion outcome by integrating finite element modeling and network analysis. *Front Bioeng Biotechnol.* 2020;8:309.
99. Sun G-W, Shook TL, Kay GL. Inappropriate use of bivariable analysis to screen risk factors for use in multivariable analysis. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 1996;49(8):907–16.
100. Jie B, Wee C-Y, Shen D, Zhang D. Hyper-connectivity of functional networks for brain disease diagnosis. *Med Image Anal.* 2016;32:84–100.
101. Xu M, Sanz DL, Garces P, Maestu F, Li Q, Pantazis D. A Graph Gaussian Embedding Method for Predicting Alzheimer's Disease Progression with MEG Brain Networks. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng.* 2021;68(5):1579–88.
102. Rashid B, Calhoun V. Towards a brain-based predictive model of mental illness. *Hum Brain Mapp.* 2020;41(12):3468–535.
103. Wei R, Li C, Fogelson N, Li L. Prediction of conversion from mild cognitive impairment to Alzheimer's Disease using MRI and structural network features. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2016;8:76.
104. Vittinghoff E, McCulloch CE. Relaxing the rule of ten events per variable in logistic and Cox regression. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2007;165(6):710–8.
105. Shrier I, Platt RW. Reducing bias through directed acyclic graphs. *BMC Med Res Methodol.* 2008;8(1):1–15.
106. Heinze G, Wallisch C, Dunkler D. Variable selection—a review and recommendations for the practicing statistician. *Biom J.* 2018;60(3):431–49.
107. Heinze G, Dunkler D. Five myths about variable selection. *Transp Int.* 2017;30(1):6–10.
108. Steyerberg EW. *Clinical prediction models: a practical approach to development, validation, and updating.* New York: Springer; 2019.
109. Khalil H, Peters M, Tricco A, Pollock D, Alexander L, McInerney P, et al. Conducting high quality scoping reviews—challenges and solutions. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2021;130:156–60.

Publisher's Note

Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Ready to submit your research? Choose BMC and benefit from:

- fast, convenient online submission
- thorough peer review by experienced researchers in your field
- rapid publication on acceptance
- support for research data, including large and complex data types
- gold Open Access which fosters wider collaboration and increased citations
- maximum visibility for your research: over 100M website views per year

At BMC, research is always in progress.

Learn more biomedcentral.com/submissions

3.3 Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction

Authors: Mariella Gregorich¹, Sean L. Simpson², Georg Heinze¹

Affiliations: ¹ Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Data Science, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria; ² Department of Biostatistics and Data Science, Wake Forest University School of Medicine, Winston-Salem, NC, USA

Publication status: The revision of the manuscript is currently under review in the peer-reviewed journal *Statistics in Medicine*. The revised manuscript is provided herein.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.15365>

Interlude: In the scoping review in Paper II, we identified methodological gaps in individual-specific network inference. In particular, we noticed a lack of consensus regarding the appropriate threshold selection approach when network sparsification of correlation-based network construction is performed. Therefore, we proposed a novel methodology tailored for individual-specific network inference in prediction modelling in Paper III. Briefly, we employed flexible parametrization of the values of a graph-theoretical feature corresponding to the full range of sparsity thresholds applied to individual-specific networks by incorporating a data-driven weighting function determined by statistical goodness-of-fit criteria to capture the relative leverage of graph-theoretical features across varying sparsity levels on the outcome. To evaluate the empirical properties of our proposed approach, we developed a comprehensive plasmode simulation study that uses individual-specific network-structured in-silico data. We compared the flexible parametrization approach with the state-of-the-art competitor approaches in the simulation study and a real-life data example for the prediction of brain maturity in children.

Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction

Mariella Gregorich¹, Sean L. Simpson² and Georg Heinze^{1,*}

¹Medical University of Vienna, Center for Medical Data Science, Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Vienna, Austria

²Department of Biostatistics and Data Science, Wake Forest University School of Medicine, Winston-Salem, NC, USA

*Corresponding author

Abstract

Statistical techniques are needed to analyse data structures with complex dependencies such that clinically useful information can be extracted. Individual-specific networks, which capture dependencies in complex biological systems, are often summarized by graph-theoretical features. These features, which lend themselves to outcome modelling, can be subject to high variability due to arbitrary decisions in network inference and noise. Correlation-based adjacency matrices often need to be sparsified before meaningful graph-theoretical features can be extracted, requiring the data analysts to determine an optimal threshold. To address this issue, we propose to incorporate a flexible weighting function over the full range of possible thresholds to capture the variability of graph-theoretical features over the threshold domain. The potential of this approach, which extends concepts from functional data analysis to a graph-theoretical setting, is explored in a plasmode simulation study using real functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) data from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) Preprocessed initiative. The simulations show that our modelling approach yields accurate estimates of the functional form of the weight function, improves inference efficiency, and achieves a comparable or reduced root mean square prediction error compared to competitor modelling approaches. This assertion holds true in settings where both complex functional forms underlie the outcome-generating process and a universal threshold value is employed. We demonstrate the practical utility of our approach by using resting-state fMRI data to predict biological age in children. Our study establishes the flexible modelling approach as a statistically principled, serious competitor to ad-hoc methods with superior performance.

Keywords: networks; complex systems; prediction; splines; fMRI

1. Introduction

In recent years, network-based studies have gained popularity, particularly those focused on individual-specific network inference, which involves estimating a separate connectivity matrix (adjacency matrix) across a common set of nodes for each individual subject in the study cohort. A key clinical challenge is to translate the heterogeneous dependency structure among individuals into clinically useful information that can aid in better clinical decision making at the individual level. For instance, functional connectivity in resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging (rs-fMRI) can be inferred through the correlations of the temporal pairwise blood oxygen level dependent (BOLD) signals among different regions of interest (ROIs) in the brain. In neuroscientific investigations, graph-theoretical features have shown immense utility, serving as valuable predictors for a wide range of neurological outcomes, including the cognitive abilities and the brain maturity of children, adolescents and young adults,¹⁻⁵ with the primary objective to identify risk factors from brain imaging data for neurological conditions, neural development and behaviour. However, individual-specific network inference based on observational data can be difficult due to nuisance or confounding factors, which must be taken into account when using these networks for prediction modelling.

Despite the increasing use and understanding of graph theory, many network inference methods include sparsification as a pre-processing step, which selects the network representative from a large space of possible network representations for an individual. Sparsification procedures are commonly applied to remove weaker links, which are most affected by experimental noise (e.g. physiological processes, subject motion or fluctuations caused by the scanner) not related to the underlying neural activity being studied and thus deemed spurious. The lack of consensus regarding the thresholding strategy keeps this topic an area of ongoing research.⁶⁻¹⁰ Past research has recognized the variability of graph-theoretical features based on the threshold used in network sparsification.⁷ Yet, prevailing practices often employ naive ad-hoc methods, such as depending on a single threshold (optimal threshold selection; OPT) or averaging features across an arbitrary subset of thresholds (averaging feature approach; AVG). Instead of selecting a single, optimal parameter value, we propose to use the complete sequence of graph-theoretical features obtained at each threshold value. We introduce a data-driven flexibly weighting function aimed at modelling the varying influence of the graph-theoretical feature at each threshold on the outcome. The flexible weighting function assigns weights based on the degree of influence the features has on the outcome, which avoids relying on a-priori specifications. It generalizes the concept of sparsification in individual-specific network inference to a functional setting and offers a novel functional thresholding approach to tackle the uncertainty associated with threshold selection for achieving both adequate network sparsity and good predictive performance.

Motivated by the limited research in individual-specific network sparsification for prediction modelling, we compare the proposed flexible approach with two ad-hoc competitors, optimized threshold selection and averaging over a range of thresholds. This study is intended to encompass an early phase of methodological evaluation (see the concept of phases of methodological research¹¹). The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the general terminology, followed by a delineation of the current common practice in network sparsification, and our proposed flexible approach. Section 3 presents a comparison of our approach with alternative methods through numerical studies. A real-life data application employing rs-fMRI data of children recorded while watching a movie to predict their age is presented in Section 4. Finally, in Section 5, we discuss the findings. Due to space limitations, a detailed description of the simulation studies and the analysis of the real data example have been relegated to the supplementary material.

2. Methods

In this section, we will begin by introducing some general notation and briefly present current statistical practices of using individual-specific networks for prediction. We will subsequently propose a novel flexible approach.

2.1. Concepts of graph theory

Given relational data per individual $i, i = 1, \dots, N$, the complex connection pattern can be represented by a network where, for each individual, a separate connectivity matrix (adjacency matrix) is estimated over a common set of nodes. In the field of neuroscience, these nodes may correspond to functional areas of interest within the brain's connectome, where the strength of their connections (edge weight) reflects the temporal correlation of BOLD signals. For purpose of analysis, an undirected network with p nodes can be mathematically represented by a symmetric adjacency matrix $A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$. In this matrix, the entries $a_i(r, s)$ represent the connection strength between the nodes r and s in individual i , and hence an $a_i(r, s) \neq 0$ indicates that nodes r and s are connected, and $a_i(r, s) = 0$ indicates that they are not connected. The connection strengths could be estimated by various methods, e.g. marginal correlation between time series of signals, partial correlation, mutual information, etc. For the sake of simplicity, we have chosen to use marginal correlation throughout this work, which is a common choice in network analysis. When correlation-based estimates of connectedness are based on empirical data, the case that any edge weight $a_i(r, s) = 0$ will occur, yielding a fully connected network. Without loss of generality, we consider only positive edges $a_i(r, s) \in [0, 1]$ for any i, r, s as positive and negative correlation values can have a different neurobiological interpretation and some graph-theoretical features rely on positive weights (e.g. degree).¹²⁻¹⁴ Negative edge weights can be managed by setting

them to zero, converting negative values to positive, or analyzing them separately. For edge weights stemming from alternative approaches other than correlation-based inference with values beyond this range, normalization of the distribution can transform these values to the interval $[0,1]$. Sparsifying the initial adjacency matrix means removing weak connections such that only a proportion of all pairs of nodes are connected. Graph theory then provides the basis to describe the network's properties using graph-theoretical features. For example, a network can be described by the characteristic path length (CPL) or by the clustering coefficient (CC) given by

$$CPL = \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \sum_{i \neq j} d_{ij} \quad \text{and} \quad CC = \frac{1}{|V|} \sum_{j=1}^p cc_j \quad \text{with} \quad cc_j = \frac{A_{jj}^3}{k_j(k_j-1)}$$

where d_{ij} denotes the shortest distance between node i and j (e.g. computed by Dijkstra's algorithm¹⁵), and $k_j := \sum_{i=1}^p A_{ij}$ denotes the number of nodes connected to node j (degree).¹⁶ Finally, such graph-theoretical features lend themselves as predictors in a regression model to predict a trait y (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Process of individual-specific network inference for prediction modelling

With most methods of sparsification, network inference depends on a parameter t , which is the threshold that is applied to remove apparently weak or spurious connections. Commonly, it is either a maximum value for the density (density-based thresholding) or a minimum edge weight (weight-based thresholding).¹⁷ Approaches to sparsify the individual-specific networks are not tied to the specific method used to estimate the connection strength. Neither for density-based nor for weight-based thresholding is there a commonly accepted consensus on the exact threshold that should be used to infer the individual-specific networks A_i , and various methods are used in practice to determine the threshold at which graph-theoretical characteristics become relevant for prediction. However, graph-theoretical features exhibit great variability depending on the chosen threshold (see Supplementary Figure 2 and 13 for examples).

2.2. Prediction modelling with sparse networks

Consider a cohort of N individuals, in which we aim to model a continuous health-related outcome $y = (y_1, \dots, y_N)$, such as brain maturity or a pain sensitivity score, using individual-specific networks, which may have been acquired through correlation-based inference. Let $x_i(t)$ denote a graph-theoretical feature that describes the estimated network of individual i obtained from applying threshold t to the initial adjacency matrix A_i of subject i , $i = 1, \dots, N$. As the graph-theoretical feature $x_i(t)$ depends on the selected threshold, our formulation of the linear regression model combines the classical regression notation with an additional intermediate term that models the sparsification process as a weighted sum of a sequence of the features $\{x_i(t) : t \in \mathcal{T}\}$ resulting from applying a discrete grid \mathcal{T} of L incremental thresholds, $\mathcal{T} = \{0 = t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_L = 1\}$, to the initial adjacency matrix

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \sum_{l=1}^L \omega(t_l) x_i(t_l) + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_{j+1} z_{ij} + \epsilon_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (1)$$

where β_0 denotes an intercept, while β_1 represents the regression coefficient corresponding to the weighted sum of the values $x_i(t_l)$ of a graph-theoretical feature with weights $\omega(t_l)$, $l = 1, \dots, L$, to be defined below. The variables z_{ij} , $j = 1, \dots, J$ are auxiliary fixed covariates of individual i (e.g. clinical covariates) and ϵ_i is some error term. The framework outline in Equation (1) requires defining the weight function ω , which could be preselected based on pathophysiological and/or graph-theoretical insight. However, it is frequently predetermined implicitly by solely considering the feature evaluated within a subset $\tilde{\mathcal{T}} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$, as detailed in Section 2.2.1. Alternatively, we propose its estimation through a flexible weighting function determined by statistical goodness-of-fit criteria to avoid relying on poorly informed a priori specifications of the weighting term, refer to Section 2.2.2. While the theory is denoted here for a single graph-theoretical feature $x(t)$, its application can be extended to G features such that a unique weighting function ω_g , $g = 1, \dots, G$, can be computed for each feature $x_g(t)$, $g = 1, \dots, G$. The graph-theoretical multivariable regression model is then given by

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \sum_{g=1}^G \beta_g \sum_{l=1}^L \omega_g(t_l) x_{ig}(t_l) + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_{j+G} z_{ij} + \epsilon_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

where, for the sake of notation, we assume the evaluation of all weighting functions and graph-theoretical features on a unified grid of thresholds $\mathcal{T} := \{t_1, \dots, t_L\}$. If necessary, the grid can be different for each feature, respectively. For ease of understanding of the following weighting approaches, we will introduce the methods assuming a single graph-theoretical feature. Furthermore, to ensure brevity, we will denote the threshold parameter as t without explicitly indexing it with $l = 1, \dots, L$ throughout this paper.

2.2.1. State-of-the-art approaches

Previous attempts to exploit the information in the sequence of features $x_i(t)$ available for an individual i concentrated mainly on two approaches: the optimal threshold approach (OPT) and the average feature approach (AVG), with both approaches relying on a restricted predefined subsequence $\tilde{\mathcal{T}} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$. We will explain both approaches in the notation of Equation (1).

Optimal threshold approach (OPT): the first of the frequently employed approaches in applied research presupposes the existence of an optimal universal threshold t_{opt} for the entire cohort. In the modelling framework in (1), this would result in the weight function being represented by an indicator function of the form

$$\omega(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } t = t_{opt} \\ 0, & \text{for } t \neq t_{opt} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

and model (1) is given by:

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i(t_{opt}) + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_{j+1} z_{ij} + \epsilon_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

To determine the optimal threshold t_{opt} , the sum of squares of ϵ_i (or more generally, a loss function f_{loss} applied to the predictions \hat{y} and observed outcomes y) is minimized over the sequence of models defined by $t \in \tilde{\mathcal{T}}$, such that $t_{opt} := \underset{t \in \tilde{\mathcal{T}}}{\operatorname{argmin}} f_{loss}(y, \hat{y})$. However, the optimization of f_{loss} requires the repeated refitting of (1) with $x_i(t_l)$, $l = 1, \dots, L$, to find t_{opt} . In case of a correlation-derived adjacency matrix, the search is commonly performed in $\tilde{\mathcal{T}} = \{0.1, \dots, 0.4\}$ with a step size of 0.05 or 0.1 and the (apparent) mean squared prediction error as the loss function to be minimized.¹⁷

Average feature approach (AVG): in the second modelling approach, the graph-theoretical feature is computed for every threshold within a predefined subset $\tilde{\mathcal{T}} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ and then averaged to prevent the selection of a suboptimal threshold.¹⁷ Consequently, the weight function is implicitly predetermined as a piecewise-constant function across a specified sequence $t \in \tilde{\mathcal{T}}$ such that

$$\omega(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{|\tilde{\mathcal{T}}|}, & \text{for } t \in \tilde{\mathcal{T}} \\ 0, & \text{for } t \notin \tilde{\mathcal{T}} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $|\tilde{\mathcal{T}}|$ denotes the cardinality of the set $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}$. Given (5), model (1) then has the form

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \frac{\beta_1}{|\tilde{\mathcal{T}}|} \sum_{l=1}^{|\tilde{\mathcal{T}}|} x_i(t_l) + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_{j+1} z_{ij} + \epsilon_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (6)$$

Similarly to OPT, the respective subset is $\tilde{\mathcal{T}} = \{0.1, \dots, 0.4\}$ in correlation-based network inference, with the difference that all graph-theoretical features which result from the application of the equidistant

thresholds in the subset are averaged. Hence, despite the pre-specification of the interval as in OPT, this method does not involve repeated model refitting.

2.2.2. Extension to flexibly weighting

Since the network can attain various representations based on the chosen threshold parameter, a predefined threshold interval for the weighting function might exclude the most informative parameter value(s) that explain the variability of the outcome variable.

Flexible weighting approach (FLEX): we propose the data-driven estimation of the weight function by a flexible parametrization of the form

$$\omega(t) = \sum_{m=1}^M \theta_m b_m(t) \quad (7)$$

where $b_m(\cdot)$ denotes a set of M functional basis functions of t and θ_m the corresponding weights, $m = 1, \dots, M$. The functional form of the weight function $\omega(t)$ is a-priori unknown and its shape has to be estimated. Functional basis forms can be defined by restricted cubic splines¹⁸, B-splines¹⁹ or penalized splines.²⁰ Decisions regarding the desired flexibility of the weight function (e.g., number and positions of knots) can be guided by the acceptable degree of model complexity. In the presence of prior knowledge about a plausible shape of the weight function, outer knots could be placed such that e.g. $\omega(0) = 0$, while interior knots are placed in equidistant steps.

The product of β_1 and θ_m in Equation (7) is given as:

$$\gamma_m = \beta_1 \theta_m, \quad m = 1, \dots, M \quad (8)$$

Given (7) and (8) and the basis functions $b_m(\cdot)$, the model in (1) can be reparameterized as

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{l=1}^L \gamma_m b_m(t_l) x_i(t_l) + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_{j+1} z_{ij} + \epsilon_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (9)$$

with the vector of regression coefficients $\beta = (\beta_0, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_M, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_J)$ of length $M + J + 1$ to be estimated. However, after computing the graph-theoretical feature $x_i(t_l)$ for each threshold t_l , $l = 1, \dots, L$ in (9), standard statistical software for scalar-on-function regression, like the R-package *refund*²¹ or *fda*²², can be employed to jointly estimate the flexible weight function and the regression coefficients.²³

FLEX strives to learn the most suitable functional form $\hat{\omega}(t)$ for the complete sequence of thresholds \mathcal{T} based on the available data instead of assuming a universally optimal threshold or treating a subset of thresholds as equally appropriate. Knowing where $\hat{\omega}(t)$ assumes large or small values provides information about at which thresholds t values of $x(t)$ will have the greatest leverage on the predictions \hat{y} , and may also help to support the assumptions made in the OPT or AVG approaches, or to define a

suitable subsequence $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$. Such information can also be very useful for choosing appropriate sparsification thresholds if the individual networks are not only used for prediction but their structures and topologies are also interpreted individually. The formulations above are not entirely new and similar concepts have been used for modelling time-dependent exposures²⁴ or in functional data analysis.²⁵

3. Simulation studies

3.1. Aim

We conducted a plasmode simulation study²⁶ in which we created data closely resembling the complex network structures of real fMRI data but with additional features and corresponding outcomes. The aim of the simulation study was (i) to provide evidence for a proof-of-concept of our proposed methodology, and to (ii) evaluate its predictive performance comparing it to common ad-hoc modelling approaches.

3.2. Motivating example and data-generating mechanism

We used a subset of the publicly available data in the pre-processed repository from the ABIDE initiative, which is a multi-site observational data collection of functional and structural brain imaging data on autism spectrum disorder (ASD).^{27,28} The ABIDE initiative aims to understand the extent to which ASD impacts brain functional connectivity at rest and to investigate how age interacts with the effect of ASD on resting-state functional connectivity. The functional pre-processed data of the 'ABIDE Preprocessed' initiative comprises 1112 observations from 539 individuals with Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and 573 age-matched typical controls (TC) from seventeen sites.²⁸ The full cohort was restricted according to the quality assurance and sample selection specified in Di Martino et al,²⁷ which includes, inter alia, the restriction to only male participants due to the low number of females (N=164), yielding N=704. In addition, we omitted 18 observations with missing or unmeasured time series, leaving N=686 individuals with corresponding pre-processed fMRI data. Baseline characteristics of the full cohort and the subset are shown in Supplementary Table 1. In practical applications where multiple cohorts contribute to a study, center effects may have to be considered to adjust for different fMRI pre-processing steps with approaches like ComBat^{29,30} but we don't assume them to be present here.

We computed $P \times P$ -dimensional adjacency matrices $A_i, i = 1, \dots, N$, based on Spearman correlations between the time series (P=116) for each individual. Each individual-specific network consisted of 116 nodes. Details of the fMRI data pre-processing can be found in the Supplement Section 1.1. We varied the sample size $N = \{75,150,300,600\}$ by randomly selecting subsets without replacement. For feature extraction, the two most frequently used graph-theoretical features, the clustering coefficient and the characteristic path length, were computed, which served as our true predictor $x(t)$ evaluated at weight-

based thresholds $t \in \mathcal{T}$. Supplementary Figure 2 illustrates the variations in graph-theoretical features across weight-based thresholds. We focused on these two features because of their frequency of use and their distinct patterns of curve shapes, location of peaks, and areas of increased variability across thresholds (see Supplementary Figure 2). Our outcome-generating mechanism (OGM) assumed the following form

$$E[Y|x(t)] = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x^*$$

with x^* defined as either

- *universal* threshold: $x^* = x(\tau)$ with $\tau = 0.25$
- *random* threshold: $x_i^* = x_i(\tau_i)$ with $\tau_i \in U(0.1, 0.4)$
- *functional* threshold: $x_i^* = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \omega(t) x_i(t)$ with
 - I. *flat* functional form: $\omega(t) = 4$
 - II. *early peak* functional form: $\omega(t) = 6.5 \sin(2\pi t) I(t < 0.5)$
 - III. *arc* functional form: $\omega(t) = 6 \sin(\pi t)$

and drawing outcomes $y_i = E[Y|x_i(t)] + \epsilon_i$ with Gaussian errors $\epsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ accordingly. Illustrations for the universal and random threshold selection are depicted in Supplementary Figure 3, while functional forms are shown in Supplementary Figure 4.

Residual variance:

The variance σ^2 of the residuals ϵ was specified such that in each of the OGMs, the true model (oracle) yields an R^2 of 1, 0.6, or 0.3 corresponding to no, moderate, and high residual variance, respectively, and was determined in a pilot study prior to the simulation study. The scenarios with $R^2 = 1$ may seem unrealistic but were included as a benchmark to study bias resulting from model and/or network misspecification. The values of σ^2 are shown in Supplementary Table 2.

Contamination of the edge weights:

In applied network inference, the edge weights in A_i cannot be reliably estimated. This was reflected in our simulation by introducing contamination to the originally measured edge weights $a_i(r, s), \forall(r, s)$ ³¹. More specifically, we added stochastic perturbations to the correlation-based adjacency entries for each individual to create contaminated adjacency matrices $\tilde{A}_i = g(A_i, u_i, \alpha)$ according to a modified version of the strategy proposed by Hardin et al.³¹ While full details are given in the Supplement, here we only stress that the parameter α controls the maximum allowed deviation of any edge weights between the original and contaminated adjacency matrices. Similar to the residual variance, three levels of contamination were examined: none ($\alpha = 0$), moderate ($\alpha = 0.15$) and high contamination ($\alpha = 0.3$).

For each combination of the parameter values, i.e. magnitude of residual variance, degree of contamination and sample size, the graph-theoretical features (clustering coefficient, CC; characteristic path length, CPL) and the five OGMs (*universal*, *random*, *flat*, *half-arc* and *arc*), we simulated 500 datasets (as a balanced compromise between precision and managing computational runtime, see Supplement Section 1.2.3), each comprising N individual-specific adjacency matrices \tilde{A}_i and the outcome y_i . Note that outcomes were generated before perturbing the adjacency matrices.

3.3. Estimands and targets

The estimands in our simulation were the expected values of the outcome variable $E(Y|A_i)$ and the weight functions $\omega(t)$.

3.4. Methods of data analysis

Given the (contaminated) adjacency matrices \tilde{A}_i , the discrete sequence of (contaminated) graph-theoretical features $\tilde{x}_i(t)$ was computed for $T = \{0, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 1\}$. This was done for the clustering coefficient and the characteristic path length, both under density-based and weight-based thresholding, yielding 4 sequences $\tilde{x}_i(t)$ forming the basis for the following procedures.

The OPT, AVG, and FLEX approach were implemented with varying threshold subsets considering the thresholding strategy (weight- or density-based) and the respective analysis approach (OPT, AVG, FLEX), as summarized in Table 1. The optimal threshold according to the OPT approach was identified by cross-validation with respect to the minimal cross-validated RMSPE. The weight function $\hat{\omega}(t)$ for the sequence $\tilde{x}(t)$, $t \in \tilde{T}$, in FLEX was estimated by penalized splines with a fixed number of segments of 25 and cubic degree. In addition, we implemented two benchmark methods, the NULL and the ORACLE approach. The former served as a lower benchmark and took the average of the observed y as its prediction \hat{y} , whereas the latter (upper benchmark) received the true outcome-generating weight function and was only included in case of weight-based analysis, as the true weight function was defined for weight-based thresholding only.

Table 1. Overview of methods parameters and subset specifications

Method	Thresholding	Threshold subset	Threshold(s) selection
OPT	Weight-based	$\tilde{T} = \{0, 0.01, \dots, 0.75\}$	Threshold selection by cross-validation within subset \tilde{T}
	Density-based	$\tilde{T} = \{0.25, 0.26, \dots, 1\}$	
AVG	Weight-based	$\tilde{T} = \{0.1, 0.11, \dots, 0.4\}$	Averaging over all features $\tilde{x}(t)$, $t \in \tilde{T}$
	Density-based	$\tilde{T} = \{0.6, 0.61, \dots, 0.9\}$	
FLEX	Weight-based	$\tilde{T} = \{0, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 1\}$	Penalized splines with a fixed number of segments of 25 for the weight function $\hat{\omega}(t)$, $t \in \tilde{T}$
	Density-based	$\tilde{T} = \{0, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 1\}$	

3.5. Performance measures

We evaluated the following performance measures of the prediction models:

- root mean squared prediction error (RMSPE),
- the R^2 ,
- calibration slope (CS),

These performance measures were evaluated in each simulated data set using 5-fold cross-validation (CV), and then averaged over the simulation repetitions of each scenario. The RMSPE values were also normalized by dividing by the minimum RMSPE achieved in a scenario (relative RMSPE) and shown as boxplots. We also report the 2.5% and 97.5% percentiles of the distribution of each performance measure over the simulation repetitions.

Further details of the simulation settings are presented in Supplementary Material 1. All code and implemented functions used to conduct the presented numerical experiments can be found online on GitHub: <https://github.com/mgregorich/PRONET>.

3.6. Results

3.6.1. Instability of the OPT model

In the OGM *universal*, we assumed the functional form to be an indicator function with $\omega(0.25) = 1$ and 0 otherwise to resemble a universal threshold for the entire study cohort creating a scenario favouring the OPT model, whereas approximating an indicator function using penalized splines in this setting might prove difficult. While under close to optimal conditions ($R^2 = 1$ and moderate edge weight contamination), OPT demonstrated on average the best and also most stable prediction performance, in particular when considering CPL and when performing weight-based thresholding (see Supplementary Figure 6, OGM *universal*). However, in a more realistic setting with R^2 of 0.3 and moderate edge weight contamination as stated in Table 2, the OPT approach had higher RMSPE than its competitors, in particular compared with AVG (AVG: 5.03, 95% CI 4.29- 5.72; OPT: 5.14, 4.38-5.86). In the latter setting, the AVG method performed similarly to the Oracle model, particularly when considering the clustering coefficient (AVG: 5.03, 95% CI 4.29- 5.72; Oracle: 5.03, 4.30-5.72). Despite the challenges in accurately approximating an indicator function in this particular scenario, FLEX performed slightly better than OPT (FLEX: 5.11, 95% CI 4.38-5.86). Across all OGMS, OPT often underperformed on average compared to its competitors, as shown in Supplementary Figure 6. When OPT was conducted to identify the optimal density level, a low variability of both explanatory features and the additional difficulty introduced by tuning the optimal threshold by cross-validation led to considerable uncertainty in model estimation (see Figure 2).

Table 2. Simulation study: Average performance measures across simulation replicates for the setting of sample size $n=75$, moderate residual variance, high level of contamination of the edge weights and the clustering coefficient for OGM universal and weight-based analysis

Model	Performance			
	RMSPE (95% CI)	Relative RMSPE (95% CI)	R2 (95% CI)	CS (95% CI)
Oracle	5.027 (4.302, 5.716)	1.005 (1, 1.028)	0.296 (0.167, 0.438)	1.060 (0.927, 1.226)
OPT	5.135 (4.375, 5.861)	1.027 (1, 1.08)	0.270 (0.139, 0.412)	1.050 (0.864, 1.314)
AVG	5.031 (4.291, 5.715)	1.006 (1, 1.028)	0.295 (0.167, 0.436)	1.062 (0.925, 1.24)
FLEX	5.109 (4.376, 5.863)	1.021 (1, 1.064)	0.28 (0.146, 0.421)	0.992 (0.812, 1.188)
Null	5.815 (4.989, 6.607)	1.165 (1.062, 1.313)	-	-

3.6.2. Gain in performance by flexible modelling

In Figure 2, the relative root mean squared prediction error (RMSPE) of four model-building methods (OPT, AVG, FLEX, and Oracle) was compared for all OGMs, with high contamination of the edge weights. The FLEX model outperformed other methods across all OGMs in the absence of residual variance. With decreasing R^2 , the performance of the modelling approaches showed little deviations when weight-based thresholding was applied; however, FLEX consistently maintained comparable or marginally superior predictive performance, in particular for more complex functional forms (early peak and arc form). Extreme values in relative RMSPE occurred with the OPT methodology, especially with small samples ($n=75, 150$) and density-based analysis (see Figure 2 and Supplementary Figure 7). The AVG modelling approach outperformed the OPT method and even demonstrated comparable performance to FLEX with decreasing R^2 . However, in terms of calibration, the AVG approach exhibited instability when the OGM employed functional forms largely deviating from the intrinsic weighting function of AVG (i.e. *flat* and *arc*) and the characteristic path length was evaluated (*flat*: 0.057, 95% CI -15.34-14.29); *arc*: 12.35, 95% CI -13.40-11.84; refer to Supplementary Table 3). Overall, the FLEX method appeared to be a reliable and robust method for analysing network data. The results provided in Figure 2, based on a sample size of $n = 75$, are consistent with the findings illustrated in Supplementary Figure 8, which demonstrates no variations of the main conclusions when varying sample sizes.

Figure 2. Simulation study: Relative RMSPE for various outcome-generating mechanisms for the predictive graph-theoretical features (A) clustering coefficient and (B) characteristic path length for a sample size of 75 under density-based and weight-based thresholding, respectively.

3.6.3. Impact of contamination on functional forms and threshold selection

The estimated functional form with 95% confidence intervals of FLEX across different OGMs is presented in Supplementary Figure 9, considering varying levels of edge weight contamination and a fixed sample size of 150. The estimated coefficient functions were obtained by averaging over 500 simulation replicates to derive the average functional form. To compare with the true underlying functional form of each OGM, weight-based thresholding was employed. The FLEX approach demonstrated shape preservation up to moderate levels of edge weight contamination. However, at high levels of contamination, the shape became less discernible in the majority of scenarios.

In Supplementary Figure 10, the accuracy of threshold selection for the model-building approach OPT is depicted across varying sample sizes, levels of residual variance and contamination of edge weights. The red dashed line indicates the true threshold for the OGM *universal*. Despite the clear advantage of the OPT approach in the *universal* OGM, it was apparent that the introduced nuisance factors for the outcome and the edge weights had a notable influence. This was evident when comparing the dashed line to the solid red line. While the variation within the range may not be substantial relative to the y-axis, adjustments in the threshold can have a significant effect on edge weight reduction due to the pronounced right-skewed distributions of edge weights (refer to Supplementary Figure 1). In addition, the OPT approach effectively captured the functional form in the OGM *early peak*, where the coefficient function $\omega(t)$ exhibited its highest leverage point at $t = 0.25$. In the OGM *random*, a threshold was randomly chosen from a uniform distribution $U(0.1, 0.4)$ for each individual, hence, when utilizing the OPT model, the selected threshold should also be centered around 0.25 on average. Supplementary Figure 9 demonstrated that this held true with minimal contamination in both the outcome vector and the edge weights. However, at higher contamination levels, as seen in the 'universal' outcome-generating scenario, there were more significant fluctuations.

In summary, when considering increasing residual variance and contamination of the edge weighting, the FLEX approach exhibited a decline in shape preservation of the true functional form, while OPT demonstrated a relatively robust selection of the underlying threshold despite these nuisance factors. However, in terms of predictive performance, FLEX gained an advantage from its greater adaptability due to its flexibility and, as a result, achieved improved performance compared to the ad-hoc alternatives.

4. Real data analysis: predicting brain age of children by rs-fMRI

The aim of many neuroscientific studies is to 'predict' children's brain age based on an individual's unique functional connectome, as understanding the functional architecture of the brain and its variability has been shown to be informative about the neurodevelopment in children.^{2,4,5} Disagreement between the brain age and the chronological age may indicate atypical neurodevelopment. We used publicly available data from a study conducted by Richardson et al³² to predict the brain age of children. In this study, rs-fMRI data was recorded while participants were viewing a short animated film. Details of the study design and data pre-processing can be found in the Supplementary Material (Section 1.1). The full study cohort comprised 122 children with an average age of 6.7 years (2.3) and 33 adults with an average age of 24.8 years (5.3). We restricted the study cohort to only children (age range: 3.5 – 12.3 years), see Supplementary Table 4 for an overview of the demographic characteristics of the study

participants. Additional information on data pre-processing can be found in the Supplementary Material Section 2.2. Supplementary Figure 14 demonstrates functional brain connectivity deviations that correspond to varying threshold parameters for the three study participants with the lowest, median, and highest age. We evaluated the out-of-sample performance of the competitor modelling approaches by internal 5-fold cross-validation (CV) with 10 repetitions. For the OPT approach, optimal threshold search was performed within the interval $\{0, 0.01, \dots, 0.75\}$, thus including the option for no thresholding. For the AVG approach, we averaged graph-theoretical features within the interval $\{0.1, 0.11, \dots, 0.4\}$ with equidistant thresholds with a step size of 0.01. For FLEX, we used penalized splines with 25 segments and cubic degree. The results for the graph-theoretical feature characteristic path length are not presented, as there seemed to be no association with age. Gender was included in the model building procedure for adjusted analyses; however, its inclusion did not result in any improvements.

In contrast to the coefficient function in the density-based thresholding procedure, the functional form for the weight-based thresholding procedure in Figure 3 (right) displays more variability, characterized by fluctuations and shifts in direction as the threshold increases. For the latter, the estimated curve exhibits multiple peaks with the global absolute maximum occurring at $t = 0.29$ with $\hat{\beta}_{std}(0.29) = -7.6$ (95%CI: $-14.8, -0.3$). Intervals of t where $|\beta(t)|$ is large are influential for the prediction of age in children, with the sign implying a negative association for the cc. However, interpretation is difficult given the change in direction of the association and the high correlation of 0.84 between the clustering coefficient for networks thresholded at $t = 0.06$ and $t = 0.29$. The shape of the smooth function indicates the relative leverage of thresholds in density- and weight-based thresholding and the additional importance of the clustering coefficient evaluated for thresholds around 0.29.

Figure 3. Real data analysis: Estimated flexible coefficient function $\hat{\beta}(t)$ and pointwise 95% confidence interval for the FLEX model of the association between the clustering coefficient and age. The fit is standardized by the empirical standard deviation of the graph-theoretical feature at each threshold to account for large values at the extremes due to low variability of the feature.

The selected OPT threshold with a value of $t_{opt} = 0.25$ falls within a comparable range. However, the OPT and AVG modelling approaches did not detect an association with the outcome according to the R^2 and the higher RMSPE. When density-based thresholding was conducted, we achieved comparable values of RMSPE, the R^2 and the calibration slope for AVG and FLEX as stated in Table 3. The results align with the functional form of the FLEX modelling approach, which assigned fairly homogeneous weights to the thresholds (Figure 3, left), resembling piecewise constant splines. OPT selected the density-based threshold of 0.9 as optimal but did not reach similar predictive performance as its competitors. Further, the weight-based analysis generally suffered more from overfitting (particularly AVG and OPT) compared to the density-based analysis, where the calibration slope was closer to 1. In the density-based approach, FLEX was perfectly calibrated ($CS = 1.00$), whereas AVG slightly underfitted ($CS > 1$).

Table 3. Real data analysis: Predictive performance of the three modelling approaches using weight-based and density-based thresholding. Grid search for optimal threshold selection was only conducted in the OPT approach. RMSPE, root mean squared prediction error, CS, calibration slope

Method	Thresholding	Threshold	RMSPE	R^2	CS
FLEX	weight-based	-	7.707	0.134	0.861
AVG	weight-based	-	8.118	0.019	0.744
OPT	weight-based	0.25	8.148	0.019	0.488
AVG	density-based	-	7.669	0.126	1.114
FLEX	density-based	-	7.680	0.138	1.002
OPT	density-based	0.9	7.976	0.096	0.978

The findings of the applied data example exhibit similarities with those of the simulation study, albeit within a diagnostic framework. The explained variability of the graph-theoretical features is less pronounced compared to the simulated dataset, yet it still showcases the added predictive value of individual-specific networks. In cases involving more intricate functional forms, FLEX demonstrates superior performance. Conversely, in scenarios where simpler functional patterns resembling a piecewise-constant weighting are present, FLEX still achieves comparable performance to AVG.

Prediction of brain age through brain imaging data reveals relevant insights into early brain maturation, aiding research on typical and atypical neurodevelopment in children. Our findings complement previous studies on the predictive value of large-scale functional brain networks and prompts further exploration of childhood functional brain network development.

5. Discussion

With the increasing availability of relational data, it is becoming more critical to address methodological gaps persisting in network inference. Many neuroimaging studies have demonstrated the potential of functional network connectivity patterns estimated from rs-fMRI to discriminate groups or to predict a clinical outcome.¹⁷ Two modelling approaches are mainly employed in applied studies to address the variability of graph-theoretical features resulting from the selection of thresholds across a broad spectrum of sparsity levels. The first one selects a single threshold based on optimal prediction (OPT), while the other one averages the resulting graph-theoretical feature over a predefined range of thresholds (AVG). We explored an alternative method, referred to as FLEX, which incorporates flexible weighting of the full range of possible thresholds instead of the traditional approach of selecting a single threshold or assigning equal weight to a restricted subset of thresholds.

In the plasmode simulation study, we used the pre-processed real-life fMRI data from the ABIDE initiative ensuring that the complex dependencies inherent in fMRI data were fully conserved and generated a synthetic outcome variable. In addition, the impact of noisily measured networks was assessed by contaminating the edge weights according to a realistic noise model. The FLEX model was able to recover a variety of plausible shapes of the true weight function in the absence and presence of contamination and provided great predictive accuracy and calibration of the predicted outcome, specifically when OGM consisted of complex functional forms. The various levels of contamination demonstrated the FLEX model to be the most resilient to contamination of edge weights and to achieve well-calibrated predictions, suggesting its effectiveness in real-world scenarios, followed by the AVG approach. While the plasmode simulation design was motivated by neurological data settings, the methodology is designed and presented in generality and is applicable to many other areas of scientific research.

In the real data example, we compared the three modelling approaches in their ability to predict brain age in children based on rs-fMRI data, assessing the potential utility of brain network analysis for defining brain maturation. In weight-based thresholding, however, only FLEX was able to establish an association between the clustering coefficient and the age of the children. In density-based thresholding, we could only see a minimal advantage of FLEX over AVG, probably because the additional parameters that FLEX needs to be estimated are not well supported, and equally weighting the features over the thresholds created more stability. Both approaches outperformed OPT (as in the simulation study), which needs another layer of cross-validation to determine the optimal threshold, and this generates additional estimation uncertainty. A similar effect was noted for regularized regression when the penalty strength has to be estimated from the data.³³ Therefore, when using cross-validation in small data sets to determine the optimal approach (as exemplified in the analysis of the applied data example) one should be aware of these effects and probably prefer stability over flexibility. Both in the simulation

study and in the applied example, the OPT approach proved to be unstable and satisfactory performance strongly dependent on sufficient sample size.

In practice, the proposed method can be applied in two settings. First, it can supplement a conventional primary analysis with flexible weights for the full range of possible thresholds by allowing data-driven flexible estimation of threshold leverage and perhaps more stable weighting without restricting the search within a subset of thresholds. By allowing weighting to be determined by predictive leverage, substantial gains were possible compared to the competitor methods, which require an additional layer of cross-validation (usually not performed in applied studies) in the OPT modelling approach, or the prespecification of a subset of thresholds in the AVG approach. Second, the flexible parametrization approach could be the primary analysis, specifically supported in larger sample sizes to warrant the additional complexity, and if more complex functional forms are assumed. Clearly, the FLEX model does not require predefined subsets at the planning stage but additional degrees of freedom due to the flexible parametrization. When comparing the modelling approaches, it was found that OPT exhibited instability, particularly when dealing with small data sets. If the assumption of piecewise-constant weighting is valid, the AVG approach yields robust and accurate prediction results in weight-based analysis. However, to confirm the accuracy of this assumption, additional applied studies need to be conducted to assess the adequacy of the AVG modelling approach. Structures and topologies of the network, as captured by graph-theoretical features, may differ by the threshold applied for sparsification, and hence flexible weighting seems most appropriate to consider their effects on the outcome. The FLEX model provides a useful strategy to handle multiple graph-theoretical features with corresponding weighting functions across thresholds. In addition, several extensions of our approach are possible. For example, prior knowledge about the possible shape of the functional form can be incorporated to facilitate the estimation by imposing a constraint, ensuring it aligns with a predetermined value at threshold t .

We have provided two novel contributions to the assessment of individual-specific networks for prediction modelling. First, we introduced the FLEX approach, which achieved comparable or superior performance as existing approaches, both under contamination of the graphs and regardless of the thresholding technique used. By leveraging graph-theoretical features and considering the dynamic interplay between networks and outcomes, we can gain valuable insights and improve our understanding of complex systems, thereby enhancing diagnostic capabilities in various domains. Second, this study compared several sparsification approaches in a synthetic setting under a variety of realistic data-generating settings using real-life individual-specific networks. Considering the current lack of consensus in the applied literature, our study establishes a solid foundation for the choice of the thresholding approach and serves as a stepping stone for further applied exploration of appropriate

modelling techniques in prediction modelling utilizing individual-specific networks. We found that the additional parameters that FLEX needs to estimate need to have support in the data set, and in very small studies the AVG approach might be preferable for its stability. However, both approaches are clearly superior to selecting a single optimal threshold.

Conflicts of interest

None of the authors has a conflict of interest to disclose.

Funding

Mariella Gregorich received funding for this work as part of the DOC fellowship from the Austrian Academy of Sciences.

Data sharing

The ABIDE data set^{27,28} is freely available at <http://preprocessed-connectomes-project.org/abide/> (accessed August 10, 2023). The rs-fMRI data set³² used in Section 4 is freely available at <https://openneuro.org/datasets/ds000228/versions/1.1.0> (accessed August 10, 2023).

References

1. Qin J, Chen S-G, Hu D, Zeng L-L, Fan Y-M, Chen X-P, Shen H. Predicting individual brain maturity using dynamic functional connectivity. *Front Hum Neurosci.* 2015;9:418.
2. Lund MJ, Alnæs D, de Lange A-MG, Andreassen OA, Westlye LT, Kaufmann T. Brain age prediction using fMRI network coupling in youths and associations with psychiatric symptoms. *Neuroimage Clin.* 2022;33:102921.
3. Chaddock-Heyman L, Weng TB, Kienzler C, Weisshappel R, Drollette ES, Raine LB, Westfall DR, Kao S-C, Baniqued P, Castelli DM. Brain network modularity predicts improvements in cognitive and scholastic performance in children involved in a physical activity intervention. *Front Hum Neurosci.* 2020;14:346.
4. Kardan O, Kaplan S, Wheelock MD, Feczko E, Day TK, Miranda-Domínguez Ó, Meyer D, Eggebrecht AT, Moore LA, Sung S. Resting-state functional connectivity identifies individuals and predicts age in 8-to-26-month-olds. *Dev Cogn Neurosci.* 2022;56:101123.
5. Dosenbach NU, Nardos B, Cohen AL, Fair DA, Power JD, Church JA, Nelson SM, Wig GS, Vogel AC, Lessov-Schlaggar CN. Prediction of individual brain maturity using fMRI. *Science.* 2010;329(5997):1358-1361.
6. Brugere I, Gallagher B, Berger-Wolf TY. Network structure inference, a survey: Motivations, methods, and applications. *ACM Comput Surv.* 2018;51(2):1-39.
7. Simpson SL, Bowman FD, Laurienti PJ. Analyzing complex functional brain networks: fusing statistics and network science to understand the brain. *Stat Surv.* 2013;7:1.
8. Adamovich T, Zakharov I, Tabueva A, Malykh S. The thresholding problem and variability in the EEG graph network parameters. *Sci Rep.* 2022;12(1):18659.
9. Garrison KA, Scheinost D, Finn ES, Shen X, Constable RT. The (in) stability of functional brain network measures across thresholds. *Neuroimage.* 2015;118:651-661.
10. Civier O, Smith RE, Yeh C-H, Connelly A, Calamante F. Is removal of weak connections necessary for graph-theoretical analysis of dense weighted structural connectomes from diffusion MRI? *Neuroimage.* 2019;194:68-81.
11. Heinze G, Boulesteix AL, Kammer M, Morris TP, White IR. Phases of methodological research in biostatistics—Building the evidence base for new methods. *Biom J.* 2022:2200222.

12. Tomlinson CE, Laurienti PJ, Lyday RG, Simpson SL. A regression framework for brain network distance metrics. *Netw Neurosci*. 2022;6(1):49-68.
13. Parente F, Frascarelli M, Mirigliani A, Di Fabio F, Biondi M, Colosimo A. Negative functional brain networks. *Brain Imaging Behav*. 2018/04/01 2018;12(2):467-476. doi:10.1007/s11682-017-9715-x
14. Schwarz AJ, McGonigle J. Negative edges and soft thresholding in complex network analysis of resting state functional connectivity data. *Neuroimage*. 2011/04/01/ 2011;55(3):1132-1146.
15. Dijkstra EW. A note on two problems in connexion with graphs. *Numerische Mathematik*. 1959/12/01 1959;1(1):269-271. doi:10.1007/BF01386390
16. Wasserman S, Faust K. Social network analysis: Methods and applications. 1994;
17. Gregorich M, Melograna F, Sunqvist M, Michiels S, Van Steen K, Heinze G. Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—a scoping review of methods. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2022;22(1):62.
18. Harrell FE. *Regression modeling strategies: with applications to linear models, logistic regression, and survival analysis*. vol 608. Springer; 2001.
19. De Boor C. On calculating with B-splines. *Journal of Approximation theory*. 1972;6(1):50-62.
20. Sauerbrei W, Perperoglou A, Schmid M, Abrahamowicz M, Becher H, Binder H, Dunkler D, Harrell FE, Royston P, Heinze G. State of the art in selection of variables and functional forms in multivariable analysis—outstanding issues. *Diagn Progn Res*. 2020;4(1):1-18.
21. Goldsmith J, Scheipl F, Huang L, Wrobel J, Di C, Gellar J, Harezlak J, McLean M, Swihart B, Xiao L, Crainiceanu C, Reiss P. refund: Regression with Functional Data. R package version 0.1-30: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=refund>; 2023.
22. Ramsay J, Graves S, Hooker G. fda: Functional Data Analysis. R package version 6.0.5: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=fda>; 2022.
23. R Core Team R. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Vienna, Austria: URL <https://www.R-project.org/>; 2023.
24. Sylvestre MP, Abrahamowicz M. Flexible modeling of the cumulative effects of time-dependent exposures on the hazard. *Stat Med*. 2009;28(27):3437-3453.
25. Ramsay J, Silverman B. Functional data analysis. 2nd Springer. New York. 2005;
26. Vaughan LK, Divers J, Padilla MA, Redden DT, Tiwari HK, Pomp D, Allison DB. The use of plasmodes as a supplement to simulations: a simple example evaluating individual admixture estimation methodologies. *Comput Stat Data Anal*. 2009;53(5):1755-1766.
27. Di Martino A, Yan C-G, Li Q, Denio E, Castellanos FX, Alaerts K, Anderson JS, Assaf M, Bookheimer SY, Dapretto M. The autism brain imaging data exchange: towards a large-scale evaluation of the intrinsic brain architecture in autism. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2014;19(6):659-667.
28. Craddock C, Benhajali Y, Chu C, Chouinard F, Evans A, Jakab A, Khundrakpam BS, Lewis JD, Li Q, Milham M. The neuro bureau preprocessing initiative: open sharing of preprocessed neuroimaging data and derivatives. *Front Neuroinform*. 2013;7:27.
29. Yu M, Linn KA, Cook PA, Phillips ML, McInnis M, Fava M, Trivedi MH, Weissman MM, Shinohara RT, Sheline YI. Statistical harmonization corrects site effects in functional connectivity measurements from multi-site fMRI data. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2018;39(11):4213-4227.
30. Fortin J-P, Parker D, Tunç B, Watanabe T, Elliott MA, Ruparel K, Roalf DR, Satterthwaite TD, Gur RC, Gur RE. Harmonization of multi-site diffusion tensor imaging data. *Neuroimage*. 2017;161:149-170.
31. Hardin J, Garcia SR, Golan D. A method for generating realistic correlation matrices. *Ann Appl Stat*. 2013:1733-1762.
32. Richardson H, Lisandrelli G, Riobueno-Naylor A, Saxe R. Development of the social brain from age three to twelve years. *Nat Commun*. 2018;9(1):1027.
33. Šinkovec H, Heinze G, Blagus R, Geroldinger A. To tune or not to tune, a case study of ridge logistic regression in small or sparse datasets. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2021;21:1-15.

Supplementary Material

1. Simulation design

1.1. Data

1.1.1. Study design and pre-processing

The Preprocessed Connectomes Project (PCP) provides pre-processed fMRI neuroimaging data from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE). Multiple strategies and pipelines were conducted for the functional pre-processing due to the lack of consensus on the best approach. Following Di Martino et al. ¹, we chose the Configurable Pipeline for the Analysis of Connectomes (CPAC) for basic processing with global signal correction and band-pass filtering (0.01 - 0.1 Hz) the preprocessing of the resting-state fMRI data. Time series from region of interests were extracted for the Automated Anatomical Labelling (AAL) atlas ².

The data of the ABIDE Preprocessed initiative comprises 1112 observations from 539 individuals with Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and 573 age-matched typical controls (TC) from seventeen sites ³. The full cohort was restricted according to the quality assurance and sample selection specified in Di Martino et al. ¹, which includes, inter alia, the restriction to only males participants due to the low number of females (N=164), yielding N=704. In addition, we omitted 18 observations with missing or unmeasured time series.

Supplementary Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the full cohort available from the ABIDE Preprocessed initiative and the selected subset of the ABIDE project

Variable	Full Cohort (N=1112)	Restricted Cohort (N=686)
Age, years	17.1 ± 8.0	16.1 ± 6.9
Handedness, %		
Left	99 (9.1)	64 (9.5)
Right	969 (88.8)	602 (89.3)
Left -> Right	1 (0.1)	0 (0)
Mixed	6 (0.5)	4 (0.6)
Ambidextrous	16 (1.5)	4 (0.6)
Medication intake, %	136 (16.8)	86 (16.6)
Diagnostic group, %	539 (48.5)	328 (47.8)
DSM-IV-TR Diagnostic Category, %		
Autism	347 (33.4)	215 (34.1)
Asperger's	93 (8.9)	55 (8.7)
PDD-NOS	36 (3.5)	19 (3.0)
Asperger's or PDD-NOS	6 (0.6)	0 (0)
Control	558 (53.7)	342 (54.2)
Full-scale IQ	108.4 ± 15.1	108.5 ± 13.5
Verbal IQ	107.8 ± 16.2	108.4 ± 14.8
Performance IQ	106.6 ± 15.3	106.7 ± 14.0

Abbreviations: DSM-IV-TR, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders; PDD-NOS, Pervasive developmental disorder not otherwise specified; IQ, intelligence quotient

1.1.2. Graph-theoretical initial data analysis

The distribution of edge weights in fMRI connectivity networks is usually centered around zero. Hence, if only positive edge weights are considered and negative edge weights set to zero, the distribution of edge weights tends to follow a log-normal distribution, with a few strong connections and many weak connections. However, there is also variability in the edge weight distribution across individuals. Some individuals may have more connections with high edge weights, while others may have more connections with low edge weights. This variability may be related to individual differences in brain function or structure, as well as differences in the task or condition being studied; hence we can see variations in the individual edge weight distributions of a randomly selected subset (N=300) of the ABIDE cohort in Supplementary Figure 1.

Supplementary Figure 1. Individual-specific variability across edge weight distributions for a random selected subset of 300 individuals in the ABIDE cohort. Individual edge weight distributions are coloured in blue variations.

Supplementary Figure 2. Distribution of the graph theoretical features, clustering coefficient (A) and characteristic path length (B), across varying threshold for weight-based sparsification thresholds for each individual depicted in blue variations.

1.2. Data-generating mechanism

Since we assume that the outcome is generated by a linear regression model

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \sum_{t \in T} \omega(t) x_i(t),$$

We assessed varying forms of the outcome-generating function $\omega(t)$:

- (i) a universal threshold for all individuals $i = 1, \dots, N$ as illustrated in Suppl. Figure 3 (left),
 - (ii) randomly selected thresholds for each individual in Suppl. Figure 3 (right)
- and three truly functional forms:
- (iii) a flat form as in Suppl. Figure 4 (left),
 - (iv) an early peak form (Suppl- Figure 4, middle) and
 - (v) an arc form (Suppl. Figure 4, right).

Supplementary Figure 3. True coefficient of the universal threshold approach and the individual-specific threshold randomly selected from a uniform distribution $U(0.1,0.4)$.

Supplementary Figure 4. The true functional forms $\beta(t)$ of the OGMs flat, early peak, and arc.

1.2.1. Specification of residual variance

The residual variance σ^2 in each of the functional form settings (universal, random, flat, half-arc, and arc) was chosen to match the desired levels of R^2 (1, 0.6, or 0.3) in the different OGMs. These levels represent no, moderate, and high residual variance, respectively. The specific values for σ^2 were determined through a preliminary pilot study conducted before the simulation study.

Supplementary Table 2. Residual variance for the five functional forms.

Functional form	Residual variance		
	None ($R^2=1$)	Moderate ($R^2=0.6$)	High ($R^2=0.3$)
universal	0	2.50	5.00
random	0	3.00	6.00
flat	0	2.50	5.00
early peak	0	2.50	5.00
arc	0	2.50	5.00

1.2.2. Contamination of the edge weights

Hardin et al. ⁴ proposed an algorithm to incorporate noise into a given correlation matrix in a realistic manner such that it remains positive-definite and the condition number is bounded from above. The algorithm by Hardin et al. ⁴ takes a prespecified $p \times p$ dimensional correlation matrix Σ , a maximum contamination strength s and a positive integer m , and then samples p vectors $\mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$, such that we obtain the $m \times p$ matrix \mathbf{U} of the normalized vectors given by

$$\mathbf{U} = \left(\frac{\mathbf{u}_1}{\sqrt{\mathbf{u}'_1 \mathbf{u}_1}}, \dots, \frac{\mathbf{u}_p}{\sqrt{\mathbf{u}'_p \mathbf{u}_p}} \right) \quad (1)$$

The contaminated correlation matrix \mathbf{S} is then given by

$$\mathbf{S} = \Sigma + \alpha \delta_i (\mathbf{U}' \mathbf{U} - \mathbf{I}_p) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{I}_p is the $p \times p$ dimensional identity matrix and the parameter $\delta_i = 1$ in the original algorithm by Hardin. The transformation only affects the off-diagonal elements of Σ and ensures that $|S_{ij} - \Sigma_{ij}| \leq \alpha$. The n -dimensional vector $\delta \sim U(0,1)$ controls the impact of contamination across the individual-specific networks. The parameter α is specified to reflect a realistic amount of noise in the edge weights. Specifically, for moderate contamination, α is set to 0.15, while in highly contamination scenarios α is increased to 0.3. An example of the impact of the contamination is illustrated in Supp. Figure 5.

Supplementary Figure 5. Example of high contamination ($\alpha = 0.3$) for two randomly selected individuals from the ABIDE study cohort.

1.2.3. Monte Carlo error for RMSPE

Because of the substantial computational time required for performing extensive matrix computations, which include repeated thresholding and the calculation of graph-theoretical features on large datasets, the simulation replicates were constrained to $n_{sim} = 500$. Nevertheless, the choice of employing 500 replicates was thoroughly evaluated across all 360 data-generating mechanisms and model construction methods as outlined in ⁵. This assessment involved computing the Monte Carlo error for the RMSPE and resulted in a maximum error of 0.08.

1.2.4. Additional results

Supplementary Figure 6. Relative RMSPE of the competitor models and the oracle model for the OGMs universal, flat, early peak and arc for a fixed sample size of $n=75$ for no residual variance ($R^2=1$) and high residual variance ($R^2=0.3$) and the inclusion of the explanatory variable clustering coefficient (A) and characteristic path length (B) under weight-based thresholding.

Supplementary Figure 7. Relative RMSPE of the competitor models and the oracle model for the OGMs universal, flat, early peak and arc for a fixed sample size of $n=75$ for no residual variance ($R^2=1$) and high residual variance ($R^2=0.3$) and the inclusion of the explanatory variable (A) clustering coefficient and (B) characteristic path length under density-based thresholding.

Supplementary Table 3. Calibration slope of the competitor models and the oracle model for the OGMs universal, flat, early peak and arc for a fixed sample size of $n = 75$ for no residual variance ($R^2=1$) and high residual variance ($R^2=0.3$) and the inclusion of the explanatory variable (A) clustering coefficient and (B) characteristic path length under density-based thresholding.

			Outcome-generating mechanism			
Feature	Model	Residual variance	universal	flat	early peak	arc
CC	Oracle	none	1.003 (0.995, 1.014)	1.003 (0.993, 1.015)	1.003 (0.994, 1.015)	1.004 (0.992, 1.018)
CC	OPT	none	1.002 (0.99, 1.014)	1.002 (0.981, 1.028)	1.002 (0.989, 1.016)	1.002 (0.982, 1.024)
CC	AVG	none	1.005 (0.995, 1.018)	0.998 (0.982, 1.014)	1.003 (0.994, 1.013)	0.996 (0.973, 1.017)
CC	FLEX	none	1.000 (0.988, 1.013)	1.002 (0.99, 1.016)	0.999 (0.986, 1.013)	1.001 (0.984, 1.018)
CC	Oracle	high	1.060 (0.927, 1.226)	1.051 (0.909, 1.216)	1.094 (0.935, 1.317)	1.043 (0.916, 1.203)
CC	OPT	high	1.050 (0.864, 1.314)	1.041 (0.844, 1.292)	1.086 (0.829, 1.421)	1.038 (0.855, 1.245)
CC	AVG	high	1.062 (0.925, 1.24)	1.046 (0.918, 1.195)	1.094 (0.932, 1.312)	1.034 (0.923, 1.188)
CC	FLEX	high	0.992 (0.812, 1.188)	0.984 (0.788, 1.161)	0.978 (0.733, 1.227)	0.991 (0.814, 1.160)
CPL	Oracle	none	1.001 (0.997, 1.006)	1.007 (0.934, 1.088)	1.002 (0.996, 1.009)	1.004 (0.935, 1.081)
CPL	OPT	none	1.001 (0.994, 1.007)	0.966 (-1.934, 2.529)	1.001 (0.984, 1.026)	0.704 (-2.257, 4.23)
CPL	AVG	none	1.006 (0.996, 1.020)	2.335 (-9.694, 8.146)	1.002 (0.995, 1.009)	0.215 (-13.83, 13.913)
CPL	FLEX	none	0.998 (0.979, 1.014)	0.978 (0.886, 1.064)	1.000 (0.991, 1.010)	0.992 (0.909, 1.076)
CPL	Oracle	high	1.051 (0.937, 1.216)	1.270 (0.878, 1.606)	1.07 (0.938, 1.268)	1.096 (0.903, 1.339)
CPL	OPT	high	1.042 (0.852, 1.313)	-2.003 (-5.836, 4.174)	1.056 (0.857, 1.346)	6.716 (-4.449, 6.164)
CPL	AVG	high	1.058 (0.932, 1.251)	0.057 (-15.343, 14.29)	1.069 (0.941, 1.256)	12.350 (-13.397, 11.836)
CPL	FLEX	high	0.973 (0.791, 1.131)	0.954 (0.624, 1.287)	0.979 (0.788, 1.157)	0.960 (0.658, 1.194)

Supplementary Figure 8. Results across OGMs and varying levels of outcome contamination (none, moderate, high). Clustering coefficient used as graph-theoretical feature and no contamination for the graphs were specified.

Supplementary Figure 9. Average functional form $\hat{\beta}(t)$ obtained by the estimated flexible parametrization using penalized splines with 25 segments for the variable clustering coefficient (top) and the characteristic path length (bottom) for varying levels of edge weight contamination across all OGMs. The sample size was fixed at $n = 75$. Weighted-based thresholding was performed.

Supplementary Figure 10. Threshold selection of the OPT model for all OGMs averaged across simulation runs when performing weight-based analysis. The dashed line indicates the true underlying threshold implemented for the OGM ‘universal’.

2. Real data example

2.1. Study design and pre-processing

The data was obtained from OpenNeuro (as ds000228) available as derivative data that was pre-processed using fMRIPrep. In this experiment conducted by ⁶, the participants were asked to lie still in the scanner and watch the movie "Partly Cloudy" by Disney Pixar. They were not given any specific task during this time. To begin the experiment, there was a 10-second period of rest with a black screen. Following the rest period, the movie started, and the first 10 seconds consisted of the opening credits, including the Disney castle and Pixar logo. The total length of the experiment was 5.6 minutes. For the atlas choice functional (BASC multiscale) was used. Among the findings of the study, the authors state that functional maturity of each network was related to increasingly anti-correlated responses between the networks. The characteristics of the study cohort are presented in Supplementary Table 4.

Supplementary Table 4. Demographic characteristics of the study participants

Variable	Full cohort (N=155)	Restricted cohort (N=122)
Age, in years	7.7 [5.3, 11.0]	6.0 [4.9, 8.4]
Sex, female (%)	84 (54.2)	64 (52.5)
Age ≥ 18 years (%)	33 (21.3)	-
Handedness (%)		
Left-handed	10 (6.5)	9 (7.4)
Right-handed	142 (91.6)	110 (90.2)
Ambidextrous	3 (1.9)	3 (2.5)

Out of the 155 study participants, not all were children but 33 were already over the age of 18. The oldest study participant was 39 years old, while the youngest was 3.5 years.

2.2. Graph-theoretical initial data analysis

For the analysis of individual-specific networks, we used the absolute correlation coefficients to focus on the strength of relationships between variables, disregarding the direction of the correlations. The change in the initial adjacency by disregarding the direction of the correlation is illustrated in Suppl. Figure 11.

Supplementary Figure 11. (A) The initial correlation-based adjacency matrix of a randomly chosen individual featuring a network density of 100%, and (B) the corresponding matrix after the transformation to absolute values, with a density of less than 100%.

The density distribution of the absolute edge weights of each individual-specific network depicted in Suppl. Figure 12 shows the characteristic shape of individual-specific networks inferred by correlation-based network construction with a high number of low edge weights and few strong connections.

Supplementary Figure 12. Edge weight distribution of the individual-specific networks

In Suppl. Figure 13, the individual-specific curves of the graph-theoretical features for increasing threshold levels are depicted and show that these mainly differ by amplitude due to heterogeneity of edge weights across individual-specific networks.

Supplementary Figure 13. Distribution of the graph-theoretical feature clustering coefficient across the range of thresholds for the individual-specific networks.

Supplementary Figure 14. Illustrative adjacency matrices showcasing three individuals from the cohort, representing the minimum, median, and maximum age, using thresholds of 0, 0.06, and 0.29. The presented thresholds align with the peaks in the functional form obtained in the weight-based analysis in Figure 3.

References

1. Di Martino A, Yan C-G, Li Q, Denio E, Castellanos FX, Alaerts K, Anderson JS, Assaf M, Bookheimer SY, Dapretto M. The autism brain imaging data exchange: towards a large-scale evaluation of the intrinsic brain architecture in autism. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2014;19(6):659-667.
2. Tzourio-Mazoyer N, Landeau B, Papathanassiou D, Crivello F, Etard O, Delcroix N, Mazoyer B, Joliot M. Automated anatomical labeling of activations in SPM using a macroscopic anatomical parcellation of the MNI MRI single-subject brain. *Neuroimage*. 2002;15(1):273-289.
3. Craddock C, Benhajali Y, Chu C, Chouinard F, Evans A, Jakab A, Khundrakpam BS, Lewis JD, Li Q, Milham M. The neuro bureau preprocessing initiative: open sharing of preprocessed neuroimaging data and derivatives. *Front Neuroinform*. 2013;7:27.
4. Hardin J, Garcia SR, Golan D. A method for generating realistic correlation matrices. *Ann Appl Stat*. 2013;1733-1762.
5. Morris TP, White IR, Crowther MJ. Using simulation studies to evaluate statistical methods. *Stat Med*. 2019;38(11):2074-2102.
6. Richardson H, Lisandrelli G, Riobueno-Naylor A, Saxe R. Development of the social brain from age three to twelve years. *Nat Commun*. 2018;9(1):1027.

3.4 Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach

Authors: Mariella Gregorich¹, Michael Kammer^{1,2}, Harald Mischak^{3,4} and Georg Heinze¹

Affiliations: ¹ Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Data Science, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria; ² Division of Nephrology and Dialysis, Department of Internal Medicine III, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria; ³ School of Cardiovascular and Metabolic Health, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, UK; ⁴ Mosaiques Diagnostics GmbH, Hannover, Germany

Publication status: The manuscript is submitted to a peer-reviewed journal and available as a preprint version on arXiv.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.02064>

Interlude: In the last paper of this doctoral thesis, we shifted our attention toward the intricate task of variable selection from a set of correlated predictors. Building upon the concerns raised in the discussion of Paper II, where we highlighted the high correlation among graph-theoretical features, we acknowledged that variable selection can be a challenging endeavor and assessed approaches for variable selection using correlated predictors. Given the limited availability and public access of large sample sizes in the most common research domain of Paper III, namely neurological studies, we utilized mass-spectrometry data, which presented an additional challenge due to the zero-inflated nature of the variables, characterized by an excess of zeros among the candidate predictors. In Paper IV, we expanded the existing body of knowledge by conducting both, a comparative simulation study and a case study, of one-stage and two-stage regularization-based variable selection and shrinkage techniques, with a special focus on a nonnegative garrote with ridge estimates as initial estimates in the first stage. Additionally, we implemented a split of each zero-inflated predictor into a binary and a continuous component variable to more accurately capture the dual nature of the distribution. Therefore, this paper serves as an illustrative case for dealing with data with complex correlation structures, acknowledging that correlation alone is rarely the only complex facet of data analysis.

Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach

Mariella Gregorich¹, Michael Kammer^{1,2}, Harald Mischak^{3,4} and Georg Heinze^{1,*}

¹Medical University of Vienna, Center for Medical Data Science, Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Vienna, Austria

²Medical University of Vienna, Department of Medicine III, Division of Nephrology, Vienna, Austria

³University of Glasgow, School of Cardiovascular and Metabolic Health, Glasgow, UK

⁴Mosaiques Diagnostics GmbH, Hannover, Germany

*Corresponding author

Abstract

Building prediction models from mass-spectrometry data is challenging due to the abundance of correlated features with varying degrees of zero-inflation, leading to a common interest in reducing the features to a concise predictor set with good predictive performance given the experiments' resource-intensive nature. In this study, we formally established and examined regularized regression approaches, designed to address zero-inflated and correlated predictors. In particular, we describe a novel two-stage regularized regression approach (ridge-garrote) explicitly modelling zero-inflated predictors using two component variables, comprising a ridge estimator in the first stage and subsequently applying a nonnegative garrote estimator in the second stage. We contrasted ridge-garrote with one-stage methods (ridge, lasso) and other two-stage regularized regression approaches (lasso-ridge, ridge-lasso) for zero-inflated predictors. We assessed the predictive performance and predictor selection properties of these methods in a comparative simulation study and a real-data case study with the aim to predict kidney function using peptidomic features derived from mass-spectrometry. In the simulation study, the predictive performance of all assessed approaches was comparable, yet the ridge-garrote approach consistently selected more parsimonious models compared to its competitors in most scenarios. While lasso-ridge achieved higher predictive accuracy than its competitors, it exhibited high variability in the number of selected predictors. Ridge-lasso exhibited slightly superior predictive accuracy than ridge-garrote but at the expense of selecting more noise predictors. Overall, ridge emerged as a favourable option when variable selection is not a primary concern, while ridge-garrote demonstrated notable practical utility in selecting a parsimonious set of predictors, with only minimal compromise in predictive accuracy.

Keywords: zero-inflation; regularized regression; mass-spectrometry; nonnegative garrote

1. Introduction

Prediction modelling involves the identification of predictors that can accurately prognosticate future health outcomes or assist in diagnosing a patient's condition. To that end, modern technologies facilitate the generation of a large number of such predictive factors, for example peptide intensities measured via mass-spectrometry. However, usually a considerable proportion of the collected variables may not be needed for accurate prediction of the particular outcome of interest. Not only the large number of peptides poses a challenge, but in addition the measured intensities from mass-spectrometers are often subject to zero-inflation, i.e., their distribution exhibits a spike at zero, resulting in peptide distributions that need special consideration when used as predictors in a (generalized) linear model. The zero intensities have been termed point mass values (PMVs), while the continuous, nonnegative intensities that are not zero have been referred to as non-PMVs [1]. The reasons for measuring zero values are twofold: (1) structural zeros due to biological absence of a peptide in a sample or (2) sampling zeros due to under-sampling of low-abundance peptides (e.g. when the true intensity is lower than a technical limit of detection, LOD), technical issues (e.g. loss during preparation due to absorbance or signal suppression) or error in the interpretation of raw mass spectral data. Unfortunately, it is impossible to distinguish between these cases objectively in practical settings as the exact biological mechanisms behind the production of peptides are usually the target of investigation and thus often unknown. Ad-hoc techniques dealing with the excess of zeros generally either assume all PMVs to be structural zeros, or treat all PMVs as sampling zeros and substitute them with LOD / c , $LOD/\sqrt{2}$ or $LOD - c$, where c is an arbitrary constant value [2-4]. Nonetheless, both methods fail to address the dual nature of the intensity distribution, leading to potentially biased parameter estimates and inadequate model fit.

Previous research has addressed the challenges associated with the analysis of high-dimensional, zero-inflated and correlated predictors by employing regularized regression models combined with different data pre-processing strategies to handle the excess zeros in the data. For instance, Gajjala et al. [5] used the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (lasso) to identify proteomic markers of chronic kidney disease (CKD) progression from high-dimensional plasma peptides. The peptide intensity values were subjected to pre-processing, involving a \log_2 -transformation and accounting for PMVs by subtracting a constant value from the minimum measured values of individual peptides. Further, Pena et al. [6] implemented a two-stage modelling approach to identify plasma proteomics markers. Initially, lasso was used to select differentially expressed peptides between subjects with CKD and those without. Following this, ridge regression was conducted, using two variables for each selected peptide: a binary variable that distinguished between PMVs and non-PMVs, and a continuous variable, representing the logarithm of the non-PMVs. A comparable procedure to derive a proteomic score able to differentiate between patients and controls was carried out in the study of Gajjala et al. [7]. In many cases, algorithmic classifiers such as support vector machines [8, 9] or random forest [10] were employed for diagnostic purposes to sidestep the need for data pre-processing considerations. Nonetheless, the optimal strategy

for handling and analysing zero-inflated and correlated predictors is uncertain, particularly in high-dimensional settings.

As mass-spectrometry experiments are costly and time-consuming, it is crucial to identify a technique that offers good predictive performance while identifying a parsimonious set of peptides relevant for prediction. Here, we aimed to explicitly define the methodological background of regularized regression techniques tailored for variable selection or shrinkage in the presence of zero-inflation and a complex correlation structure. Additionally, we examined their capabilities in predictive performance and assessed their predictor selection properties. We considered two-stage regularized regression approaches combining L_1 - and L_2 penalties with the objective to obtain a parsimonious set of predictive peptides. A particular emphasis is put on the evaluation of the nonnegative garrote with ridge estimates in the first stage instead of the standard ordinary least squares estimates (ridge-garrote) [11]. In a case study, we demonstrate the performance of the approaches to predict estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) using mass-spectrometry data.

The following section outlines the methodological background of the regularized regression techniques tailored to address the challenges of predictors with zero-inflation. Following that, an extensive simulation study evaluates their predictive performance and their ability to produce a parsimonious set of predictors in Section 3. Additionally, a case study demonstrates their use in predicting kidney function from proteomic mass-spectrometry data in Section 4. In the last section, we discuss the study's findings, limitations, and draw conclusions.

2. Methods

2.1. Strategies for handling zero-inflated predictors

Zero-inflated predictors need special treatment in statistical models if one has reason to assume that the expected value of the outcome at a zero value of a predictor cannot be extrapolated from the association of non-zero values of the predictor with the outcome [12]. While we focus on the strategy that represents each predictor by two component variables [6, 13, 14], a naïve approach based on imputation of the PMVs is also briefly outlined. We assume a study cohort of n subjects. Let $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T$ be the vector of observed outcomes and \mathbf{Z} the $n \times q$ matrix of predictors with observed continuous and nonnegative intensity values $z_{ij}, i = 1, \dots, n; j = 1, \dots, q$. Let \mathbf{z}_j be the j th, potentially zero-inflated predictor in \mathbf{Z} .

Strategy A - ‘component variables’: The predictor \mathbf{z}_j may be represented by two component variables:

- I. a binary component: $\mathbf{d}_j := I(\mathbf{z}_j > 0)$, where $I(\cdot)$ denotes the indicator function for the presence or absence of an intensity value higher than 0, and

- II. a continuous component: $\mathbf{u}_j := f(\mathbf{z}_j)$, where $f(\cdot)$ represents a monotone function that aims to symmetrize the distribution of the intensities (such as the logarithm, or the square root, but may also be the identity function). If $f(0)$ is undefined, PMVs are substituted with a common representative value that can be chosen arbitrarily.

The binary component matrix \mathbf{D} addresses the PMVs in the data, thereby allowing to model the zeros and non-zero values separately and accounting for potentially different processes that generated these intensities. The continuous component matrix \mathbf{U} comprises the non-PMVs. When employing a modelling approach that can only select \mathbf{u}_j , the choice of the representative value of the PMVs is crucial to prevent information loss caused by the integration of PMVs into the distribution of the non-PMVs, thereby complicating the interpretation of the corresponding coefficient in the model. Strategy A is useful to handle PMVs if they are a mixture of structural and sampling zeros.

Strategy B - ‘imputation of PMVs’: we may define the matrix \mathbf{X} , which consists of the normalized values of \mathbf{Z} after replacing PMVs with a fixed, biologically meaningful value larger than 0 (e.g. $LOD/2$, LOD or $LOD/\sqrt{2}$). This imputation assumes that all PMVs are sampling zeros. If PMVs are a mixture of structural and sampling zeros, a model that considers only \mathbf{X} for the peptide data imposes the strong assumption that structural zeros of the peptides behave exactly like sampling zeros.

The matrix \mathbf{X} is obtained by a similar normalization transformation as \mathbf{U} and differs from \mathbf{U} merely in the value chosen to impute PMVs. While for \mathbf{U} , imputations for PMVs (e.g. the mean of the normalized non-PMVs) should support interpretability of the regression coefficients of the binary components \mathbf{d}_j , for \mathbf{X} PMVs are replaced by biologically meaningful values. However, the strategies are not mutually exclusive; one may consider to use matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{D} to represent the candidate variables which would allow to obtain interpretable models even if \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{D} components are independently selected. We refer to the data example in Section 4 for further details on the data transformation in an applied setting. In the following sections, we assume the transformations have been applied to the observed values of the intensity distribution \mathbf{Z} , following Strategy A to produce component matrices \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} with all binary and continuous variables, and following Strategy B to generate the transformed matrix \mathbf{X} .

2.2. One-stage regression models

As commonly used in practice, we investigated lasso regression [15] which provides selection and shrinkage of the regression coefficients for the candidate predictors based on L_1 -regularization. In the case of linear regression, it minimizes the criterion

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\mathbf{X}}^{lasso}(\lambda) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\mathbf{X}}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\mathbf{X}}\|_2^2 + \lambda\|\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\mathbf{X}}\|_1, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\mathbf{X}}$ are the unknown regression parameters corresponding to \mathbf{X} , and λ is a parameter to control the amount of regularization.

As another common choice in practice, we included a method based on ridge regression, in which the regression parameters are estimated by

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^{ridge}(\lambda) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\beta}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{y} - (\mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\beta}_U + \mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\beta}_D)\|_2^2 + \lambda(\|\boldsymbol{\beta}_U\|_2^2 + \|\boldsymbol{\beta}_D\|_2^2), \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} := (\boldsymbol{\beta}_U^T, \boldsymbol{\beta}_D^T)^T$ in which $\boldsymbol{\beta}_U$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_D$ are the regression parameter vectors for \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} , respectively. Whilst lasso is capable of performing predictor selection, unlike ridge regression, it has been noted that ridge regression is better suited to handle correlated predictors [16].

2.3. Two-stage regression approaches

In the lasso-ridge approach, the first stage applies the lasso on the candidate variables represented by \mathbf{X} . At the second stage, the selected predictors $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} \subseteq \mathbf{X}$, are subjected to a ridge regression model but are represented in this model by their corresponding components $\tilde{\mathbf{U}} \subseteq \mathbf{U}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{D}} \subseteq \mathbf{D}$:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^{lasso-ridge}(\lambda) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\beta}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{y} - (\tilde{\mathbf{U}}\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{U}} + \tilde{\mathbf{D}}\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{D}})\|_2^2 + \lambda(\|\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{U}}\|_2^2 + \|\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{D}}\|_2^2), \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} := (\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{U}}^T, \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{D}}^T)^T$, with the $\tilde{q} \leq q$ -dimensional vectors of the selected component variables $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{U}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\tilde{D}}$.

In the ridge-lasso approach, the first stage fits a ridge regression as in Equation (2). Then, a weight term for each predictor is defined as the reciprocal of the sum of the absolute values of the corresponding estimated coefficients of the component variables from the first-stage ridge model:

$$\mathbf{w}_j = \frac{1}{(|\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{U_j}| + |\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{D_j}|)} \quad , j = 1, \dots, q \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{U_j}$ denotes the regression coefficient corresponding to the j th component variable in \mathbf{U} , and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{D_j}$ represents the regression coefficient for the j th component variable in \mathbf{D} . At the second stage, a lasso fit is obtained utilizing these weights as peptide-specific penalization factors by minimizing

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^{ridge-lasso}(\lambda) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\beta}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{y} - (\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}_X + \mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\beta}_D)\|_2^2 + \lambda(\|\mathbf{w}\boldsymbol{\beta}_X\|_1 + \|\mathbf{w}\boldsymbol{\beta}_D\|_1). \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} := (\boldsymbol{\beta}_X^T, \boldsymbol{\beta}_D^T)^T$. For the ridge-lasso approach, we substitute the component variable \mathbf{U} by \mathbf{X} at the second stage because the two components are independently selected in (7). If for a peptide the binary component \mathbf{D} is not selected the regression coefficient of the remaining \mathbf{X} component can still be interpreted.

In the ridge-garrote approach, the first stage fits a ridge regression model with \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} to obtain $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_U^{ridge}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_D^{ridge}$ [11, 17]. At the second stage, shrinkage factors for all q predictors are estimated by solving

$$\hat{c}(\lambda) = \underset{c}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{y} - (\mathbf{U}\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\mathbf{U}} + \mathbf{D}\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\mathbf{D}})\mathbf{c}\|_2^2 + \lambda\|\mathbf{c}\|_1, \text{ subject to } c_j \geq 0 \text{ and } \lambda \geq 0, \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\mathbf{U}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\mathbf{D}}$ are diagonal matrices of the initial regression coefficients $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\mathbf{U}}^{\text{ridge}}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\mathbf{D}}^{\text{ridge}}$ for \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} , respectively. The ridge-garrote estimates for both components of each predictor can then be computed by

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\mathbf{U}}^{\text{ridge-garrote}}(\lambda) = \hat{c}(\lambda)\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\mathbf{U}}^{\text{ridge}} \text{ and } \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\mathbf{D}}^{\text{ridge-garrote}}(\lambda) = \hat{c}(\lambda)\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\mathbf{D}}^{\text{ridge}}. \quad (9)$$

For a given predictor, the second step assigns a common shrinkage factor to both components. If this shrinkage factor is estimated as 0, the predictor is deselected from the model.

3. Simulation study

We used the structured approach of ADEMP (aim, data, estimands, methods, performance) to report the simulation study [18].

3.1. Aims

Our study aimed to evaluate the predictive performance and variable selection properties of five regularized regression methods (ridge, lasso, ridge-lasso, lasso-ridge and ridge-garrote) to predict a continuous outcome variable in situations with zero-inflated predictors and complex correlation structure between predictors.

3.2. Data-generating mechanism

Motivated by real-life data from mass-spectrometry studies, we simulated data from a multivariate binomial and lognormal mixture distribution. First, a matrix of latent continuous covariates $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times q}$ with $q = 200$ was sampled from a multivariate log-normal distribution with a prespecified correlation structure (see Supplementary Figure 1), and with a geometric mean of $\exp(10)$ and log standard deviation of 1 for each variable. Omics-derived variables often exhibit clusters of correlated predictors that exhibit stronger dependencies within each cluster than between the clusters. To account for such a group structure, we specified a block-diagonal correlation matrix with a hub correlation structure for 4 groups among the 200 predictors with a group size of 50 predictors, respectively [19]. In each group, the first variable was designated as the hub, while variables 2 through 50 within each group had a progressively declining correlation with the hub variable (see Supplementary Figure 1). We also assumed the presence of one group of with little to no correlation (4th group). We defined three settings with the percentage of total zeros (structural and sampling zeros) per predictor within each group ranging from 0 to 25%, 0 to 50% and 0 to 75%, as motivated by the case study (see Supplementary Figure 2). In each scenario, either $1/3$ or $2/3$ of all zeros were structural zeros (see Supplementary Figure 3 and Supplementary Table 1). Structural zero-inflation was accounted for by a $n \times q$ -dimensional binary

matrix \mathbf{D} with elements $d_{ij} \sim \text{Bin}(1, p_j^{\text{struc}})$, where the parameter p_j^{struc} denotes the proportion of structural zeros in latent variable j . The structural zeros were then introduced into the nonnegative, right-skewed intensity values by $\mathbf{Z}^{\mathbf{D}} = \mathbf{Z} \oplus \mathbf{D}$, where \oplus represents the element-wise product of matrices [20].

For the outcome-generating model, we substituted PMVs of $\mathbf{Z}^{\mathbf{D}}$ with the theoretical geometric mean of the log-normal distribution, $\mu = \exp(10)$, and then log-transformed $\mathbf{Z}^{\mathbf{D}}$, yielding \mathbf{U} . We assumed that the outcome \mathbf{y} for n subjects is generated from the following linear model

$$\mathbf{y} = \boldsymbol{\beta}_0 + a\mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\beta}_U + (1 - a)\mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\beta}_D + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0$ denotes an intercept, $\boldsymbol{\beta}_U$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_D$ are two q -dimensional vectors of regression coefficients, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ represents an error term. The parameter a controlled the contributions of the continuous and binary components to the variability of the outcome vector \mathbf{y} . We defined three scenarios based on the value of a : (i) the variances of both terms, $a\mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\beta}_U$ and $(1 - a)\mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\beta}_D$, were equal ('U=D'), (ii) the variance of $a\mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\beta}_U$ was twice the variance of $(1 - a)\mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\beta}_D$ ('U=2D'), or (iii) $a = 1$ ('U') such that only the continuous part was relevant for the outcome generation. In a pilot study, the variance σ^2 of the error term was determined to approximately achieve a target R^2 of 0.3 or 0.6 in a simulated dataset of size $n = 100,000$ for each scenario. Additionally, we considered $\sigma^2 = 0$ to simulate a scenario with $R^2 = 1$ in order to focus on the bias from model misspecification.

Within this general framework, we considered several outcome-generating models (OGM) defining the association between the simulated peptides and the outcome (see also Supplementary Figure 4):

- OGM (A) The predictors in groups 1 and 3 were all associated with outcome with varying regression coefficients in $[0.1, 1]$ within each group, including both the continuous and binary components.
- OGM (B) In each group, only five predictors were associated with the outcome with varying regression coefficients in $[1, 2]$, independently for the continuous and the binary components.
- OGM (C) All predictors in groups 1 and 3 were weakly associated with the outcome with varying coefficients in $[0.1, 0.4]$. The continuous and binary components had identical regression coefficients.

While the outcome values were generated using model (10) according to the three OGMs, we assumed that a data analyst might also need to deal with sampling zeros in the intensity values. These were generated by setting values which were below the theoretical p_j^{sam} -quantile of \mathbf{Z}_j to zero. In each scenario, $2/3$ or $1/3$ of all zeros were sampling zeros. Overlap between structural and sampling zeros may occur as structural and sampling zeros were introduced independently on \mathbf{Z} . We assumed that the hypothetical data analyst in our simulation study received the data matrix \mathbf{Z}^a which contained the

original right-skewed continuous intensity values \mathbf{Z} impeded by (undistinguishable) structural and sampling zeros.

For each combination of the parameters listed above, we considered three sample sizes ($n = 100, 200$ and 400) but always exactly 200 candidate predictors. We used a full factorial design, resulting in 486 scenarios with 500 repetitions each. The full specification of scenarios is stated in Table 1.

Table 1. Computation and overview of the number of total simulation scenarios

Source of variability	Number of configurations	Settings
OGM	3	A, B, C
Number of candidate predictors	1	200
Maximum proportion of total zero-inflation	3	0.25, 0.5, 0.75
Proportion of sampling and structural zeros	2	$(1/3, 2/3)$ and $(2/3, 1/3)$
Specification of the error variance	3	$R_{target}^2 = \{0.3, 0.6, 1\}$
Specification of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} contribution	3	Only \mathbf{U} , $\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{D}$, and $\mathbf{U} = 2\mathbf{D}$
Sample size	3	100, 200, 400
Total number of simulated scenarios	486	

3.3. Estimands

To assess the predictive performance, we considered the root mean squared prediction error (RMSPE), the relative RMSPE, the R^2 (i.e. the squared correlation between predicted and observed values) and the calibration slope (CS) of the fitted models on a validation dataset of size $n = 100,000$ that was generated once for each scenario. The relative RMSPE was obtained by dividing the RMSPE of each method by the RMSPE of the benchmark approach oracle-ridge. The CS was computed as the slope of a regression of the observed on the predicted outcome values. To assess predictor selection we recorded the number of selected predictors $q_S(\cdot)$, where a predictor counted as 'selected' if either the continuous or the binary component or both were selected into the final model. We also assessed the true positive discovery rate (TPDR) and the false negative discovery rate (FNDR), which refer to the proportion of selected true predictors among all selected predictors and the proportion of falsely non-selected true predictors among all non-selected predictors, respectively.

3.4. Methods

In each of the simulated datasets, the regularized regression approaches defined in 2.2 and 2.3 were evaluated: (i) ridge, (ii) lasso, (iii) lasso-ridge, (iv) ridge-lasso, and (v) ridge-garrote. Prior to model fitting, the generated matrix of predictors \mathbf{Z}^a of each simulated data set was transformed in accordance

with Section 2.1 to obtain the binary matrix \mathbf{D} as well as the two continuous data matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{U} . For \mathbf{X} , PMVs were substituted prior to the log-transformation by half the global minimum of the non-PMVs in \mathbf{Z}^a , while for \mathbf{U} , PMVs were substituted by the predictor-specific geometric means of the non-PMVs in \mathbf{Z}^a (see Supplementary Figure 5). Thus, the models containing both \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} considered the 200 predictors with 2 components each, resulting in 400 component variables to be included. The regularization parameter λ of the one-stage models was chosen by minimizing the 10-times repeated 10-fold cross-validated RMSPE across a range of 50 potential values for λ [21, 22]. For the two-stage approaches, in addition to the selection process used for the one-stage models, we conducted a grid search to identify the optimal combination of $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$ among 50^2 possible combinations (see Supplementary Material Section 1.5).

In addition to the regularized regression approaches, we estimated 'oracle models' using ordinary least squares (oracle-OLS) and using ridge regression (oracle-ridge) where exactly the true predictors were included. Table 2 outlines the data utilization within the models, model specifications, regularization parameters, and the coefficients estimated in the final model.

Table 2. Overview of model specifications and data usage at each stage for both the one-stage and two-stage regularized regression approaches

Approach	Data for the Modelling Stages		Regularization parameter	Estimated coefficients
	Stage 1	Stage 2		
Oracle-OLS	True predictors in \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D}	-	-	$\beta_{\mathbf{U}}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{D}}$
Oracle-ridge	True predictors in \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D}	-	λ	$\beta_{\mathbf{U}}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{D}}$
Ridge	\mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D}	-	λ	$\beta_{\mathbf{U}}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{D}}$
Lasso	\mathbf{X}	-	λ	$\beta_{\mathbf{X}}$
Lasso-ridge	\mathbf{X}	Subset of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D}	(λ_1, λ_2)	$\beta_{\mathbf{U}}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{D}}$
Ridge-lasso	\mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D}	\mathbf{X} and \mathbf{D}	(λ_1, λ_2)	$\beta_{\mathbf{X}}$ and/or $\beta_{\mathbf{D}}$
Ridge-garrote	\mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D}	\mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D}	(λ_1, λ_2)	$\beta_{\mathbf{U}}$ and $\beta_{\mathbf{D}}$

All methods were implemented in the R statistical programming language (R version 4.2.3, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). The code of the simulation study and the implementation of the methods are publicly available as a web supplement on Github: [mgregorich/ZIPSel](https://github.com/mgregorich/ZIPSel).

3.5. Performance measures

As performance measures for the models' predictive capabilities, we computed the mean and standard deviation of the RMSPE, the R^2 and the CS across the 500 simulation replicates. The expected values of the TPDR and the FNDR were obtained by taking the mean across simulation replicates in each scenario. Additionally, we determined the predictor inclusion frequency (PIF) [23], representing the probability of each predictor being included, estimated as the proportion of replicates where a predictor was included. Lastly, Monte Carlo Standard Errors (MCSEs) for the RMSPE were computed [18].

3.6. Results

Here we present the main findings from the simulation study, for more details we will refer to the supplementary material.

3.6.1. Predictive ability

Predictive accuracy evaluated on the validation dataset is illustrated in Figure 1 and Supplementary Figures 6-8. In simulation scenarios with a target $R^2 \in \{0.6, 0.3\}$, the predictive performance of all modelling approaches, except for lasso in the UD dependency setting 'U', was comparable in terms of RMSPE relative to oracle-ridge, as illustrated in Figure 1. For better scale and clarity, the scenarios with a target $R^2 = 1$ have been edited out of Figure 1 but are depicted in Supplemental Figure 6.

Figure 1. Mean relative root mean squared prediction error (RMSPE) for the three UD dependency settings and three outcome generating mechanisms (OGMs) across sample sizes and target R^2 values of 0.6 and 0.3. The maximum percentage of zero-inflation of 75% is fixed of which 1/3 and 2/3 are structural zeros, respectively.

Ridge regression exhibited a slightly superior predictive performance compared to its competitors in OGMs A and C, whereas the lasso had the highest relative RMSPE across all scenarios. Within the two-stage approaches, lasso-ridge outperformed ridge-lasso and ridge-garrote in all scenarios, albeit with only a very small improvement in relative RMSPE. In OGM B, ridge outperformed competitors at low sample sizes ($n = 100$). However, its RMSPE improvements with larger samples were relatively less pronounced compared to those achieved by oracle-ridge (and its competitors), leading to increased relative RMSPE in those cases, as can be seen in Figure 1.

The one-stage methods did not show good calibration across most scenarios, especially noticeable in scenarios with low sample sizes (see Supplementary Figure 7). Specifically, lasso exhibited poor calibration when solely the continuous component was associated with the outcome in the UD dependency scenarios ‘U’ (see Figure 1 and Supplementary Figure 7). Further, the target R^2 values were only approximately achieved by the benchmark models oracle-OLS and oracle-ridge despite increasing sample size, as depicted in Supplementary Figure 8. Even in scenarios without added residual error ($R^2_{target} = 1$), the estimated R^2 remained below 1 for all models, due to the information loss induced by sampling zeros and the effects of data transformations.

3.6.2. Evaluation of predictor selection

Across scenarios in which both, the continuous component and the binary component were associated with the outcome (UD dependency settings ‘U=D’ and ‘U=2D’), the ridge-garrote approach selected fewer or as many predictors as its competitors, and with the smallest variability, as shown in Figure 2. Lasso-ridge exhibited high variability in the number of selected predictors.

Figure 2. Number of selected predictors across simulation replicates for all one-stage and two-stage modelling approaches for the outcome-generating mechanisms (OGMs) A, B and C and the UD dependency settings ‘U’, ‘U=D’ and ‘U=2D’ pertaining to a setting of $n = 400$, a target R^2 of 0.6,

maximum 75% zero values of which 1/3 are structural zero and 2/3 sampling zeros. Black dashed line marks the number of true predictors associated with the outcome for each OGM. Oracle-ridge and ridge are included as benchmark approaches.

While lasso showed low variability in the number of selected predictors, it also tended to have the highest median number of selected predictors followed either by lasso-ridge or ridge-lasso in most scenarios. In most scenarios, ridge-lasso and ridge-garrote had the smallest median numbers of selected predictors. In a direct comparison between the two competitors, ridge-lasso and ridge-garrote, depicted in Supplementary Figure 9, ridge-garrote selected fewer predictors than or as many predictors as ridge-lasso when the continuous and binary component of the predictor were associated with the outcome (setting ‘U=D’ and ‘U=2D’). This was particularly pronounced for higher sample sizes ($n = 400$), while for lower sample sizes ($n = 100$), predictor selection was comparable between ridge-lasso and ridge-garrote.

In Supplementary Figure 10, the PIF of each predictor across simulation replicates for each OGM are illustrated. The PIF for both lasso and lasso-ridge models was influenced by the distribution and magnitude of zero-inflation, while ridge-lasso and ridge-garrote remained largely unaffected. This was evident as the PIF tended to be elevated for predictors exhibiting greater zero-inflation, and conversely, lower for those with lower zero-inflation. This observation was highlighted upon comparing Supplementary Figure 10 with the zero-inflation distribution depicted in Supplementary Figure 2. In terms of TPDR depicted in Supplementary Figure 11, ridge-garrote was more effective than ridge-lasso in selecting true predictors in OGM B when there were few true predictors available. However, the true-positive discovery rate was quite low for all methods in population setting B compared to A and C. In most other scenarios, the TPDR outcomes of both methodologies largely coincided, except in low sample sizes settings in which ridge-lasso demonstrated a higher TPDR.

4. Real data analysis: Prediction of kidney function

In this section, we employed the regularized regression approaches and a random forest to predict kidney function based on demographic covariates (age, sex) and a set of predictors obtained through mass-spectrometry. The dataset results from a pooled cohort of urine samples that were analyzed by Mosaiques Diagnostics and comprised 3210 observations on 3192 proteomic predictors. The outcome variable of interest was the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), a measure of kidney function estimated by the CKD-EPI equation [24], with a mean \pm standard deviation in the cohort of 92.50 ± 23.47 . The set of candidate predictors comprised age (52 ± 14 years), gender (47% female), and the proteomic variables (Supplementary Table 2). Before analysis, we transformed the peptide intensity values as follows (see Supplementary Figure 12): For methods utilizing X (lasso and stage 1 of lasso-ridge), we \log_2 -transformed the non-PMVs, substituting PMVs with half the global minimum of the

log₂-transformed non-PMVs across all peptides. For methods utilizing \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} (ridge, stage 2 of lasso-ridge, ridge-lasso and ridge-garrote), we log₂-transformed the non-PMVs for the continuous component, substituting PMVs with the mean of the log₂-transformed non-PMVs. Consequently, coefficients linked to the binary component variables \mathbf{D} can be understood as the expected difference in the outcome variable when comparing a subject with an average non-zero intensity to one with no intensity for a peptide. We included the demographic variables in the analysis using the ‘residual’ method as proposed in De Bin et al. [25]. First, a linear model is fitted based on the demographic covariates only, then the resulting linear predictor is included as an offset in a regularized regression model using the peptides as predictors. The continuous variables in \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{U} were standardized using the standard deviation of the log₂-transformed non-PMVs. Predictive accuracy was evaluated by 10-fold cross-validation. For the validation data, the offset of unseen individuals is estimated from the linear model based on the demographic variables and included in the prediction procedure.

In the analysis of mass-spectrometry data peptidomic predictors which exhibit excessive proportions of PMVs are frequently discarded before outcome modelling, as their distribution is nearly degenerate and not informative for prediction. Figure 3 examines the modelling methods across various cutoff levels for the maximum allowed proportion of PMVs (maxPMV) to explore how sensitive results are to these cutoff levels. The highest maxPMV considered was 90%, preselecting 1,333 peptides out of 3,192.

Figure 3. Performance of the regularized regression approaches and the random forest in terms of (A) 10-fold cross-validated root mean squared prediction error (RMSPE) and (B) the number of included/selected peptides (B). The x-axis represents the maximum allowed proportion of PMVs (maxPMV) within a predictor.

The patterns observed in the model evaluation across different maxPMV for lasso, ridge, ridge-lasso, lasso-ridge, and ridge-garrote were similar to the findings of the simulation study. Ridge, lasso-ridge and ridge-lasso mostly overlapped in terms of predictive accuracy and outperformed the competitors (Figure 3, left). Notably, random forest which is not capable of variable selection did not exhibit better predictive performance compared to other methods (Figure 3, left) and did not improve in RMSPE with increasing availability of zero-inflated candidate predictors. Further, the representation of zero-inflated

predictors by component variables U and D (Strategy A of Section 2.1) was always superior to using only X (Strategy B) no matter which method was used (see Supplementary Figure 13).

Figure 3 (right) shows that the ridge-garrote model was the approach with the smallest number of selected peptides and demonstrated stability in predictor selection across increasing levels of maxPMV in contrast to lasso-ridge. The lasso-ridge model, despite its predictive capabilities, showed similar variability in terms of the number of selected variables as in the simulation study, as can be seen by the sudden jump in selected predictors at a maximum percentage of zero-inflation of 90%. Furthermore, Supplementary Figure 14 demonstrates that the random forest performed considerably worse in terms of calibration compared to other models. Figure 4 highlights a significant difference in the execution time of the modelling approaches. The fastest of the approaches was random forest, followed by the one-stage methods. Lasso and ridge exhibited notably faster performance compared to the two-stage methods. Among the two-stage modelling approaches, ridge-garrote showed the lowest execution time, while ridge-lasso demonstrated the highest.

Figure 4. Logarithm of the execution time in seconds of the regularized regression approaches and the random forest. The measured time encompasses the execution of the grid search of the regularization parameter(s) via 10-fold cross-validation, 10 repetitions across a range of 100 potential values for λ and the fitting of the final model.

5. Discussion

In this study, we established and examined one-stage and two-stage regularized regression approaches, designed to address challenges arising from zero-inflated and correlated predictors. Our emphasis was on evaluating predictive performance and properties of predictor selection. While the findings of the simulation study demonstrated mostly small differences in predictive accuracy and calibration between all methods, the assessment of predictor selection highlighted an advantage of the ridge-lasso and ridge-garrote techniques. However, we noticed that when ridge-lasso had better prediction performance than

ridge-garrote this came at the price of selecting more noise predictors into the final model, in particular with higher sample sizes. In the case study regarding the prediction of kidney function based on a high-dimensional set of peptidomic variables, ridge-lasso, ridge and lasso-ridge exhibited the smallest RMSPE followed by ridge-garrote. Despite its good predictive performance, lasso-ridge exhibited large variability in the number of selected predictors both in the simulation study and in the applied case study. Ridge-garrote consistently selected a smaller set of peptides in comparison to its competitors both in the simulation and in the case study. Lasso with imputed PMVs and the random forest showed the poorest predictive performance among the approaches, thus emphasizing the importance of considering the binary component in addition to the continuous intensity values.

A simulation study can only cover a limited number of possible data models. We specified several plausible scenarios regarding the zero-inflation and correlation structure of predictors based on our real data example. The wide variety of scenarios studied likely allows to extend the conclusions on the capabilities of the regularized regression approaches in predictive performance and predictor selection also to data coming from different applications and following different data generating mechanisms.

The appropriate handling of PMVs in predictors continues to be a subject of ongoing research. Single component approaches such as the imputation of PMVs with the sample mean or with LOD , $LOD/2$ or $LOD/\sqrt{2}$ has been shown to lead to overestimated standard errors and/or biased estimates for the intercept and the slope in applied studies [4, 13, 26, 27]. By contrast, our study showed that strategies using component variables appeared to be more robust to mixtures of structural and sampling zeros. Recently a latent variable approach was proposed to disentangle such mixtures [13].

The choice of variable selection technique often depends on the specific attributes of the data, the objective of the research, and the balance between model simplicity and predictive accuracy sought by the data analyst. If obtaining a parsimonious model is not a priority, then our simulation study and applied case example revealed that ridge regression with two components representing the continuous and zero-inflated parts of the predictors is perhaps the optimal approach. The utility of ridge-garrote in achieving good predictive accuracy with a minimal set of predictors was apparent in presence of many candidate predictors with varying degree of zero-inflation. If the number of selected predictors is irrelevant, lasso-ridge provided good predictive accuracy. It assumes that all PMVs are sampling zeros at the first stage (which in our simulation study was only partly true), but then relaxes this assumption at the second stage by considering two-component specifications of the selected predictors. A parsimonious selection of a set of predictors that can accurately predict the outcome is often desirable for economic reasons when applying the model, in particular if there is little or no gain when considering all candidate predictors in the model.

In this study we have presented and investigated five regularized regression approaches in their capabilities in dealing with zero-inflated and correlated predictors. While the choice of method may

depend on the goal of the analysis to achieve a larger or smaller number of selected predictors, our study demonstrated that optimal predictive accuracy can only be achieved when zero-inflated predictors are appropriately handled using two component variables. Ridge-garrote demonstrated to be an attractive analysis option in situations in which the generation of a shortlist of predictors with good predictive performance is the objective.

Conflicts of interest

Harald.Mischak is the co-founder and co-owner of Mosaiques Diagnostics. All other authors have no conflict of interest to disclose.

Data Availability

Data of the case study cannot be shared for ethical/privacy reasons. The code of the simulation study is publicly available at GitHub under: mgregorich/ZIPSeI,

Funding

This work was supported by the Austrian Academy of Sciences from which Mariella Gregorich received funding as part of the DOC fellowship.

6. References

1. Gleiss, A., M. Dakna, H. Mischak, et al., *Two-group comparisons of zero-inflated intensity values: the choice of test statistic matters*. *Bioinformatics*, 2015. **31**(14): p. 2310-2317.
2. Huang, Z. and C. Wang, *A Review on Differential Abundance Analysis Methods for Mass Spectrometry-Based Metabolomic Data*. *Metabolites*, 2022. **12**(4): p. 305.
3. Yin, X., D. Levy, C. Willinger, et al., *Multiple imputation and analysis for high-dimensional incomplete proteomics data*. *Stat Med*, 2016. **35**(8): p. 1315-1326.
4. Nie, L., H. Chu, C. Liu, et al., *Linear regression with an independent variable subject to a detection limit*. *Epidemiology (Cambridge, Mass.)*, 2010. **21**(Suppl 4): p. S17.
5. Gajjala, P.R., H. Bruck, H. Noels, et al., *Novel plasma peptide markers involved in the pathology of CKD identified using mass spectrometric approach*. *J Mol Med*, 2019. **97**: p. 1451-1463.
6. Pena, M.J., J. Jankowski, G. Heinze, et al., *Plasma proteomics classifiers improve risk prediction for renal disease in patients with hypertension or type 2 diabetes*. *J Hypertens*, 2015. **33**(10): p. 2123-2132.
7. Gajjala, P.R., V. Jankowski, G. Heinze, et al., *Proteomic-biostatistic integrated approach for finding the underlying molecular determinants of hypertension in human plasma*. *Hypertension*, 2017. **70**(2): p. 412-419.
8. De Beer, D., C.M. Mels, A.E. Schutte, et al., *Identifying a urinary peptidomics profile for hypertension in young adults: The African-PREDICT study: Urinary peptidomics and hypertension*. *Proteomics*, 2023. **23**(11): p. 2200444.

9. Rodríguez-Ortiz, M.E., C. Pontillo, M. Rodríguez, et al., *Novel urinary biomarkers for improved prediction of progressive eGFR loss in early chronic kidney disease stages and in high risk individuals without chronic kidney disease*. Sci Rep, 2018. **8**(1): p. 15940.
10. Brondani, L.d.A., A.A. Soares, M. Recamonde-Mendoza, et al., *Urinary peptidomics and bioinformatics for the detection of diabetic kidney disease*. Sci Rep, 2020. **10**(1): p. 1242.
11. Breiman, L., *Better subset regression using the nonnegative garrote*. Technometrics, 1995. **37**(4): p. 373-384.
12. Lorenz, E., C. Jenkner, W. Sauerbrei, et al., *Modeling Variables With a Spike at Zero: Examples and Practical Recommendations*. Am J Epidemiol, 2017. **185**(8): p. 650-660.
13. Ye, P., S. Bai, W. Tang, et al., *Joint modeling approaches for censored predictors due to detection limits with applications to metabolites data*. Stat Med, 2023.
14. Tang, W., H. He, W. Wang, et al., *Untangle the structural and random zeros in statistical modelings*. Journal of applied statistics, 2018. **45**(9): p. 1714-1733.
15. Tibshirani, R., *Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso*. Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological), 1996. **58**(1): p. 267-288.
16. Hastie, T., R. Tibshirani, J.H. Friedman, et al., *The elements of statistical learning: data mining, inference, and prediction*. Vol. 2. 2009: Springer.
17. Yuan, M. and Y. Lin, *On the non-negative garrote estimator*. Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology, 2007. **69**(2): p. 143-161.
18. Morris, T.P., I.R. White, and M.J. Crowther, *Using simulation studies to evaluate statistical methods*. Stat Med, 2019. **38**(11): p. 2074-2102.
19. Hardin, J., S.R. Garcia, and D. Golan, *A method for generating realistic correlation matrices*. The Annals of Applied Statistics, 2013: p. 1733-1762.
20. Kaul, A., O. Davidov, and S.D. Peddada, *Structural zeros in high-dimensional data with applications to microbiome studies*. Biostatistics, 2017. **18**(3): p. 422-433.
21. Boulesteix, A.-L., A. Richter, and C. Bernau. *Complexity selection with cross-validation for lasso and sparse partial least squares using high-dimensional data*. in *Algorithms from and for Nature and Life: Classification and Data Analysis*. 2013. Springer.
22. Boulesteix, A.-L., R. De Bin, X. Jiang, et al., *IPF-LASSO: integrative-penalized regression with penalty factors for prediction based on multi-omics data*. Comput Math Methods Med, 2017. **2017**.
23. Wallisch, C., D. Dunkler, G. Rauch, et al., *Selection of variables for multivariable models: Opportunities and limitations in quantifying model stability by resampling*. Stat Med, 2021. **40**(2): p. 369-381.
24. Levey, A.S., L.A. Stevens, C.H. Schmid, et al., *A new equation to estimate glomerular filtration rate*. Ann Intern Med, 2009. **150**(9): p. 604-612.
25. De Bin, R., W. Sauerbrei, and A.L. Boulesteix, *Investigating the prediction ability of survival models based on both clinical and omics data: two case studies*. Stat Med, 2014. **33**(30): p. 5310-5329.
26. Hornung, R.W. and L.D. Reed, *Estimation of average concentration in the presence of nondetectable values*. Appl Occup Environ Hyg, 1990. **5**(1): p. 46-51.
27. Arunajadai, S.G. and V.A. Rauh, *Handling covariates subject to limits of detection in regression*. Environmental and ecological statistics, 2012. **19**(3): p. 369-391.

Supplementary Material

1. Additional information on the simulation study

1.1. The hub correlation structure in the data generation

The hub correlation structure pertained to a setting with 4 groups, where the variables within each group were linked to a central variable (known as the hub) with decreasing levels of correlation strength with increasing distance (in terms of position in the group) to the hub. The hub variable was chosen to be the first variable in each group i.e. the variable with index 1, 51, 101, and 151.

Supplementary Figure 1. Specification of the hub correlation structure of the simulated data with 4 groups.

1.2. Specification of zero-inflation of the variables

The shape of the distribution of the proportion of total zero-inflation across candidate predictors within each group was motivated by the observed shape in the dataset from Mosaiques Diagnostics, as illustrated in Supplementary Figure 2. If the proportion of zero-inflation is sorted in an increasing manner and plotted per variable, we can observe an approximately linear increase of zero-inflation in the variables until levelling out at a maximum allowed proportion of zero-inflation of 75%. The maximum proportion of total zero-inflation in the simulation study was restricted to 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75, respectively. Since researchers don't know the split between structural and sampling zeros in a real dataset, the total proportion of zero-inflation was subdivided in varying levels of the proportion of structural and sampling zeros such that one comprised $1/3$ or $2/3$ of the data, while the other made up the rest.

Supplementary Figure 2. Proportion of total zero-inflation observed in the data set from Mosaiques Diagnostics restricted to a maximum allowed percentage of PMVs of 90%. The red dashed line indicates the maximum allowed percentage of PMVs across peptides.

Supplementary Figure 3. Distribution of the proportion of zero-inflation across predictors in each group for a scenario with a structural zero proportion of 1/3 and sampling zeros of 2/3 with a maximum allowed proportion of zero-inflation of 75% across the three outcome generating mechanisms (OGM).

Supplementary Table 1. Overview of zero-inflation specifications with allocation for structural and sampling zeros.

Maximum percentage of zero-inflation	Structural proportion	Percentage of structural zeros	Sampling proportion	Percentage of sampling zeros
75%	1/3	25%	2/3	50%
	2/3	50%	1/3	25%
50%	1/3	16.7%	2/3	33.3%
	2/3	33.3%	1/3	16.7%
25%	1/3	8.3%	2/3	16.7%
	2/3	16.7%	1/3	8.3

1.3. Outcome-generating mechanism and variable effect specification: A, B, and C

Different effect specifications of the four predictor groups were established to investigate the regularized regression methods under diverse scenarios, as illustrated in Supplementary Figure 4.

Supplementary Figure 4. True regression coefficients for each OGM setting across predictor groups for the continuous (red) and binary (red) component variables corresponding to each predictor.

1.4. Data transformations

Supplementary Figure 5. Distribution of simulated data with (A) the log-normal distributed data, (B) the log-transformed log-normal distributed data with PMVs at half the global minimum and the two component variables: the continuous component with PMVs at the mean of the log-transformed log-normal data (C1) and the binary component indicating values above 0 (C2).

1.5. Penalty parameter tuning for the two-stage approaches

The penalization parameters λ_1 and λ_2 can be pre-specified, but are usually optimized simultaneously by minimizing the RMSPE with 10-fold cross validation or the optimization of an information criterion such as Akaike's information criterion. This involves evaluating a series of penalties in the first step (lasso), where each penalty parameter is assessed against a sequence of penalties in the second step (ridge). This process generates a matrix of potential penalty parameters. The optimal combination is determined by iteratively calculating the cross-validated root mean squared prediction error (RMSPE) for each pairing, with the process being repeated R times. The RMSPEs across each iteration and repeated run for each combination (λ_1, λ_2) are then averaged and the pair resulting in the minimum RMSPE is selected.

1.6. Results of the simulation study

Supplementary Figure 6. Relative RMSPE for all methods. Relative RMSPE was obtained by dividing the method's RMSPE by that of the benchmark method ridge-oracle in each simulation replicate on the validation data ($n = 100,000$). Results are given for different outcome generating mechanisms (OGM A, B, C) and UD dependency setting ('U', 'U=D', 'U=2D') with a fixed maximum proportion of zero-inflation of 75% of which 2/3 comprise structural zeros and 1/3 sampling zeros.

Supplementary Figure 7. Mean calibration slope for all methods evaluated on the validation data ($n = 100,000$). Results are given for different outcome generating mechanisms (OGM A, B, C) and UD dependency setting ('U', 'U=D', 'U=2D') with a fixed maximum proportion of zero-inflation of 75% of which 2/3 comprise structural zeros and 1/3 sampling zeros.

Supplementary Figure 8. Achieved R^2 for all methods on the validation data ($n = 100,000$). R^2 was defined as defined as the squared correlation in predicted and observed values. Results are given for different outcome generating mechanisms (OGM A, B, C) and UD dependency setting ('U', 'U=D', 'U=2D') with a fixed maximum proportion of zero-inflation of 75% of which 2/3 comprise structural zeros and 1/3 sampling zeros.

Supplementary Figure 9. Direct comparison in the number of selected peptides between ridge-lasso $q_s(\text{ridge-lasso})$ and ridge-garrote $q_s(\text{ridge-garrote})$ for $n = 400$, fixed proportion of structural zeros of 1/3 of the maximum proportion of zero-inflation and no added residual error. A positive difference indicates the selection of more predictors for the ridge-lasso approach, while negative values indicate more peptides selected in the ridge-garrote approach.

Supplementary Figure 10. Predictor inclusion frequency across simulation replicates in all outcome generating mechanisms A-C for each of the methods performing predictor selection with a fixed sample size of $n = 200$, a maximum proportion of zero-inflation of 75% with 1/3 structural zero proportion, UD dependency 'U=D' and

target $R^2=1$. Predictor inclusion frequency of oracle-ridge was included in the figure in grey to indicate the true predictors across OGMs and groups.

Supplementary Figure 11. True-positive discovery rate of all regularized regression methods across simulation replicates for all outcome generating mechanisms (OGM A, B, C) and for a setting with maximum proportion of zero-inflation of 75% of which 1/3 are structural zeros and 2/3 sampling zeros.

2. Additional information on the real-life data example: Prediction of kidney function

2.1. Data and modelling strategy

The dataset contains data from 3,210 individuals, encompassing measurements of 3,192 peptides obtained through mass spectrometry.

Supplementary Table 2. Overview of patients' characteristics of the data from Mosaiques Diagnostics

Variable	Value
Sample size (n)	3,210
Peptides (n)	3,192
Age, years	52.03 ± 13.46
Sex, female (%)	1,510 (47.0)
eGFR, 1.73m ² /min/1	92.50 ± 23.47

Out of the total 3,192 peptides, only 1,333 exhibited more than 10% non-zero values (i.e., intensity values above 0) and were incorporated into the five regularized regression models and the random forest.

Due to the skewed nature of the original peptides' intensity values \mathbf{Z} , we used a \log_2 transformation for the continuous component \mathbf{U} of the peptide intensities defined as

$$u_{ij} := \begin{cases} \log(z_{ij}), & z_{ij} > 0, \\ m(z_j^+), & z_{ij} = 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where

$$m(z_j^+) := \frac{1}{n^+} \sum_{i=1}^n \log_2(z_{ij}) I(z_{ij} > 0) \quad (2)$$

with n^+ indicating the number of intensities z_{ij} larger than 0. This choice of replacement of zero signals in \mathbf{u}_j mainly aids the interpretability of the regression coefficients, but also other definitions are possible (e.g. the median of log-transformed positive intensities). For a model including \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{D} , the coefficients corresponding to the binary variable can be interpreted as the expected difference in the outcome variable when comparing a subject with an average non-zero signal to a subject with absent signal for a peptide. For \mathbf{X} , data was \log_2 -transformed and PMVs were substituted with half the global minimum of the \log_2 -transformed non-PMVs.

Supplementary Figure 12 illustrates the impact of the data transformations on the distribution of a peptide's original intensity values displayed in Panel A. Panel B exhibits Strategy B resulting in a more normal distribution for positive values, with zeros replaced by half of the minimum \log_2 -transformed value. Panels C1 and C2 depict the Strategy A with the continuous and binary component variables, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 12. Illustration of the original intensity values of one selected peptide exhibiting 25% PMVs and the implications of the strategies of handling zero-inflated predictors in the dataset provided by Mosaiques Diagnostics,.

We used the random forest to investigate whether an ensemble method not requiring data pre-processing could yield improved prediction performance. The number of trees was set to 1,000 as a compromise between performance, stable variable importance estimates and computation time [17, 18]. Bootstrap samples were drawn with replacement. We expected only minor improvements by optimizing the values of the hyperparameters for random forest according to [19]. Thus, only the default setting for $mtry$ as $\lfloor \frac{p}{3} \rfloor$, a node size of 5 and a splitting rule minimizing the variance was implemented.

2.2. Results of the data example

The real-life data example demonstrated the importance of strategy A to represent the distribution of a zero-inflated predictor by two component variables. We did not only fit the models according to the component variable strategy but also implemented all methods using the \log_2 -transformed data, with PMVs substituted by half of the minimum value to assess the impact of the component split.

Supplementary Figure 13. RMSPE for all modelling approaches and random forest is depicted, with solid lines representing approaches using the component split strategy, and dashed lines denoting the imputation approach for PMVs.

Supplementary Figure 14. Calibration of the modelling approaches and random forest in terms of

IV

Discussion

4.1 Summary of contributions and implications

This doctoral thesis explored statistical approaches for handling correlated variables to improve prediction modelling. Throughout this thesis, we have demonstrated the multifaceted challenges posed by complex correlation structures. These challenges persist, necessitating not only innovative methodologies but also a reassessment of current practices in applied data analysis. An innovative approach to handle correlated variables explored in this thesis was individual-specific network inference. It not only proved to be a flexible alternative approach to deal with many correlated variables but it is also biologically motivated by the system organization of molecular or neuroimaging-derived variables. Despite these advancements, our understanding of how the system perspective focused on the individual level, might yield valuable insights beyond neuroscience remains in its early stages. Particularly, its potential applications in fields like molecular medicine are yet to be fully explored as described in Paper II. For this to happen in the future, new methods of individual-specific network inference will need to be thoroughly developed and validated against existing approaches, as performed in Paper III. As new approaches to individual-specific network inference are developed, new directions in research will emerge and the need for further development will increase. While the steps in applied data analysis and the choice of the modelling approach should be guided by the modelling objective for the most part, an additional aspect is presented by the trade-off between model simplicity and minimum predictive accuracy required. Researchers often strive to condense the abundant information into a concise set of predictors to obtain a parsimonious prediction model. We have highlighted the importance of not overlooking an old but forgotten technique such as the nonnegative garrote in Paper IV, by comparing it to other common regularized regression approaches, which we defined for zero-inflated predictors. With an abundant set of correlated and zero-inflated candidate predictors, it generated more parsimonious models with only a minimal loss in predictive accuracy.

The main contributions of the doctoral thesis are encapsulated in Chapter III. To ensure transparent reporting, the code for Papers I, III, and IV was shared on the open-source platform GitHub as distinct repositories under the username 'mgregorich'. The scoping review described in Paper II did not require coding. The remainder of this section delves into the implications of the four manuscripts comprising this thesis.

Implications of our results for handling highly correlated predictors in regression modelling

Important aspects of initial data analysis are often either disregarded or approached with minimal regard for the modelling objective, resulting in model misuse and misspecification [92, 93]. With insufficient knowledge about the data structure and the subject matter,

data analysts might be quick to deem one or more of the set of correlated predictors redundant. The problem may originate from being taught statistical problem-solving and analysis strategies in overly simplified settings without regard for the intended objective of the data analysis [94]. This leads to the misconception that variable omission has universal application if highly correlated predictors are present, irrespective of the research question intended to be answered by the statistical model. In Gregorich et al. [1], we demonstrated how diagnostic tools of collinearity may fail in guiding the applied data analyst through three applied data examples for each modelling objective: descriptive, predictive, and explanatory modelling. If collinearity is detected, the model may need to be altered but variable omission can result in the exclusion of confounding variables or valuable variables are deemed redundant. Paper I's original contribution is to highlight the importance of the research question to appropriately interpret results from diagnostic tools for detecting collinearity. It demonstrates the consequences of misconduct through applied data examples, and as a result, the paper has garnered extensive usage among applied researchers, has been recommended in scientific social media, and to our knowledge was the subject of several journal clubs.

Diagnostic tools alone cannot detect whether collinearity will provoke issues in the model. Additional investigations, such as monitoring deviations from model behavior expected by subject matter knowledge, changes in the estimated magnitude of coefficients, or changes in the sign of covariate effects due to small alterations in the data, may also indicate the presence of collinearity. Our study has demonstrated that despite diagnostic tools indicating no issues of collinearity (in the prediction setting), the effects of collinearity may still arise. This issue may arise due to the inadequacy of diagnostic tools presently available. For instance, Mela and Kopalle [95] suggest that the effects of collinearity are moderated by the correlation between the outcome and the independent variables, as well as by the sign of the correlation. It is worth noting that interdependencies among explanatory variables do not necessarily pose problems. However, it is essential to determine whether a problem exists and if any alterations to the model specification would impact the research question before attempting to rectify any issues.

All analyses and findings presented were complemented by publicly accessible data and code hosted on GitHub under the repository 'mgregorich/CorrPred'. The paper explores one common misconception in statistical modelling. However, the impact of inappropriate analysis is far-reaching, including issues with selecting variables [96] or choosing functional forms [97]

Implications of our results for individual-specific network inference

Motivated by Paper I and the network-based analysis of the human T cell repertoire dy-

namics outlined in Aschauer et al. [5], the concept emerged that the abundance of variables unique to each individual within the 'omics' domains, such as genomics and proteomics, could potentially be utilized to model their molecular systems as individual-specific networks. Therefore, we explored the consideration of the explicit incorporation of relational data structures into statistical modelling by employing individual-specific network inference in Paper II. Our scoping review revealed an increasing interest, extending beyond neurological applications in recent years. Although the analysis of brain imaging data in neuroscience has naturally fuelled the interest in individual-specific network inference, its usage is expanding as an emerging field in the analysis of omics and gene-expression data. This expansion owes much to the advancement of pioneering techniques designed for individual-specific network inference such as novel Jackknife approaches or differential network analysis, which allow individual-specific network estimation from variables with a single measurement per individual. This development holds significant importance for enabling application in these research domains, given the absence of repeated measurements or time series data for the set of variables per individual. Nevertheless, given the range of application areas as evidenced by our scoping review, it is unlikely that one optimal inference method exists. Comparative studies are urgently needed to establish the superiority or inferiority of various inference approaches [98].

Statistical methods that complement the natural relational structure of molecular data hold promise in improving our comprehension of the differences in system behavior among individuals. However, these techniques are still in their early stages of application. A decade ago, Simpson et al. [33] stressed the benefits of integrating statistical expertise into brain network analysis, keeping in mind the interdisciplinary nature of the field. This need continues to be relevant today, as we have recognized methodological shortcomings, such as selecting variables based solely on univariate significance assessment, that have been known and criticized in the statistical community for a while [99]. To surmount these obstacles and attain methodological improvements and a consensus, cooperative endeavors involving multiple disciplines are crucial. However, achieving reproducibility continues to pose a significant obstacle owing to using different assay platforms, scanner types, or processing protocols and the need for large sample sizes to achieve sufficient statistical power to detect biological associations between biomarkers and the outcome [100].

Implications of our results for sparsification of correlation-based networks

Our proposed flexible thresholding operator proposed in Paper III can be viewed as the functional generalization of thresholding operators currently employed in practice. The integration of a flexible weighting function permits a combination of fundamental advantages, relative to existing network sparsification approaches. Instead of a simple pointwise evaluation as in current thresholding operators in network inference, we advocated for a

functional approach leveraging the predictive value of a graph-theoretical at varying sparsity levels of the networks. Our study revealed that various thresholding methods have divergent effects on the identification of graph-theoretical features and therefore their predictive value. We demonstrated that the weighting function provided reliable functional forms, irrespective of the thresholding approach used to establish the association between the individual-specific networks and the outcome. For a particular data analysis, choosing an optimal threshold can be challenging, making it essential to include a weighting scheme as a sensitivity analysis. Doing so can help to confirm decisions and increase the reproducibility of the selection. The flexible parameterization provides an alternative to deciding between a single selection or averaging across thresholds. This is achieved by allowing and explicitly estimating the most informative form, even if one of the naive thresholding schemes underlies the association. Nevertheless, a disadvantage is the computational complexity of the analysis approach which necessitates further degrees of freedom, as well as computing graph-theoretical features at every level of sparsity.

The code for the simulation study was made available on GitHub under the repository 'mgregorich/PRONET'.

Implications of our results for variable selection with correlated and zero-inflated predictors

In Paper IV, we demonstrated that the ridge-garrote method presents a comparable analysis option to conventional one-stage and two-stage regularized regression techniques when selecting variables amidst an extensive set of correlated and zero-inflated predictors. For the ridge-garrote, we employed ridge regression in the first stage, as advised by Yuan and Lin [75], due to the challenges associated with the OLS estimates as in the classical nonnegative garrote approach introduced by [74] when dealing with high-dimensional correlated predictors. The ridge-garrote approach exhibited comparable predictive accuracy of a scalar outcome to the commonly employed regularized regression techniques such as lasso, ridge, or adaptive lasso. The ridge-garrote approach was able to achieve this performance with smaller predictor sets — an imperative objective in many omics data analysis tasks. This attribute is particularly crucial in the study of biofluid biomarkers due to the extensive costs, time, and labor involved in their analysis. Similarly to the implication of Paper I, the selection of the appropriate regression method should be guided by the intended research objective. If the aim is to obtain a concise collection of predictors with minimal compromise on predictive performance, then we showed that the ridge-garrote approach is an appropriate choice. If the focus is on improved predictive accuracy rather than variable selection, then ridge regression showed superiority over its evaluated competitors. In summary, Paper IV demonstrated that the ridge-garrote approach represents a promising alternative for variable selection in a high-dimensional setting with correlated

predictors suffering from zero inflation.

The code for the simulation study was made available on GitHub under the repository 'mgregorich/ZIPSel'.

4.2 Future prospects and outlook

Drawing upon the proposed concepts and methodology in this thesis, this section explores potential avenues for future research. Throughout the work on this thesis, additional topics for further investigation emerged that were beyond the scope of the PhD time frame. In this section, we will discuss three areas that have demonstrated research potential.

Novel methods for individual-specific networks inference

The advancement of theory and domain-specific applications in network analysis often unfolds independently, posing a risk to the seamless integration of theoretical and methodological advancements with the practical implementation of network science. As stated in the previous section, individual-specific network inference in genomics and proteomics is still in its infancy. In biomedical research, network inference is a flexible tool for uncovering the complex relationships between biological entities such as metabolites or peptides, using observed data to reveal dependency structures. While systems biology approaches have the potential to unravel disease-related complexity by fusing different layers of omics information, the resulting networks often overlook individual differences due to their reliance on aggregated data. Thus, there is an urgent need for algorithms and methods capable of estimating individual-specific networks.

As identified in our scoping review, two approaches have emerged recently. The first, known as "lioness" [48], operates based on the Jackknife principle also known as the leave-one-out approach which involves removing each individual once from the aggregated study cohort, such that the difference between the resulting network and the estimated full group-level network yields the individual-specific network. However, this approach has its drawbacks. First, the individual-specific network approach determines the individual's contribution to the network at the group level, indicating the deviation from the mean. As a result, the individual-specific network does not accurately reflect the individual's system behavior but rather indicates the degree of deviation from a network based on collected data. Secondly, edge weights are no longer confined to the range of $[-1, 1]$. As a result, the magnitude of the deviation is relative and reliant on the group-specific network and its underlying cohort. Lastly, independence is compromised, affecting the reliability of the results. Novel approaches are urgently needed that enable the inference of individual-specific system behavior without being dependent on the composition or size of the full study cohort.

A call for neutral comparative simulation studies in the evaluation of approaches for network construction and sparsification

Simulation studies are powerful tools for evaluating the performance of statistical methods because the true data generation mechanism and the underlying outcome association are known to the experimenter. Most evaluations of network inference methods for prediction modelling rely heavily on observational datasets, leaving a critical gap for neutral comparative simulation studies to evaluate network construction and sparsification approaches. For example, the simulation of realistic brain connectivity networks that closely mimic real brains remains uncharted territory. To fill this gap and advance our understanding, plausible data-generating models for setting up comparative simulation studies are essential. A closed, parametric, and scalable network data model would allow us to define hypothetical environments in which to reliably and reproducibly study network approaches. This groundwork could enable the simulation of individual networks that more closely resemble the intricate complexities found in real applications. Of course, no simulation design can cover all possible data settings of interest. However, researchers in all medical fields who wish to evaluate techniques for individual-specific network inference could modify designs that were made publicly available to suit their requirements. Additionally, synthetic data that is produced from generative network models does not raise any data sharing or privacy concerns in contrast to data obtained from research experiments involving human subjects.

The correlational structure among graph-theoretical features and variable selection

A potential issue arises with existing correlation structures when incorporating multiple graph-theoretical features into a statistical model. This is because certain graph-theoretical features tend to have an inherent association in specific network types. For instance, when examining functional brain networks, local efficiency, which measures the effective transmission of data, may display a robust positive correlation with modularity, which quantifies the creation of node clusters that feature an increase in edge formation. In some of the studies reviewed during the scoping process, some studies investigated up to 60 distinct graph-theoretical features [2]. These features were evaluated in terms of their relevance or insignificance using simplistic variable selection methods, such as univariate significance testing with the outcome.

An interesting endeavor would be to evaluate the handling of correlated graph-theoretical features with respect to variable selection within a neurological study where sufficient sample size is available. As a first method of variable selection, the nonnegative garrote approach can be considered, with the advantage that sets of graph-theoretical features that characterize similar attributes of the network structure or topology can be defined

in such a way that they would simultaneously be eliminated from or retained in a model. As shown in the definition of design variables for zero-inflated variables, the nonnegative garrote lends itself to the elimination of a set of design variables, e.g. defined as a set of graph-theoretical features with high correlation or defined by background knowledge to characterize the same network attribute. Such a study could close the loop of the papers included in this thesis by investigating whether regularised variable selection methods could be used with the graph-theoretical features, or whether correlated graph-theoretical features could be reparameterized using background knowledge, statistical properties, and the research objective as described in Paper I.

4.2.1 Final remarks

Correlation holds a crucial place in our understanding of the real world, yet it can lead to fallacies in scientific endeavors. The danger lies not only in mistaking correlation for causation but also in mishandling correlated variables in statistical modelling, leading to model misspecification and misinterpretation. While the aspiration to establish simple guidelines for applied researchers in handling correlated variables persists, it remains a matter shaped by the research objective rather than by rules of thumb. As evidenced, blindly following guidelines may not always be expedient, potentially resulting in suboptimal results if one of the correlated variables is omitted. The persistent lack of consensus in managing correlated variables persists, likely due to the absence of a universal solution. An interesting and promising approach to harnessing these patterns has emerged through the inference of individual-specific networks. Although many methodological gaps in individual-specific network inference demand attention, advancements in inference methods, particularly within the omics domain, could unveil new insights into the biological system's structure and pathogenesis. Despite the enthusiasm sparked by rich datasets driving the quest for innovative statistical techniques, it remains crucial not to overlook existing methodologies. For instance, the nonnegative garrote has proven to be a viable alternative for variable selection compared to other regularized regression methods, despite its prior neglect due to limitations in handling high-dimensional data.

Although dealing with a large set of correlated variables remains challenging, it is of utmost importance to keep the respective research question in mind when building a statistical model. Methodological research in the field of statistical modelling includes the critical evaluation of current practices, the consideration and refinement of existing methodologies, and the development of innovative methods when a methodological gap needs addressing. This doctoral thesis contributed to each of these principles and established a sound foundation for future research endeavors aimed at addressing complex correlation structures in statistical modelling, particularly when the research objective is prediction modelling.

Bibliography

1. Gregorich M, Strohmaier S, Dunkler D, and Heinze G. Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2021;18:4259.
2. Gregorich M, Melograna F, Sunqvist M, Michiels S, Van Steen K, and Heinze G. Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—A scoping review of methods. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. 2022;22:1–17.
3. Gregorich M, Simpson SL, and Heinze G. Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction. *arXiv preprint: 2308.15365*. 2023.
4. Gregorich M, Kammer M, Mischak H, and Heinze G. Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach. *arXiv preprint:2402.02064*. 2024.
5. Aschauer C, Jelencsics K, Hu K, Heinzel A, Gregorich MG, Vetter J, Schaller S, Winkler SM, Weinberger J, Pimenov L, et al. Prospective tracking of donor-reactive T-cell clones in the circulation and rejecting human kidney allografts. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2021;12:750005.
6. Gregorich M, Heinzel A, Kammer M, Meiselbach H, Böger C, Eckardt KU, Mayer G, Heinze G, and Oberbauer R. A prediction model for the decline in renal function in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus: study protocol. *Diagnostic and Prognostic Research*. 2021;5:1–9.
7. Aschauer C, Jelencsics K, Hu K, Gregorich M, Reindl-Schwaighofer R, Wenda S, Wekerle T, Heinzel A, and Oberbauer R. Effects of reduced-dose anti-human T-lymphocyte globulin on overall and donor-specific T-cell repertoire reconstitution in sensitized kidney transplant recipients. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2022;13:843452.
8. Kammer M, Heinzel A, Hu K, Meiselbach H, Gregorich M, Busch M, Duffin KL, Gomez MF, Eckardt KU, and Oberbauer R. Different roles of protein biomarkers predicting eGFR trajectories in people with chronic kidney disease and diabetes mellitus: a nationwide retrospective cohort study. *Cardiovascular Diabetology*. 2023;22:1–10.
9. Gregorich M, Kammer M, Heinzel A, Böger C, Eckardt KU, Heerspink HL, Jung B, Mayer G, Meiselbach H, Schmid M, et al. Development and Validation of a Prediction Model for Future Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate in People With Type 2 Diabetes and Chronic Kidney Disease. *JAMA Network Open*. 2023;6:e231870–e231870.
10. Heinze G, Wallisch C, and Dunkler D. Variable selection—a review and recommendations for the practicing statistician. *Biometrical Journal*. 2018;60:431–49.
11. Zhu W, Lévy-Leduc C, and Ternès N. Identification of prognostic and predictive biomarkers in high-dimensional data with PPLasso. *BMC Bioinformatics*. 2023;24:25.
12. Wang X and Leng C. High dimensional ordinary least squares projection for screening variables. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*. 2016;78:589–611.
13. Wang H, Lengerich BJ, Aragam B, and Xing EP. Precision Lasso: accounting for correlations and linear dependencies in high-dimensional genomic data. *Bioinformatics*. 2019;35:1181–7.
14. Barabasi AL and Oltvai ZN. Network biology: understanding the cell’s functional organization. *Nature Reviews Genetics*. 2004;5:101–13.
15. Barabási AL, Gulbahce N, and Loscalzo J. Network medicine: a network-based approach to human disease. *Nature Reviews Genetics*. 2011;12:56–68.

16. Huang S, Li J, Sun L, Ye J, Fleisher A, Wu T, Chen K, Reiman E, Initiative ADN, et al. Learning brain connectivity of Alzheimer’s disease by sparse inverse covariance estimation. *NeuroImage*. 2010;50:935–49.
17. Chaddock-Heyman L, Weng TB, Kienzler C, Weissshappel R, Drollette ES, Raine LB, Westfall DR, Kao SC, Baniqued P, Castelli DM, et al. Brain network modularity predicts improvements in cognitive and scholastic performance in children involved in a physical activity intervention. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*. 2020;14:346.
18. Dosenbach NU, Nardos B, Cohen AL, Fair DA, Power JD, Church JA, Nelson SM, Wig GS, Vogel AC, Lessov-Schlaggar CN, et al. Prediction of individual brain maturity using fMRI. *Science*. 2010;329:1358–61.
19. Qin J, Chen SG, Hu D, Zeng LL, Fan YM, Chen XP, and Shen H. Predicting individual brain maturity using dynamic functional connectivity. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*. 2015;9:418.
20. Belsley DA, Kuh E, and Welsch RE. *Regression diagnostics: Identifying influential data and sources of collinearity*. John Wiley & Sons, 2005.
21. Vaughan LK, Divers J, Padilla MA, Redden DT, Tiwari HK, Pomp D, and Allison DB. The use of plasmodes as a supplement to simulations: a simple example evaluating individual admixture estimation methodologies. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2009;53:1755–66.
22. Cattell R and Jaspers J. A general plasmode for factor analytic exercises and research (No. 30-10-52). *MBR Monographs*. 1967;3:67.
23. Pearson K. VII. Mathematical contributions to the theory of evolution.—III. Regression, heredity, and panmixia. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, containing papers of a mathematical or physical character*. 1896:253–318.
24. Spearman C. The Proof and Measurement of Association between Two Things. *The American Journal of Psychology*. 1904;15:72–101.
25. Embrechts P, McNeil A, and Straumann D. Correlation and dependence in risk management: properties and pitfalls. *Risk management: value at risk and beyond*. 2002;1:176–223.
26. Lauritzen SL. *Graphical models*. Vol. 17. Clarendon Press, 1996.
27. Epskamp S and Fried EI. A tutorial on regularized partial correlation networks. *Psychological Methods*. 2018;23:617.
28. Meinshausen N and Bühlmann P. High-dimensional graphs and variable selection with the Lasso. *The Annals of Statistics*. 2006;34:1436–62.
29. Kolaczyk ED and Csárdi G. *Statistical analysis of network data with R*. Vol. 65. Springer, 2014.
30. Maathuis M, Drton M, Lauritzen S, and Wainwright M. *Handbook of graphical models*. CRC Press, 2018.
31. Zhao H and Duan ZH. Cancer genetic network inference using Gaussian graphical models. *Bioinformatics and Biology Insights*. 2019;13:1177932219839402.
32. Zhang J and Li Y. High-dimensional Gaussian graphical regression models with covariates. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. 2023;118:2088–100.
33. Simpson SL, Bowman FD, and Laurienti PJ. Analyzing complex functional brain networks: fusing statistics and network science to understand the brain. *Statistics Surveys*. 2013;7:1.
34. Borsboom D and Cramer AO. Network analysis: an integrative approach to the structure of psychopathology. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*. 2013;9:91–121.
35. Shutta KH, De Vito R, Scholtens DM, and Balasubramanian R. Gaussian graphical models with applications to omics analyses. *Statistics in Medicine*. 41:5150–87.

36. Pineda S, Sigdel TK, Liberto JM, Vincenti F, Sirota M, and Sarwal MM. Characterizing pre-transplant and post-transplant kidney rejection risk by B cell immune repertoire sequencing. *Nature Communications*. 2019;10:1906.
37. Doucet GE, Rider R, Taylor N, Skidmore C, Sharan A, Sperling M, and Tracy JJ. Presurgery resting-state local graph-theory measures predict neurocognitive outcomes after brain surgery in temporal lobe epilepsy. *Epilepsia*. 2015;56:517–26.
38. Spisak T, Kincses B, Schlitt F, Zunhammer M, Schmidt-Wilcke T, Kincses ZT, and Bingel U. Pain-free resting-state functional brain connectivity predicts individual pain sensitivity. *Nature Communications*. 2020;11:187.
39. Pelgrim TA, Bossong MG, Cuiza A, Allende LM, Mena C, Tepper A, Ramirez-Mahaluf JP, Iuretagoyena B, Ornstein C, Fritsch R, et al. Abnormal nodal and global network organization in resting state functional MRI from subjects with the 22q11 deletion syndrome. *Scientific Reports*. 2021;11:21623.
40. Liu X, Wang Y, Ji H, Aihara K, and Chen L. Personalized characterization of diseases using sample-specific networks. *Nucleic Acids Research*. 2016;44:e164–e164.
41. Huang Y, Chang X, Zhang Y, Chen L, and Liu X. Disease characterization using a partial correlation-based sample-specific network. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*. 2021;22:bbaa062.
42. Park B, Lee W, Park I, and Han K. Finding prognostic gene pairs for cancer from patient-specific gene networks. *BMC Medical Genomics*. 2019;12:1–14.
43. Maron BA, Wang RS, Shevtsov S, Drakos SG, Arons E, Wever-Pinzon O, Huggins GS, Samokhin AO, Oldham WM, Aguib Y, et al. Individualized interactomes for network-based precision medicine in hypertrophic cardiomyopathy with implications for other clinical pathophenotypes. *Nature Communications*. 2021;12:873.
44. Chen S, Gallagher MJ, Hogg F, Papadopoulos MC, and Saadoun S. Visibility graph analysis of intraspinal pressure signal predicts functional outcome in spinal cord injured patients. *Journal of Neurotrauma*. 2018;35:2947–56.
45. Pathak A, Roy D, and Banerjee A. Whole-brain network models: from physics to bedside. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*. 2022;16:866517.
46. Xie S, Li X, McColgan P, Scahill RI, Zeng D, and Wang Y. Identifying disease-associated biomarker network features through conditional graphical model. *Biometrics*. 2020;76:995–1006.
47. Xie S, McDonnell E, and Wang Y. Conditional Gaussian graphical model for estimating personalized disease symptom networks. *Statistics in Medicine*. 2022;41:543–53.
48. Kuijjer ML, Tung MG, Yuan G, Quackenbush J, and Glass K. Estimating sample-specific regulatory networks. *Iscience*. 2019;14:226–40.
49. Dijkstra EW. A note on two problems in connexion with graphs:(*Numerische Mathematik*, 1 (1959), p 269-271). 1959.
50. Wasserman S and Faust K. *Social network analysis: methods and applications*. Cambridge University Press, 1994.
51. Wang Y, Ghumare E, Vandenberghe R, and Dupont P. Comparison of different generalizations of clustering coefficient and local efficiency for weighted undirected graphs. *Neural Computation*. 2017;29:313–31.
52. Saramäki J, Kivela M, Onnela JP, Kaski K, and Kertesz J. Generalizations of the clustering coefficient to weighted complex networks. *Physical Review E*. 2007;75:027105.
53. Fortunato S and Newman ME. 20 years of network community detection. *Nature Physics*. 2022;18:848–50.
54. Erdős P and Rényi A. On random graphs I. *Publicationes Mathematicae Debrecen*. 1959;6:18.
55. Watts DJ and Strogatz SH. Collective dynamics of ‘small-world’ networks. *Nature*. 1998;393:440–2.

56. Barabási AL and Albert R. Emergence of scaling in random networks. *Science*. 1999;286:509–12.
57. Buchanan CR, Bastin ME, Ritchie SJ, Liewald DC, Madole JW, Tucker-Drob EM, Deary IJ, and Cox SR. The effect of network thresholding and weighting on structural brain networks in the UK Biobank. *NeuroImage*. 2020;211:116443.
58. Craddock C, Benhajali Y, Chu C, Chouinard F, Evans A, Jakab A, Khundrakpam BS, Lewis JD, Li Q, Milham M, Yan C, and Bellec P. The neuro bureau preprocessing initiative: open sharing of preprocessed neuroimaging data and derivatives. *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics*. 2013;7:5.
59. Di Martino A, Yan CG, Li Q, Denio E, Castellanos FX, Alaerts K, Anderson JS, Assaf M, Bookheimer SY, Dapretto M, et al. The autism brain imaging data exchange: towards a large-scale evaluation of the intrinsic brain architecture in autism. *Molecular Psychiatry*. 2014;19:659–67.
60. Schwarz AJ and McGonigle J. Negative edges and soft thresholding in complex network analysis of resting state functional connectivity data. *Neuroimage*. 2011;55:1132–46.
61. Tomlinson CE, Laurienti PJ, Lyday RG, and Simpson SL. A regression framework for brain network distance metrics. *Network Neuroscience*. 2022;6:49–68.
62. Shmueli G. To Explain or to Predict? *Statistical Science*. 2010;25:289–310.
63. Altman DG and Lyman GH. Methodological challenges in the evaluation of prognostic factors in breast cancer. *Prognostic variables in node-negative and node-positive breast cancer*. 1998:379–93.
64. Harrell F. *Regression modeling strategies: with applications to linear models, logistic and ordinal regression, and survival analysis*. Springer Series in Statistics. Springer International Publishing, 2017.
65. Hastie T, Tibshirani R, Friedman JH, and Friedman JH. *The elements of statistical learning: data mining, inference, and prediction*. Vol. 2. Springer, 2009.
66. Frisch R. *Statistical confluence analysis by means of complete regression systems*. (No Title). 1934.
67. Hastie T, Tibshirani R, and Wainwright M. *Statistical learning with sparsity: the lasso and generalizations*. CRC press, 2015.
68. Akaike H. Information theory and the maximum likelihood principle. In (BN Petrov & F. Csäki, Eds.) In: *Proc. 2nd Intl. Symp on Information Theory*. 1973.
69. Schwarz G. Estimating the Dimension of a Model. *The Annals of Statistics*. 1978;6:461–4.
70. Tibshirani R. Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*. 1996;58:267–88.
71. Friedman J, Hastie T, Höfling H, and Tibshirani R. Pathwise Coordinate Optimization. *The Annals of Applied Statistics*. 2007:302–32.
72. Zhao P and Yu B. On model selection consistency of Lasso. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*. 2006;7:2541–63.
73. Zou H. The adaptive lasso and its oracle properties. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. 2006;101:1418–29.
74. Breiman L. Better subset regression using the nonnegative garrote. *Technometrics*. 1995;37:373–84.
75. Yuan M and Lin Y. On the non-negative garrote estimator. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*. 2007;69:143–61.
76. Kipruto E and Sauerbrei W. Exhuming nonnegative garrote from oblivion using suitable initial estimates-illustration in low and high-dimensional real data. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.15592*. 2022.

77. De Boor C and De Boor C. A practical guide to splines. Vol. 27. Springer Verlag New York, 1978.
78. Eilers PH and Marx BD. Flexible smoothing with B-splines and penalties. *Statistical Science*. 1996;11:89–121.
79. Royston P and Altman DG. Regression using fractional polynomials of continuous covariates: parsimonious parametric modelling. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series C: Applied Statistics*. 1994;43:429–53.
80. Perperoglou A, Sauerbrei W, Abrahamowicz M, and Schmid M. A review of spline function procedures in R. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. 2019;19:1–16.
81. Eilers PH and Marx BD. *Practical smoothing: The joys of P-splines*. Cambridge University Press, 2021.
82. Meyer MC. Constrained penalized splines. *Canadian Journal of Statistics*. 2012;40:190–206.
83. Wang JL, Chiou JM, and Müller HG. Functional data analysis. *Annual Review of Statistics and its application*. 2016;3:257–95.
84. Kokoszka P and Reimherr M. *Introduction to functional data analysis*. CRC press, 2017.
85. Ieva F and Paganoni AM. Risk prediction for myocardial infarction via generalized functional regression models. *Statistical Methods in Medical Research*. 2016;25:1648–60.
86. Goldsmith J, Crainiceanu CM, Caffo B, and Reich D. Longitudinal penalized functional regression for cognitive outcomes on neuronal tract measurements. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series C: Applied Statistics*. 2012;61:453–69.
87. Chiou JM and Müller HG. Linear manifold modelling of multivariate functional data. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*. 2014;76:605–26.
88. Tuddenham RD. Physical growth of California boys and girls from birth to eighteen years. *University of California publications in child development*. 1954;1.
89. Ramsay J and Silverman BW. *Functional data analysis (Springer series in statistics)*. 1997.
90. Reiss PT, Goldsmith J, Shang HL, and Ogden RT. Methods for scalar-on-function regression. *International Statistical Review*. 2017;85:228–49.
91. Goldsmith J, Bobb J, Crainiceanu CM, Caffo B, and Reich D. Penalized functional regression. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*. 2011;20:830–51.
92. Heinze G, Baillie M, Lusa L, Sauerbrei W, Schmidt C, Harrell F, and Huebner M. Regression without regrets – initial data analysis is an essential prerequisite to multivariable regression. 2023.
93. Huebner M, Vach W, and Cessie S le. A systematic approach to initial data analysis is good research practice. 2016.
94. Carlin JB and Moreno-Betancur M. On the uses and abuses of regression models: a call for reform of statistical practice and teaching. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.06668*. 2023.
95. Mela CF and Kopalle PK. The impact of collinearity on regression analysis: the asymmetric effect of negative and positive correlations. *Applied Economics*. 2002;34:667–77.
96. Wallisch C, Bach P, Hafermann L, Klein N, Sauerbrei W, Steyerberg EW, Heinze G, Rauch G, and 2 of the STRATOS initiative topic group. Review of guidance papers on regression modeling in statistical series of medical journals. *PloS one*. 2022;17:e0262918.
97. Sauerbrei W, Perperoglou A, Schmid M, Abrahamowicz M, Becher H, Binder H, Dunkler D, Harrell FE, Royston P, Heinze G, et al. State of the art in selection of variables and functional forms in multivariable analysis—outstanding issues. *Diagnostic and Prognostic Research*. 2020;4:1–18.
98. Boulesteix AL, Lauer S, and Eugster MJ. A plea for neutral comparison studies in computational sciences. *PloS one*. 2013;8:e61562.

99. Heinze G and Dunkler D. Five myths about variable selection. *Transplant International*. 2017;30:6–10.
100. Marek S, Tervo-Clemmens B, Calabro FJ, Montez DF, Kay BP, Hatoum AS, Donohue MR, Foran W, Miller RL, Hendrickson TJ, et al. Reproducible brain-wide association studies require thousands of individuals. *Nature*. 2022;603:654–60.

Appendix A: Online supplements to publications

Supplementary Material 1

Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution

Section S1: Additional information regarding the blood analysis data

Table S1. Full subset of the data from the study of Ratzinger et al. (2014) used for the blood cell example in the paper. White blood cells consist of the five subtypes neutrophils eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes and monocytes and hence, their sum equals the white blood cell count.

Observation	Neutrophils (G/L)	Eosinophils (G/L)	Basophils (G/L)	Lymphocytes (G/L)	Monocytes (G/L)	White blood cell count (G/L)	C-reactive protein (mg/dL)
1	11.5	0.0	0.1	0.6	1.1	13.3	15.99
2	13.9	0.0	0.0	3.0	3.3	20.2	13.27
3	13.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	1.1	14.5	14.99
4	11.0	0.1	0.0	0.6	0.8	12.5	9.93
5	10.1	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.8	11.5	16.70
6	4.2	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	6.1	7.74
7	11.9	0.2	0.0	1.4	1.0	14.5	10.13
8	4.5	0.2	0.0	0.7	0.6	6.0	4.86
9	3.5	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	4.0	15.02
10	6.4	0.2	0.0	1.2	0.6	8.4	3.76
11	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.4	12.53
12	3.5	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.4	4.2	15.72
13	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.0	0.5	1.6	1.39
14	10.5	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.3	13.0	7.66
15	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.1	0.9	7.09
16	7.5	0.0	0.0	1.9	0.6	10.0	10.34
17	4.9	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.3	5.5	16.58
18	6.1	0.4	0.1	1.4	0.8	8.8	6.09
19	9.5	0.3	0.0	1.4	0.9	12.1	5.01
20	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.2	1.8	8.28

Section S2: Additional information regarding the climate change example

Figure S1. Autocorrelation (left) and partial autocorrelation (right) function of the residuals of the non-linear regression model for temperature anomalies adjusted by year and CO₂ emission

Table and functional form of the model for temperature anomalies with year and CO₂ emission as independent variables

Table S2. Results of the linear regression model for temperature anomalies adjusted for year linearly and CO₂ emission with natural cubic splines with 5 degrees of freedom. The 95% CI was computed using the HAC estimator.

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error
Intercept	-22.140948	5.6256498
Year	0.011681	0.0029903
ns(carbon_emissions. df = 5)1	-0.506030	0.2515340
ns(carbon_emissions. df = 5)2	-0.985015	0.2430262
ns(carbon_emissions. df = 5)3	-0.513098	0.3244648
ns(carbon_emissions. df = 5)4	-1.151119	0.4600711
ns(carbon_emissions. df = 5)5	-0.393499	0.3535838

The functional form of the linear regression model for the expected value of temperature anomalies adjusted for CO₂ emission with natural cubic splines with 5 degrees of freedom and year linearly is given by

$$E(temp_{anomaly}) = X\hat{\beta}.$$

where $X\hat{\beta} =$

$$\begin{aligned} & -22.140948 + 0.01168096 * year - 0.50603025 * [1] - 0.98501459 * [2] - 0.51309841 * [3] \\ & \quad - 1.1511193 * [4] - 0.3934988 * [5] \end{aligned}$$

and the variable CO₂ emission is pretransformed into the natural cubic spline bases using the *ns* function of the R package *splines* yielding the respective values for [1] - [5].

Sensitivity analysis

Data collected in a time sequence manner typically contains autocorrelated errors since one observation point at a specific time tends to be correlated with its adjacent observation point. Serial correlation of current errors terms with past ones violates the elementary regression model assumption of independent and identically distributed (iid) error terms. This model misspecification can cause distortions in the ordinary least-squares regression procedure similar to the consequences introduced by near collinearity such as biased standard errors of the model parameters.

In order to study the uncertainty inferred by the autocorrelated residuals, a non-linear regression model with ARMA errors was additionally fitted to the climate data example using the `auto.arima` function of the R-package `forecast` (31). Again, the independent variable CO₂ emission was included in the modelling process using natural cubic splines with 5 degrees of freedom and year linearly. For the selection of the ARMA parameters p and q , the lowest bias corrected Akaike information criterion (AICc) value was used. The `auto.arima` function suggested a regression model with ARMA(1.0.2) errors as the best fit to the observed data despite the strong evidence of non-stationarity and trend of the time series provided by the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (TDF=-2.24, $p=0.47$) and the visual time series display in Figure 2. A possible explanation might lie in the structural breaks within the temperature time series causing standard unit root tests to fail as stated by Estrada and Perron (32). The Ljung-Box test was conducted to examine the presence of autocorrelation among the model residuals and gave no evidence for a rejection of the null hypothesis of independence (TLB=0.01, $df=1$, $p=0.93$). The time plot of the residuals, the corresponding ACF, and the distribution of the model residuals were also inspected but did not raise suspicions regarding model violations. Since the estimated regression coefficients of the non-linear regression model with ARMA errors have no straightforward interpretation again only the partial effect plots are illustrated in supplementary figure 2.

Despite the extensive overlap of the partial effect curves corresponding to year and CO₂ emissions, the superimposed partial effect plots generated by the standard regression (`reg`) approach and the regression with ARMA errors (`regARMA`) model illustrates an increased uncertainty of the estimated effect curve in the `regARMA` model as can be seen in supplementary figure 2. The regression model with ARMA(1.2) errors indicates a stronger loss of precision regarding the model parameters than the standard regression approach. Despite these deviations in the spectrum of the confidence interval, the estimated partial effects of both models only show slight differences at the extremes of the data ranges.

Figure S2. Partial effect plots obtained by classical regression and the regression model using ARMA errors to adjust for the serially correlated error terms.

Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling – A scoping review of methods

Supplementary Material S1 – Detailed Methods

1. ADDITIONAL METHODS

Search Strategy

We conducted a scoping review to assess the use of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks in prediction modelling and various field of application in medicine and biology. Relevant studies were identified by searching PubMed, Scopus and Embase published in journals after January 1st, 2000 up until August 31, 2020, using a pairwise combination of two main sets of keywords: (1) words indicative of graph theory (e.g. *network*, *graph-theory*) and (2) words indicative of prediction modelling as well as a set of exclusion keywords to increase the proportion of relevant articles. The keyword fields, which were investigated were the title and the abstract. The two main sets of keywords were used for all databases. Excluding keywords in the query syntax were varied in between the databases depending on the abundance of articles found.

The two main keyword sets and the respective terms used for the search strategy are listed in Supplementary Table 1.

Table S1. Keyword sets used in the search strategy across the databases for article extraction

Keyword Set	Terms	Position
Network	Network parameters OR network variables OR network attributes OR network traits OR network features OR network characteristics OR graph-theory OR graph-theoretic	Title/Abstract
Prediction Modelling	Prognosis OR predictive OR prediction OR predict OR predicting OR predictor OR forecast OR forecasting	Title/Abstract
Exclusion Keywords	NOT neural network	Title/Abstract

	NOT neural networks NOT artificial networks NOT learning network NOT learning networks NOT adversarial network NOT adversarial networks NOT link prediction NOT signal network NOT sensor network	
--	---	--

As an example, the search for the PubMed database can be replicated by the following link:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=%28%22graphtheory%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22graphtheoretic%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22network+parameters%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22network+variables%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22network+attributes%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22network+traits%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22network+features%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22network+characteristics%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D%29+AND+%28%22predictive%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22predictive%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22prediction%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22prognosis%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22predict%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22prediction%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+forecast%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22forecasting%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D%29+NOT+%28%22neural+network%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22neural+networks%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22artificial+networks%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22learning+network%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22learning+networks%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22adversarial+network%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22adversarial+networks%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22link+prediction%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22signal+network%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D+OR+%22sensor+network%22%5BTitle%2FAbstract%5D%29&filter=dates.2000%2F1%2F1-2020%2F8%2F31>

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Article Inclusion:

- (1) The description of a method to include individual-specific networks or their graph-theoretical attributes as independent predictors in prediction modelling.
- (2) The application of a method which includes individual-specific networks or their graph-theoretical attributes as independent predictors in prediction modelling.
- (3) An overview of several methods to include individual-specific networks or their graph-theoretical attributes as independent predictors in prediction modelling (e.g. review article, commentary).

- (4) The comparison of several methods (e.g. via simulation studies) to include individual-specific networks or their graph-theoretical attributes as independent predictors in prediction modelling

Article Exclusion:

- (1) The article is a duplicate (arising from e.g. using two different search engines)
- (2) The article focuses on group-level (multi-individual) networks derived from aggregated data and not on single-individual networks.
- (3) The evaluation of the network characteristics is performed for descriptive purposes of the network itself only but without an outcome of interest.
- (4) The article focuses on using the networks or their attributes to predict further links, node interactions or dynamic change in the networks (i.e. a graph-theoretical feature constitutes the dependent variable and not the independent predictor).
- (5) The term network is used in another context (e.g. to describe a complex pattern, interlinked components) but neither the network nor its graph-theoretical attributes are used in a statistical model.

Selection of Articles

Articles not written in English were excluded. Identified articles by the search strategy stated above were first assessed for eligibility based on the titles. To ensure objectivity of the first reviewer with regard to the inclusion and exclusion of articles, a random subset of articles in each screening phase (250 articles for title screening, 50 for abstract screening, 25 for full-text assessment) was extracted at random and assessed by three additional independent reviewers (GH, FM, MS). Any inconsistencies were discussed and resolved to reach a general consensus. Studies for which we were not able to discern the presumed relevance for the review from the title or abstract were included for further evaluation. After screening of the abstracts, all identified articles were read in full-text and manuscripts which did not focus on prediction modelling with graph-theoretical features derived from individual-specific networks were excluded from the data extraction process. Furthermore, articles were selected based on the inclusion criteria or excluded based on the exclusion criteria prespecified in the protocol of the scoping review. References of the selected articles were checked for articles fulfilling the inclusion criteria of the scoping review. Articles from the references list of selected articles that present a review were only included if the article differentiates itself methodologically from the other studies. In addition, we included articles identified through a manual search of the literature. Title and abstract screening were performed using the package '*revtools*' in the programming language R (Version 4.0.2).

Data Extraction

The scoping review adhered to an a priori protocol and followed the reporting guidelines outlined in the PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR) developed for systematic evidence synthesis from a body of literature heterogeneous in methodology and its fields of application [1]. The PRISMA-ScR checklist corresponding to the review is presented in the Supplementary Material. Further, we considered aspects of Transparent Reporting of a multivariable prediction model for Individual Prognosis Or Diagnosis (TRIPOD) Initiative [2]. However, risk of bias assessment does not constitute a component of a scoping review. Key features of data extraction from the full-text assessment focused on 1) general information on the study (e.g. study objective, study cohort, research discipline, availability of code and data), 2) network analysis such as network construction (e.g. size, setup, network sparsification) and the computed set of graph-theoretical attributes from the individual-specific networks (e.g. local or global, normalization) and 3) the multivariable outcome model including model building (e.g. the aim of the model, study endpoint, sample size, method, candidate predictors, variable selection) and model validation (e.g. internal, external or apparent, discrimination and calibration) and 4) the conduct of the simulation study where appropriate. Data extraction of full-text was conducted in the online survey software Google Forms in which a questionnaire was created with access only for the involved reviewers upon invite from the creator.

However, the search strategy described also has its limitations. The term "network" in particular is a broad and widely used term in a wide variety of contexts. Some exclusion terms were defined to limit the resulting studies, but also means that relevant studies could have been affected by this as well. Furthermore, through cooperation with other independent reviewers (GH, FM, MS), an attempt was made to guarantee the objectivity of the main authors, but the selection and exclusion of papers is still to a certain extent subjective.

2. ADDITIONAL RESULTS

General Findings

Figure S1 presents the distribution of identified articles with respect to year of publication. Apart from the exceptional year 2018 in the left panel of Figure S1, we suspect an ongoing increase in interest in individual-specific networks for the aim of personalized prediction.

Figure S1. Year of publication of the identified studies

Domain-specific findings of the scoping review

Graph-theoretical analysis of (multiple) neuroimaging data modalities has rapidly found application in clinical neuroscience to identify brain network-based biomarkers to predict and diagnose neurological health outcomes such as mental illnesses [3], neurological diseases [4-6], brain injuries [7, 8] or cognitive functioning [9]. Disturbed brain organization and topology have been shown to be indicative of neurological issues and hence make graph-theoretical features well-founded candidates for potential diagnostic biomarkers. For instance, patients with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) had grey matter network measures that were indicative of a more random network topology at the time of first visit, showed a steeper rate of decline in cognitive functioning [4, 10]. A majority of the neurological studies stated small sample size as a limitation of the study which makes statistical power a concern and affects model generalization to unseen data [11-20] but also in other areas small sample size seemed to be an issue [21]. Network analysis in neurological studies has already shown that the brain structure of healthy individuals has certain properties such as balanced integration and segregation, while patients with neurological disorders such as epilepsy approach a random network structure [11].

Table S2. Scale of the graph-theoretical features used as candidate predictors stratified by the area of application

Area of application	Graph-theoretical scale		
	Global	Local	Both

Genomics	0	3	0
Neurology	12	34	29
Pathopsychology	2	1	3
Pathology	0	0	1

Psychological studies were mostly mainly interested in determining the progression and outcome of early-stage psychotic symptoms given self-administered questionnaires for the purpose of routine screening and quantifying symptom severity [22]. To investigate the inherent daily dynamics of self-reported symptoms, vector autoregressive models (VARs) were conducted and associations between symptoms represented the strength of connection within the individualized networks. A highly relevant feature for pathopsychology was centrality to identify highly influential nodes representing centrally connected symptoms or root causes which can then be targeted by therapeutic strategies – so called early warning signals [23]. [21] conducted a proof-of-concept study to exhibit the benefit of adding graph-theoretical features in addition to patient information for the prediction of dropout in psychological treatments and found varying network structures for patient completing and those who drop out of treatment.

For cancer research, the individual-specific gene networks were employed by [24] to capture the heterogeneity of gene-gene interaction networks of breast cancer samples across individuals since according to them, network-based methods have shown more robust and efficient behaviour than single-gene methods for noisy high-throughput data. To identify local gene pair biomarkers for personalized breast cancer prognosis, a Cox proportional hazards regression model was used with prior univariate variable selection and the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO) reducing the number of candidate features from 46,916 to 272 final gene pairs. The individualized perturbation networks were further assessed to determine tipping points of complex disease (cancer) prior to disease deterioration by assessing a composite network score based on the edge weights at every available time point [25, 26] or for exploratory analysis of predictive gene pairs in cancer [27]. Huang et al. [28] generated perturbed individual-specific gene networks and was able to reach a classification accuracy of 100% using hierarchical clustering based on in-between network distance. In particular, in the network distance matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{N \times N}$ where N denotes the number of individuals, each cell value corresponds to the distance between two sample-specific networks defined as the ratio of the number of overlapping edges and the total number of edges.

Studies outside of neurology, pathopsychology and cancer research aimed for instance at the diagnosis of muscle disease with a large set of graph-theoretical features (N=44; total number of features N=82) obtained from the individual-specific muscle fibre networks using neural networks [29] or were

focused on individual-specific networks of the heart rate variability to delineate between patients with obstructive sleep apnoea and controls [30].

References

1. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Annals of Internal Medicine*. 2018;169(7):467-73.
2. Collins GS, Reitsma JB, Altman DG, Moons KG. Transparent Reporting of a Multivariable Prediction Model for Individual Prognosis or Diagnosis (TRIPOD) The TRIPOD Statement. *Circulation*. 2015;131(2):211-9.
3. Rashid B, Calhoun V. Towards a brain-based predictive model of mental illness. *Human Brain Mapping*. 2020;41(12):3468-535.
4. Tijms BM, Wink AM, de Haan W, van der Flier WM, Stam CJ, Scheltens P, et al. Alzheimer's disease: connecting findings from graph theoretical studies of brain networks. *Neurobiology of Aging*. 2013;34(8):2023-36.
5. Bernhardt BC, Bonilha L, Gross DW. Network analysis for a network disorder: the emerging role of graph theory in the study of epilepsy. *Epilepsy & Behavior*. 2015;50:162-70.
6. Guye M, Bettus G, Bartolomei F, Cozzone PJ. Graph theoretical analysis of structural and functional connectivity MRI in normal and pathological brain networks. *Magnetic Resonance Materials in Physics, Biology and Medicine*. 2010;23(5):409-21.
7. Imms P, Clemente A, Cook M, D'Souza W, Wilson PH, Jones DK, et al. The structural connectome in traumatic brain injury: A meta-analysis of graph metrics. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*. 2019;99:128-37.
8. Caeyenberghs K, Verhelst H, Clemente A, Wilson PH. Mapping the functional connectome in traumatic brain injury: What can graph metrics tell us? *NeuroImage*. 2017;160:113-23.
9. Yamashita M, Kawato M, Imamizu H. Predicting learning plateau of working memory from whole-brain intrinsic network connectivity patterns. *Scientific Reports*. 2015;5(1):1-8.
10. Dicks E, Tijms BM, Ten Kate M, Gouw AA, Benedictus MR, Teunissen CE, et al. Gray matter network measures are associated with cognitive decline in mild cognitive impairment. *Neurobiology of Aging*. 2018;61:198-206.
11. Babajani-Feremi A, Noorizadeh N, Mudigoudar B, Wheless JW. Predicting seizure outcome of vagus nerve stimulation using MEG-based network topology. *NeuroImage: Clinical*. 2018;19:990-9.
12. Bataille D, Eixarch E, Figueras F, Muñoz-Moreno E, Bargallo N, Illa M, et al. Altered small-world topology of structural brain networks in infants with intrauterine growth restriction and its association with later neurodevelopmental outcome. *NeuroImage*. 2012;60(2):1352-66.
13. Jie B, Zhang D, Wee CY, Shen D. Topological graph kernel on multiple thresholded functional connectivity networks for mild cognitive impairment classification. *Human Brain Mapping*. 2014;35(7):2876-97.
14. Khazaei A, Ebrahimzadeh A, Babajani-Feremi A. Identifying patients with Alzheimer's disease using resting-state fMRI and graph theory. *Clinical Neurophysiology*. 2015;126(11):2132-41.
15. Sun Y, Bi Q, Wang X, Hu X, Li H, Li X, et al. Prediction of conversion from amnesic mild cognitive impairment to Alzheimer's disease based on the brain structural connectome. *Frontiers in Neurology*. 2019;9:1178.
16. Wee C-Y, Yap P-T, Zhang D, Denny K, Browndyke JN, Potter GG, et al. Identification of MCI individuals using structural and functional connectivity networks. *NeuroImage*. 2012;59(3):2045-56.
17. Wee C-Y, Yap P-T, Li W, Denny K, Browndyke JN, Potter GG, et al. Enriched white matter connectivity networks for accurate identification of MCI patients. *NeuroImage*. 2011;54(3):1812-22.
18. Du J, Wang Y, Zhi N, Geng J, Cao W, Yu L, et al. Structural brain network measures are superior to vascular burden scores in predicting early cognitive impairment in post stroke patients with small vessel disease. *NeuroImage: Clinical*. 2019;22:101712.
19. Sen B, Bernstein GA, Mueller BA, Cullen KR, Parhi KK. Sub-graph entropy based network approaches for classifying adolescent obsessive-compulsive disorder from resting-state functional MRI. *NeuroImage: Clinical*. 2020;26:102208.

20. Liu L, Zhang H, Wu J, Yu Z, Chen X, Reikik I, et al. Overall survival time prediction for high-grade glioma patients based on large-scale brain functional networks. *Brain Imaging Behaviour*. 2019;13(5):1333-51.
21. Lutz W, Schwartz B, Hofmann SG, Fisher AJ, Husen K, Rubel JA. Using network analysis for the prediction of treatment dropout in patients with mood and anxiety disorders: A methodological proof-of-concept study. *Scientific Reports*. 2018;8(1):1-9.
22. Booij SH, Wichers M, De Jonge P, Sytema S, Van Os J, Wunderink L, et al. Study protocol for a prospective cohort study examining the predictive potential of dynamic symptom networks for the onset and progression of psychosis: the Mapping Individual Routes of Risk and Resilience (Mirorr) study. *BMJ Open*. 2018;8(1).
23. Fried EI, van Borkulo CD, Cramer AO, Boschloo L, Schoevers RA, Borsboom D. Mental disorders as networks of problems: a review of recent insights. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*. 2017;52(1):1-10.
24. Zhu K, Pian C, Xiang Q, Liu X, Chen Y. Personalized analysis of breast cancer using sample-specific networks. *PeerJ*. 2020;8:e9161.
25. Liu X, Chang X, Leng S, Tang H, Aihara K, Chen L. Detection for disease tipping points by landscape dynamic network biomarkers. *National Science Review*. 2019;6(4):775-85.
26. Yu X, Zhang J, Sun S, Zhou X, Zeng T, Chen L. Individual-specific edge-network analysis for disease prediction. *Nucleic Acids Research*. 2017;45(20):e170-e.
27. Park B, Lee W, Park I, Han K. Finding prognostic gene pairs for cancer from patient-specific gene networks. *BMC Medical Genomics*. 2019;12(8):1-14.
28. Huang Y, Chang X, Zhang Y, Chen L, Liu X. Disease characterization using a partial correlation-based sample-specific network. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*. 2020.
29. Sáez A, Rivas E, Montero-Sánchez A, Paradas C, Acha B, Pascual A, et al. Quantifiable diagnosis of muscular dystrophies and neurogenic atrophies through network analysis. *BMC Medicine*. 2013;11(1):1-11.
30. Dong Z, Li X, Chen W. Frequency network analysis of heart rate variability for obstructive apnea patient detection. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*. 2017;22(6):1895-905.

Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	1,4-6, 20,23
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	1-2
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	3-4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	4
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	SM1
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	5, SM1
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	5, SM1
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	SM1
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	5,SM1
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	5,SM1,F2
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	SM1, SM2
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	NA

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	5,6, SM1, SM2
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	6-7, F2
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	6-7, SM1
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	NA
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	SM1
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	F2-7, T1-2 6-20
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	20
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	23, SM1
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	20-24
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	24

JBI = Joanna Briggs Institute; PRISMA-ScR = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews.

* Where *sources of evidence* (see second footnote) are compiled from, such as bibliographic databases, social media platforms, and Web sites.

† A more inclusive/heterogeneous term used to account for the different types of evidence or data sources (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy documents) that may be eligible in a scoping review as opposed to only studies. This is not to be confused with *information sources* (see first footnote).

‡ The frameworks by Arksey and O'Malley (6) and Levac and colleagues (7) and the JBI guidance (4, 5) refer to the process of data extraction in a scoping review as data charting.

§ The process of systematically examining research evidence to assess its validity, results, and relevance before using it to inform a decision. This term is used for items 12 and 19 instead of "risk of bias" (which is more applicable to systematic reviews of interventions) to include and acknowledge the various sources of evidence that may be used in a scoping review (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy document).

From: Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169:467–473. doi: [10.7326/M18-0850](https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850).

Appendix B: Curriculum Vitae

Mariella Gloria GREGORICH

Curriculum Vitae

EDUCATION

03/2020 - ONGOING	PhD Program Medical Informatics, Biostatistics & Complex Systems DOCTORAL THESIS: <i>"Statistical Approaches for Handling Complex Correlation Structures in Prediction Modelling"</i> , funded by the DOC fellowship from the Austrian Academy of Sciences SUPERVISOR: Ao. Univ. Prof. Dr. Georg Heinze UNIVERSITY: Institute for Clinical Biometry, Center for Medical Data Science (CeDas), Medical University of Vienna, Austria
10/2015 - 03/2019	Dipl.-Ing. Biomedical Engineering (MSc equivalent) MASTER THESIS: <i>"Detecting and Understanding Glioblastoma Multiforme Using Convolutional Neural Networks"</i> SUPERVISORS: Assoc.-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Georg Langs and Univ.-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Peter Filzmoser UNIVERSITY: University of Technology, Vienna, Austria
10/2015 - 05/2018	Dipl.-Ing. Technical Mathematics (MSc equivalent) MASTER THESIS: <i>"A comparison of methods for causal inference with a rare binary outcome"</i> SUPERVISORS: Ao. Univ. Prof. Dr. Georg Heinze and Univ.-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr.techn. Peter Filzmoser UNIVERSITY: University of Technology, Vienna, Austria
09/2016 - 01/2017	ERASMUS European Exchange Program at the University of Bath, UK
10/2011 - 10/2015	BSc Technical Mathematics BACHELOR THESIS: <i>"Simulation of Colon Carcinoma Prevention in Austria - Importance of Risk Factors and Evaluation of Screening Programs"</i> SUPERVISOR: Ao.Univ.-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Felix Breitenecker UNIVERSITY: University of Technology, Vienna, Austria

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

Project lead at the Medical University of Vienna

07/2022 - ONGOING	Institute of Clinical Biometry, Center for Medical Data Science (CeDas), Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria.
-------------------	---

Biostatistician at the Medical University of Vienna

12/2019 - 06/2022	Division of Nephrology and Dialysis, University Clinic Internal Medicine III & Institute of Clinical Biometry, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria.
-------------------	---

Statistical research fellow at the University of Technology Vienna

08/2019 - 11/2019 | Research group Computational Statistics, Institute of Statistics and Mathematical Methods in Economics, University of Technology Vienna, Vienna, Austria.

Statistical research fellow at the Medical University of Vienna

08/2019 - 11/2019 | Institute of Medical Statistics, Center for Medical Data Science (CeDas), Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria

Summer Internship at the Austrian Federal Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)

07/2017 - 09/2017 | Reference Center for Infection Epidemiology in Vienna at the Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene Vienna of the Austrian Federal Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)

Summer Internship at the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)

08/2015 - 09/2015 | Department Health & Environment in the business field Biomedical Systems of the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)

Summer Internship at the Medical University of Vienna

07/2013 - 08/2013 | Institute of Clinical Biometry at the Center for Medical Statistics, Informatics and Intelligent Systems (CeMSIIS); Medical University Vienna, Austria

Summer internship at the Austrian Federal Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)

07/2011 | Reference Center for Anthropogenic Infections in Vienna / Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene Vienna of the Austrian Federal Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)
ADD. INFORM.: Honoured by the Austrian Ministry of Transport, Innovation and Technology (BMVIT) for outstanding performance

AWARDS, HONORS & FELLOWSHIPS

06/2022 - 06/2024 | Recipient of the DOC Fellowship from the Austrian Academy of Sciences for the doctoral research project conducted at the Institute of Clinical Biometrics, Center for Medical Data Science (CeDaS), at the Medical University of Vienna, Austria

2019 | Award from the Austrian Statistical Society in the category of Applied Statistics for the master thesis in Technical Mathematics

2019 | Dr. Maria Schaumayer Foundation Prize for excellence in the master thesis in Biomedical Engineering

08/2012 | Invitation to the Alpbach Technology Forum by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology (BMVIT) in Alpbach, Austria

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

2023 | Workshop for medical students: "Hochschulschriften erfolgreich verfassen" (nominated for the Ars Docendi National Award for Excellence in Teaching 2023)

2023 | Methodenseminar Statistik - Statistical seminar to support medical students in writing their thesis

2021 - 2023	Scientific Study Module (SSM3) - Seminar on statistical software
2021 - 2024	Scientific Study Module (SSM2) - Statistical methods in medical research Medical University of Vienna
09/2015 - 02/2016	Tutor for the refresher course of mathematics (AKMATH, Auffrischkurs Mathematik) for students at the University of Technology Vienna University of Technology Vienna, Austria
2014 - 2018	Online mentoring for students in Applied Mathematics at the University of Technology Vienna
2012 - 2019	Lectures in secondary schools on "Women in technical studies", participation in the FIT (germ. "Frauen in die Technik", engl. "Women in Technology") information days at the University of Technology Vienna COMPANY: FIT project of the information center "Sprungbrett" funded by the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science, and Research

LANGUAGES

NATIVE	German
FLUENT	English (Cambridge Certificate Advanced)
INTERMEDIATE	French
BASIC	Spanish

CODING PROFICIENCY

ADVANCED:	R (Markdown, Quarto, Shiny), LaTeX
INTERMEDIATE:	Python, AnyLogic, SPSS
BASIC:	C, C++, Matlab, Maple, HTML/PHP

TALKS & CONFERENCES

Invited talks

09/2021	<i>Using subject-specific networks for prediction modelling: methodological aspects and challenges</i> M. Gregorich, F. Melograna, M. Sunqvist, S. Michiels, K. Van Steen, G. Heinze Young Statisticians Session XXXIInd Conference of the Austro-Swiss Region (ROeS) of the International Biometric Society, Salzburg Austria
09/2020	<i>A comparison of methods for causal inference with a rare binary outcome</i> M. Gregorich and G. Heinze Young Statisticians Session 65th Annual Meeting of the German Association for Medical Informatics, Biometry and Epidemiology (GMDS), Meeting of the Central European Net- work (CEN: German Region, Austro-Swiss Region and Polish Region) of the International Biometric Society (IBS) including the 66th Biometric Collo- quium of the German Region (GMDS&IBS-CEN 2020), virtuell conference

Contributed Talks & Posters

- 11/2023 | *Correlated predictors: is variable omission a good default solution?*
M. Gregorich, S. Strohmaier, D. Dunkler and G. Heinze
Workshop of the project "Statistical Model Building Strategies for Cardiologic Applications - New results and future challenges"
Oral presentation
- 09/2023 | *Individual-specific network inference for prediction modelling: a plasmode simulation study*
M. Gregorich, SL Simpson and G. Heinze
6th Conference of the Central European Network (CEN), Basel Switzerland
Oral presentation
- 08/2023 | *Variable selection with 'too' many zero-inflated predictors*
M. Gregorich, M. Kammer and G. Heinze
44th Conference of the International Society for Clinical Biostatistics (ISCB44), Milan, Italy
Oral presentation
- 08/2022 | *Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction*
M. Gregorich and G. Heinze
24th International Conference on Computational Statistics (COMPSTAT), Bologna, Italy
Oral presentation
- 08/2022 | *Flexible parametrization of individual sparsified networks for prediction: a proof-of-concept*
M. Gregorich and G. Heinze
43rd Annual Conference of the International Society of Biostatistics (ISCB43), Newcastle, UK
Oral presentation
- 07/2022 | *Prediction modelling with individual-specific networks: a methodological review*
M. Gregorich and G. Heinze
International Biometric Conference (IBC), Riga, Latvia
Oral presentation
- 03/2022 | *Improved prediction of renal function decline by model updating*
M. Gregorich, M. Kammer, G. Heinze, R. Oberbauer
6th Conference of the Deutsche Arbeitsgemeinschaft Statistik (DAGStat), Hamburg, Germany
Talklet
- 07/2021 | *Subject-specific networks as features for predictive modelling - A scoping review of methods*
M. Gregorich, F. Melograna, M. Sunqvist, S. Michiels, K. Van Steen, G. Heinze
42nd Conference of the International Society for Clinical Biostatistics (ISCB42), virtual conference
Talklet

- 08/2020 | *Comparison of methods for causal inference with a rare binary outcome*
M. Gregorich and G. Heinze
41st Conference of the International Society for Clinical Biostatistics (ISCB41), virtual conference
Poster
- 10/2016 | *Cost-effectiveness analysis of colorectal cancer screening in Austria and assessment of the impact of cancer-causing risk factors*
M. Gregorich, C. Urach, F. Breitenecker
International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR) in Vienna, Austria
Poster

Courses

- 09/2020 | *Practical Smoothing. The Joys of P-splines*
held by Paul Eilers and organized by L-Biostat (KU Leuven, Belgium)
Leuven, Belgium

PUBLICATIONS

1. GREGORICH, M., KAMMER, M., MISCHAK, H., AND HEINZE, G. Prediction modelling with many correlated and zero-inflated predictors: assessing a nonnegative garrote approach. *arXiv preprint:2402.02064* (2024)
2. GREGORICH, M., SIMPSON, S. L., AND HEINZE, G. Flexible parametrization of graph-theoretical features from individual-specific networks for prediction. *arXiv preprint:2308.15365* (2023)
3. JABBOUR, R., HEINZEL, A., REINDL-SCHWAIGHOFER, R., GREGORICH, M., REGELE, H., KOZAKOWSKI, N., KLÄGER, J., FISCHER, G., KAINZ, A., BECKER, J. U., ET AL. Early progression of chronic histologic lesions in kidney transplant biopsies is not associated with hla histocompatibility. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation* (2023), gfad246
4. KAMMER, M., HEINZEL, A., HU, K., MEISELBACH, H., GREGORICH, M., BUSCH, M., DUFFIN, K. L., GOMEZ, M. F., ECKARDT, K.-U., OBERBAUER, R., ET AL. Different roles of protein biomarkers predicting egfr trajectories in people with chronic kidney disease and diabetes mellitus: a nationwide retrospective cohort study. *Cardiovascular Diabetology* 22, 1 (2023), 74
5. GREGORICH, M., KAMMER, M., HEINZEL, A., BÖGER, C., ECKARDT, K.-U., HEERSPINK, H. L., JUNG, B., MAYER, G., MEISELBACH, H., SCHMID, M., ET AL. Development and validation of a prediction model for future estimated glomerular filtration rate in people with type 2 diabetes and chronic kidney disease. *JAMA Network Open* 6, 4 (2023), e231870–e231870
6. ASCHAUER, C., JELENCICS, K., HU, K., GREGORICH, M., REINDL-SCHWAIGHOFER, R., WENDA, S., WEKERLE, T., HEINZEL, A., AND OBERBAUER, R. Effects of reduced-dose anti-human t-lymphocyte globulin on overall and donor-specific t-cell repertoire reconstitution in sensitized kidney transplant recipients. *Frontiers in Immunology* 13 (2022), 843452
7. GREGORICH, M., MELOGRANA, F., SUNQVIST, M., MICHIELS, S., VAN STEEN, K., AND HEINZE, G. Individual-specific networks for prediction modelling—a scoping review of methods. *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 22, 1 (2022), 62
8. ASCHAUER, C., JELENCICS, K., HU, K., HEINZEL, A., GREGORICH, M., VETTER, J., SCHALLER, S., WINKLER, S. M., WEINBERGER, J., PIMENOV, L., ET AL. Prospective tracking of donor-reactive t-cell clones in the circulation and rejecting human kidney allografts. *Frontiers in Immunology* 12 (2021), 750005
9. GREGORICH, M., HEINZEL, A., KAMMER, M., MEISELBACH, H., BÖGER, C., ECKARDT, K.-U., MAYER, G., HEINZE, G., AND OBERBAUER, R. A prediction model for the decline in renal function in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus: study protocol. *Diagnostic and Prognostic Research* 5 (2021), 1–9
10. GREGORICH, M., STROHMAIER, S., DUNKLER, D., AND HEINZE, G. Regression with highly correlated predictors: variable omission is not the solution. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, 8 (2021), 4259
11. FILZMOSER, P., AND GREGORICH, M. Multivariate outlier detection in applied data analysis: global, local, compositional and cellwise outliers. *Mathematical Geosciences* 52, 8 (2020), 1049–1066
12. SANDNER, S. E., NOLZ, R., LOEWE, C., GREGORICH, M., HEINZE, G., ANDREAS, M., KOLH, P., ZIMPFER, D., AND LAUFER, G. Routine preoperative aortic computed tomography angiography is associated with reduced risk of stroke in coronary artery bypass grafting: a propensity-matched analysis. *European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery* 57, 4 (2020), 684–690

February 6, 2024